

Supplementary File 2

Documentation of the Article Screening Process: Scopus Database

This document is provided to ensure full transparency and reproducibility of the article selection process, as detailed in the PRISMA diagram (Figure 1) and the Methods section of the main manuscript. It contains the complete list of all articles initially identified in the **Scopus** database search.

Legend for Screening Decisions

Each article in the list below is color-coded to indicate the outcome of the screening process. The totals correspond to the numbers presented in the study selection diagram.

- **Blue highlight:** Article was selected for full-text reading and was **included** in the final review. **(Total: 149)**
- **Red highlight:** Article was **excluded** during the title and abstract screening phase as it did not meet the pre-defined inclusion criteria. **(Total: 151)**
- **Orange highlight:** Article was identified as a **duplicate** of a record from another database and was removed prior to the screening phase. **(Total: 63)**

- 1) K.K., Kalasi, Keith K., D.M., Fitzpatrick, Daniel Mark, D.M., Stone, Diana M., T., Guttin, Talia, A., Alhassan, Andy

AUTHOR FULL NAMES: Kalasi, Keith K. (57213601975); Fitzpatrick, Daniel Mark (35760138300); Stone, Diana M. (24470145200); Guttin, Talia (56856798100); Alhassan, Andy (59790999800)

57213601975; 35760138300; 24470145200; 56856798100; 59790999800

Grenadian cats as potential reservoir for *Leptospira*

(2024) PLOS Neglected Tropical Diseases, 18 (12), art. no. e0012784

DOI: 10.1371/journal.pntd.0012784

[https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85215144755&doi=10.1371%2Fjournal.pntd.0012784&partnerID=40&md5=593ecab7a8614bb56454a14dfbd18cf9)

[85215144755&doi=10.1371%2Fjournal.pntd.0012784&partnerID=40&md5=593ecab7a8614bb56454a14dfbd18cf9](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85215144755&doi=10.1371%2Fjournal.pntd.0012784&partnerID=40&md5=593ecab7a8614bb56454a14dfbd18cf9)

- 2) DOCUMENT TYPE: Article

OPEN ACCESS: ALL OPEN ACCESS; GOLD OPEN ACCESS

P., Petakh, Pavlo, W.K., Huber, Wolfgang K., O.M., Kamyshnyi, Oleksandr Mychailovich

AUTHOR FULL NAMES: Petakh, Pavlo (57475779000); Huber, Wolfgang K. (22135017800); Kamyshnyi, Oleksandr Mychailovich (56351419900)

57475779000; 22135017800; 56351419900

Geographical factors and air raid alarms influence leptospirosis epidemiology in Ukraine (2018–2023)

(2024) One Health, 19, art. no. 100944

DOI: 10.1016/j.onehlt.2024.100944

[https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85210065184&doi=10.1016%2Fj.onehlt.2024.100944&partnerID=40&md5=8d231ac3386ae13eb78c992e800bc461)

[85210065184&doi=10.1016%2Fj.onehlt.2024.100944&partnerID=40&md5=8d231ac3386ae13eb78c992e800bc461](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85210065184&doi=10.1016%2Fj.onehlt.2024.100944&partnerID=40&md5=8d231ac3386ae13eb78c992e800bc461)

3) DOCUMENT TYPE: Article
OPEN ACCESS: ALL OPEN ACCESS; GOLD OPEN ACCESS

Y., Sato, Yukuto, K., Tsurui-Sato, Kaori, Y., Uchima, Yoichiro, C.A., Udui, Cheryl Ann, O., Lorin, Osiro, K., Rengulbai, Kashgar, C., Toma, Claudia, R., Suzuki, Ryo
AUTHOR FULL NAMES: Sato, Yukuto (23393502000); Tsurui-Sato, Kaori (57217420631); Uchima, Yoichiro (59337082200); Udui, Cheryl Ann (59337375600); Lorin, Osiro (59337837700); Rengulbai, Kashgar (16240030700); Toma, Claudia (57210368337); Suzuki, Ryo (59255360000)
23393502000; 57217420631; 59337082200; 59337375600; 59337837700; 16240030700; 57210368337; 59255360000

A systematic survey of environmental DNA in Palau's lakes and waterfalls reveals an increase in *Leptospira* levels after flooding

(2024) *One Health*, 19, art. no. 100898

DOI: 10.1016/j.onehlt.2024.100898

[https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85204544562&doi=10.1016%2Fj.onehlt.2024.100898&partnerID=40&md5=ee83e88951894c1ad07d92774121748b)

[85204544562&doi=10.1016%2Fj.onehlt.2024.100898&partnerID=40&md5=ee83e88951894c1ad07d92774121748b](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85204544562&doi=10.1016%2Fj.onehlt.2024.100898&partnerID=40&md5=ee83e88951894c1ad07d92774121748b)

4) DOCUMENT TYPE: Article
OPEN ACCESS: ALL OPEN ACCESS; GOLD OPEN ACCESS

O.J., Ifejube, O. J., S.L., Kuriakose, Sekhar Lukose, A.S.N., TS, Anish Surendran Nair, C.J., Van Westen, Cees J., J.I., Blanford, Justine I.

AUTHOR FULL NAMES: Ifejube, O. J. (57929164000); Kuriakose, Sekhar Lukose (24399700800); TS, Anish Surendran Nair (57204557549); Van Westen, Cees J. (6701664942); Blanford, Justine I. (36499154600)

57929164000; 24399700800; 57204557549; 6701664942; 36499154600

Analysing the outbreaks of leptospirosis after floods in Kerala, India

(2024) *International Journal of Health Geographics*, 23 (1), art. no. 11

DOI: 10.1186/s12942-024-00372-9

[https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85192946746&doi=10.1186%2Fs12942-024-00372-9&partnerID=40&md5=b5931353fad6040e293ca456e ECB945a)

[85192946746&doi=10.1186%2Fs12942-024-00372-](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85192946746&doi=10.1186%2Fs12942-024-00372-9&partnerID=40&md5=b5931353fad6040e293ca456e ECB945a)

[9&partnerID=40&md5=b5931353fad6040e293ca456e ECB945a](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85192946746&doi=10.1186%2Fs12942-024-00372-9&partnerID=40&md5=b5931353fad6040e293ca456e ECB945a)

5) DOCUMENT TYPE: Article
OPEN ACCESS: ALL OPEN ACCESS; GOLD OPEN ACCESS; GREEN FINAL OPEN ACCESS; GREEN OPEN ACCESS

Y., Jin, Yong, W., Lan, Wei, X., Chen, Xiaodong, W., Liu, Wu, W., Luo, Weiliang, S., Chen, Suqin

AUTHOR FULL NAMES: Jin, Yong (58821070600); Lan, Wei (57405620300); Chen, Xiaodong (58820326800); Liu, Wu (57847808900); Luo, Weiliang (14056520100); Chen, Suqin (57192605373)

58821070600; 57405620300; 58820326800; 57847808900; 14056520100; 57192605373

A rare case of anti-DPPX encephalitis combined with neuroleptospirosis

(2024) BMC Neurology, 24 (1), art. no. 34
DOI: 10.1186/s12883-024-03538-x
<https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85182676613&doi=10.1186%2Fs12883-024-03538-x&partnerID=40&md5=2227e0024bc21c8a7ea7b9462dce0d6f>

6) DOCUMENT TYPE: Article

OPEN ACCESS: ALL OPEN ACCESS; GOLD OPEN ACCESS; GREEN FINAL OPEN ACCESS; GREEN OPEN ACCESS

Y., Wu, Yao, B., Wen, Bo, D., Gasevic, Danijela, J.A., Patz, Jonathan A., A.P., Haines, Andy P., K.L., Ebi, Kristie L., V.S.G., Murray, Virginia S.G., S., Li, Shanshan, Y., Guo, Yuming

AUTHOR FULL NAMES: Wu, Yao (57218856723); Wen, Bo (57207310745); Gasevic, Danijela (40461245300); Patz, Jonathan A. (7005533678); Haines, Andy P. (19334435800); Ebi, Kristie L. (35428937200); Murray, Virginia S.G. (7005163697); Li, Shanshan (57216631901); Guo, Yuming (55712472800)
57218856723; 57207310745; 40461245300; 7005533678; 19334435800; 35428937200; 7005163697; 57216631901; 55712472800

Climate Change, Floods, and Human Health.

(2024) New England Journal of Medicine, 391 (20), pp. 1949 - 1958

DOI: 10.1056/NEJMSr2402457

<https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85210340478&doi=10.1056%2FNEJMSr2402457&partnerID=40&md5=7ad8b98f388c666f46f50646098e8811>

7) DOCUMENT TYPE: Article

S., Hota, Saswat, M., Kumar, Manish

AUTHOR FULL NAMES: Hota, Saswat (57225041716); Kumar, Manish (55458141700)
57225041716; 55458141700

Unveiling the impact of *Leptospira* TolC effluxprotein on host tissue adherence, complement evasion, and diagnostic potential

(2024) Infection and Immunity, 92 (11), art. no. e00419-24

DOI: 10.1128/iai.00419-24

<https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85208996796&doi=10.1128%2Fiai.00419-24&partnerID=40&md5=83559c289366d9c6f73d208f3e650064>

8) DOCUMENT TYPE: Article

I., Poulakida, Irene, O.S., Kotsiou, Ourania S., S., Boutlas, Stylianos, D., Stergioula, Despoina, G., Papadamou, Georgia, K.I., Gourgoulisanis, Konstantinos Ioannou, D., Papagiannis, Dimitrios

AUTHOR FULL NAMES: Poulakida, Irene (57219312406); Kotsiou, Ourania S. (56387530800); Boutlas, Stylianos (57207257427); Stergioula, Despoina (57637415400);

Papadamou, Georgia (6507862356); Gourgoulisanis, Konstantinos Ioannou (7005122973); Papagiannis, Dimitrios (55197265000)
57219312406; 56387530800; 57207257427; 57637415400; 6507862356; 7005122973;
55197265000

Leptospirosis Incidence Post-Flooding Following Storm Daniel: The First Case Series in Greece

(2024) *Infectious Disease Reports*, 16 (5), pp. 880 - 887

DOI: 10.3390/idr16050069

[https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85207561231&doi=10.3390%2Fidr16050069&partnerID=40&md5=caaedbaf5b4dd94ebaac7668172b225)

[85207561231&doi=10.3390%2Fidr16050069&partnerID=40&md5=caaedbaf5b4dd94ebaac7668172b225](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85207561231&doi=10.3390%2Fidr16050069&partnerID=40&md5=caaedbaf5b4dd94ebaac7668172b225)

9) 1DOCUMENT TYPE: Article

OPEN ACCESS: ALL OPEN ACCESS; GOLD OPEN ACCESS

D., Sutiningsih, Dwi, D.P., Sari, Dewi Puspito, C.D., Permatasari, Cintya Dipta, N.A., Azzahra, Nur Azizah, A.J., Rodriguez-Morales, Alfonso J., S., Yuliawati, Sri, N.E., Maharani, Nine Elissa

AUTHOR FULL NAMES: Sutiningsih, Dwi (57194542880); Sari, Dewi Puspito (57292553600); Permatasari, Cintya Dipta (59385066800); Azzahra, Nur Azizah (57226277905); Rodriguez-Morales, Alfonso J. (8886801000); Yuliawati, Sri (57205772140); Maharani, Nine Elissa (59384453300)

57194542880; 57292553600; 59385066800; 57226277905; 8886801000; 57205772140; 59384453300

Geospatial Analysis of Abiotic and Biotic Conditions Associated with Leptospirosis in the Klaten Regency, Central Java, Indonesia

(2024) *Tropical Medicine and Infectious Disease*, 9 (10), art. no. 225

DOI: 10.3390/tropicalmed9100225

[https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85207470794&doi=10.3390%2Ftropicalmed9100225&partnerID=40&md5=59282bff8f643813a6a062443b11dd89)

[85207470794&doi=10.3390%2Ftropicalmed9100225&partnerID=40&md5=59282bff8f643813a6a062443b11dd89](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85207470794&doi=10.3390%2Ftropicalmed9100225&partnerID=40&md5=59282bff8f643813a6a062443b11dd89)

10) DOCUMENT TYPE: Article

OPEN ACCESS: ALL OPEN ACCESS; GOLD OPEN ACCESS; GREEN ACCEPTED OPEN ACCESS; GREEN FINAL OPEN ACCESS; GREEN OPEN ACCESS

F.K., Jones, Forrest K., A.G., Medina, Abigail G., K.R., Ryff, Kyle R., J., Irizarry-Ramos, Jessica, J.M., Wong, Joshua M., E., O'Neill, Eduardo, I.A., Rodríguez, Ismael A., I., Cardona, Iris, L., Hernandez, Lorena, A.C., Hernández-Romieu, Alfonso Claudio
AUTHOR FULL NAMES: Jones, Forrest K. (58711857700); Medina, Abigail G. (59319015800); Ryff, Kyle R. (56440032600); Irizarry-Ramos, Jessica (56423742700); Wong, Joshua M. (55672629500); O'Neill, Eduardo (57201644582); Rodríguez, Ismael A. (59319043700); Cardona, Iris (57224517628); Hernandez, Lorena (57771388700); Hernández-Romieu, Alfonso Claudio (36918568700)

58711857700; 59319015800; 56440032600; 56423742700; 55672629500; 57201644582; 59319043700; 57224517628; 57771388700; 36918568700

Leptospirosis Outbreak in Aftermath of Hurricane Fiona — Puerto Rico, 2022

(2024) Morbidity and Mortality Weekly Report, 73 (35), pp. 763 - 768
DOI: 10.15585/mmwr.mm7335a2
<https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85203420004&doi=10.15585%2Fmmwr.mm7335a2&partnerID=40&md5=dec3bb3159f72637076194e51837f79b>

11) DOCUMENT TYPE: Article
OPEN ACCESS: ALL OPEN ACCESS; GOLD OPEN ACCESS

P., Uribe-Restrepo, Pablo, J., Pérez-García, Janeth, M., Arboleda, Margarita, C.A., Muñoz-Zanzi, Claudia A., P., Agudelo-Flórez, Piedad
AUTHOR FULL NAMES: Uribe-Restrepo, Pablo (58078727000); Pérez-García, Janeth (57193379121); Arboleda, Margarita (6603759847); Muñoz-Zanzi, Claudia A. (6602544065); Agudelo-Flórez, Piedad (6506752132)
58078727000; 57193379121; 6603759847; 6602544065; 6506752132
Clinical presentation of human leptospirosis in febrile patients: Urabá, Colombia
(2024) PLOS Neglected Tropical Diseases, 18 (9), art. no. e0012449
DOI: 10.1371/journal.pntd.0012449
<https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85205526310&doi=10.1371%2Fjournal.pntd.0012449&partnerID=40&md5=200fce4b76d64c7cdf7e783a0908b83e>

12) DOCUMENT TYPE: Article
OPEN ACCESS: ALL OPEN ACCESS; GOLD OPEN ACCESS

J.J., Montenegro-Idrogo, Juan José, D.K., Bonilla-Aldana, D. Katterine, A.J., Rodriguez-Morales, Alfonso J.
AUTHOR FULL NAMES: Montenegro-Idrogo, Juan José (55193461100); Bonilla-Aldana, D. Katterine (57217204705); Rodriguez-Morales, Alfonso J. (8886801000)
55193461100; 57217204705; 8886801000
Risk of human leptospirosis in Colombia: Spatiotemporal analysis and related hydroclimatic factors
(2024) Transactions of the Royal Society of Tropical Medicine and Hygiene, 118 (9), pp. 605 - 615
DOI: 10.1093/trstmh/trae013
<https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85203028226&doi=10.1093%2Ftrstmh%2Ftrae013&partnerID=40&md5=b872aba7f68cb745a5e7c4ddb53b8898>

13) DOCUMENT TYPE: Article

H.V., Manjunathachar, Haranahally Vasanthachar, P.V., Barde, Pradip Vijay, V.K., Chouksey, Vivek Kumar, P., Tiwari, Prakash, B.S., Mathapati, Basavaraj Shrishail, S.K., Shrivastava, Suyesh K., T.K., Chakma, Tapas K.
AUTHOR FULL NAMES: Manjunathachar, Haranahally Vasanthachar (55598123600); Barde, Pradip Vijay (6602277706); Chouksey, Vivek Kumar (57200967606); Tiwari,

Prakash (56154087200); Mathapati, Basavaraj Shrishail (36087657100); Shrivastava, Suyesh K. (57218667958); Chakma, Tapas K. (6506002999)
55598123600; 6602277706; 57200967606; 56154087200; 36087657100; 57218667958;
6506002999

Leptospirosis in central India: A retrospective study to explore burden of tropical illness

(2024) Indian Journal of Medical Microbiology, 51, art. no. 100689

DOI: 10.1016/j.ijmmb.2024.100689

[https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85200109554&doi=10.1016%2Fj.ijmmb.2024.100689&partnerID=40&md5=9128cbc27e8f8985ae70ceb18bb3f456)

[85200109554&doi=10.1016%2Fj.ijmmb.2024.100689&partnerID=40&md5=9128cbc27e8f8985ae70ceb18bb3f456](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85200109554&doi=10.1016%2Fj.ijmmb.2024.100689&partnerID=40&md5=9128cbc27e8f8985ae70ceb18bb3f456)

14) DOCUMENT TYPE: Article

OPEN ACCESS: ALL OPEN ACCESS; GOLD OPEN ACCESS

H.G.A.C., Carvalho, Hanna Gabryella Andrade Costa, D.M., Silva, Danilo Mundim, G.R.D., Rodrigues, Gustavo Roberto Dias, A.H., Gameiro, Augusto Hauber, R.F., Dos Santos, Renata Ferreira, C., Raineri, Camila, A.M.C., Lima-Ribeiro, Anna Monteiro Correia

AUTHOR FULL NAMES: Carvalho, Hanna Gabryella Andrade Costa (59177700200); Silva, Danilo Mundim (57190965920); Rodrigues, Gustavo Roberto Dias (58145944700); Gameiro, Augusto Hauber (24390503300); Dos Santos, Renata Ferreira (59177849300); Raineri, Camila (55192968500); Lima-Ribeiro, Anna Monteiro Correia (56581178300)
59177700200; 57190965920; 58145944700; 24390503300; 59177849300; 55192968500;
56581178300

Estimation of economic losses due to leptospirosis in dairy cattle

(2024) Preventive Veterinary Medicine, 229, art. no. 106255

DOI: 10.1016/j.prevetmed.2024.106255

[https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85196258065&doi=10.1016%2Fj.prevetmed.2024.106255&partnerID=40&md5=2623d7de2070687637c57b8e1546fa77)

[85196258065&doi=10.1016%2Fj.prevetmed.2024.106255&partnerID=40&md5=2623d7de2070687637c57b8e1546fa77](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85196258065&doi=10.1016%2Fj.prevetmed.2024.106255&partnerID=40&md5=2623d7de2070687637c57b8e1546fa77)

15) DOCUMENT TYPE: Article

Z., Akbar, Zainul, n., Ristiyanto, F.D., Handayani, Farida Dwi, S., Sayono, Sayono
AUTHOR FULL NAMES: Akbar, Zainul (59257151300); Ristiyanto, R. (8061570600);
Handayani, Farida Dwi (49963446900); Sayono, Sayono (55843159800)
59257151300; 8061570600; 49963446900; 55843159800

EVALUATION OF RAT DENSITY AND THE ASSOCIATED FACTORS IN LEPTOSPIROSIS ENDEMIC AREAS: THE FIRST REPORT ON THE USE OF BI-INDEX

(2024) Jurnal Kesehatan Lingkungan, 16 (3), pp. 190 - 199

DOI: 10.20473/jkl.v16i3.2024.190-199

[https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85201059005&doi=10.20473%2Fjkl.v16i3.2024.190-199&partnerID=40&md5=ed4c970f3c512dcb5446401ba9cad726)

[85201059005&doi=10.20473%2Fjkl.v16i3.2024.190-199&partnerID=40&md5=ed4c970f3c512dcb5446401ba9cad726](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85201059005&doi=10.20473%2Fjkl.v16i3.2024.190-199&partnerID=40&md5=ed4c970f3c512dcb5446401ba9cad726)

16) DOCUMENT TYPE: Article

OPEN ACCESS: ALL OPEN ACCESS; GOLD OPEN ACCESS

C.M., Vyn, Carys M., K.C., Libera, Kellie C., C.M., Jardine, Claire M., L.E., Grant, Lauren Elizabeth

AUTHOR FULL NAMES: Vyn, Carys M. (59153668100); Libera, Kellie C. (59153841000); Jardine, Claire M. (15843350800); Grant, Lauren Elizabeth (58015050400) 59153668100; 59153841000; 15843350800; 58015050400

Canine leptospirosis: A One Health approach for improved surveillance, prevention, and interdisciplinary collaboration

(2024) Canadian Veterinary Journal, 65 (6), pp. 609 - 612

[https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85195002690&partnerID=40&md5=dbc0a4cc909dcab1b8dcef5de628eb15)

[85195002690&partnerID=40&md5=dbc0a4cc909dcab1b8dcef5de628eb15](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85195002690&partnerID=40&md5=dbc0a4cc909dcab1b8dcef5de628eb15)

17) DOCUMENT TYPE: Article

R.S.H., Bridgemohan, Ronell S.H., M.J., Deitch, Matthew J., E., Harmon, Emily, M.R., Whiles, Matt R., P.C., Wilson, Patrick Chris, E.Z., Bean, Eban Z., P., Bridgemohan, Puran, J.H., Bisesi, Joseph H., J., Nicholas, Jodel, A.S.Z., Redhead, Aaden S.Z.

AUTHOR FULL NAMES: Bridgemohan, Ronell S.H. (6505742693); Deitch, Matthew J. (8712631900); Harmon, Emily (58690695400); Whiles, Matt R. (6701814252); Wilson, Patrick Chris (57209516672); Bean, Eban Z. (16315029600); Bridgemohan, Puran (7801584587); Bisesi, Joseph H. (37090181900); Nicholas, Jodel (58691252400); Redhead, Aaden S.Z. (58692091500)

6505742693; 8712631900; 58690695400; 6701814252; 57209516672; 16315029600;

7801584587; 37090181900; 58691252400; 58692091500

Spatiotemporal assessment of pathogenic *Leptospira* in subtropical coastal watersheds (2024) Journal of Water and Health, 22 (5), pp. 923 - 938

DOI: 10.2166/wh.2024.038

[https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85195005987&doi=10.2166%2Fwh.2024.038&partnerID=40&md5=4048ea331364676e21448071147a5d7a)

[85195005987&doi=10.2166%2Fwh.2024.038&partnerID=40&md5=4048ea331364676e21448071147a5d7a](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85195005987&doi=10.2166%2Fwh.2024.038&partnerID=40&md5=4048ea331364676e21448071147a5d7a)

18) DOCUMENT TYPE: Article

OPEN ACCESS: ALL OPEN ACCESS; GOLD OPEN ACCESS; GREEN ACCEPTED OPEN ACCESS; GREEN OPEN ACCESS

H., Sasikumar, Harishankar, P., Ganeshkumar, Parasuraman, R., Sabarinathan, Ramasamy, P.C., Rubeshkumar, Polani Chandrasekar, V., Venkatasamy, Vettrichelvan, M.V., Murhekar, Manoj Vasant

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59012813200; 54580818000; 57194166219; 57207927634; 57221591262; 35551594800

Rapid assessment of coverage of doxycycline/azithromycin chemoprophylaxis against leptospirosis following floods, Kozhikode district, Kerala, 2018

(2024) Transactions of the Royal Society of Tropical Medicine and Hygiene, 118 (5), pp. 336 - 338

DOI: 10.1093/trstmh/trad092

[https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85192027529&doi=10.1093%2Ftrstmh%2Ftrad092&partnerID=40&md5=9627fa7e477898465154a05f0b17c00b)

[85192027529&doi=10.1093%2Ftrstmh%2Ftrad092&partnerID=40&md5=9627fa7e477898465154a05f0b17c00b](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85192027529&doi=10.1093%2Ftrstmh%2Ftrad092&partnerID=40&md5=9627fa7e477898465154a05f0b17c00b)

19) DOCUMENT TYPE: Article

J.M.O., Girón, José María Ortiz, D.J.O., Díaz, Daniel José Ortiz, Á.B., González, Álvaro Bustos, N.D., Cornejo, Nohora Díaz, L.C., Ruiz, Luis Carlos, M.J.S., de la Rosa, Miguel José Sanz

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59203503200; 59203696600; 59204080500; 59204462600; 57215893665; 59204656400

Clinical hematology of patients with leptospirosis who consult urgently in a hospital in Monteria, Colombia Hematología clínica de pacientes con leptospirosis que consultan de urgencia en un hospital de Montería, Colombia

(2024) Gaceta Medica de Caracas, 132 (2), pp. 472 - 478

DOI: 10.47307/GMC.2024.132.2.18

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[85197527490&doi=10.47307%2FGMC.2024.132.2.18&partnerID=40&md5=b8f29ce28b2204e92d76b2dae995bde2](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85197527490&doi=10.47307%2FGMC.2024.132.2.18&partnerID=40&md5=b8f29ce28b2204e92d76b2dae995bde2)

20) DOCUMENT TYPE: Article

L., Douchet, Léa, C.E.R., Menkès, Christophe Eugène Raoul, V., Herbreteau, Vincent, J., Larrieu, Joséphine, M., Bador, Margot, C., Goarant, Cyrille, M., Mangeas, Morgan

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57222718557; 7102890924; 12142204300; 59047035300; 56634237700; 6603498952; 6508084191

Climate-driven models of leptospirosis dynamics in tropical islands from three oceanic basins

(2024) PLOS Neglected Tropical Diseases, 18 (4), art. no. e0011717

DOI: 10.1371/journal.pntd.0011717

[https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85192237570&doi=10.1371%2Fjournal.pntd.0011717&partnerID=40&md5=4aa9e842128248bc23ee24c703d6f84a)

[85192237570&doi=10.1371%2Fjournal.pntd.0011717&partnerID=40&md5=4aa9e842128248bc23ee24c703d6f84a](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85192237570&doi=10.1371%2Fjournal.pntd.0011717&partnerID=40&md5=4aa9e842128248bc23ee24c703d6f84a)

21) DOCUMENT TYPE: Article

OPEN ACCESS: ALL OPEN ACCESS; GOLD OPEN ACCESS; GREEN FINAL OPEN ACCESS; GREEN OPEN ACCESS

R., Thibeaux, Roman, P., Genthon, Pierre, R., Govan, Rodrigue, N., Selmaoui-Folcher, Nazha, C.M.C., Tramier, Caroline Marie Clémence, M., Kainiu, Malia, M.E., Soupé-Gilbert, Marie Estelle, K., Wijesuriya, Kavya, C., Goarant, Cyrille
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41662312500; 6603278646; 57264469100; 57260506500; 57222595241; 57217129893; 55777279000; 57915898700; 6603498952

Rainfall-driven resuspension of pathogenic *Leptospira* in a leptospirosis hotspot (2024) *Science of the Total Environment*, 911, art. no. 168700

DOI: 10.1016/j.scitotenv.2023.168700

[https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85178194848&doi=10.1016%2Fj.scitotenv.2023.168700&partnerID=40&md5=b59e3fa3b544c27642a820c2793b83f9)

[85178194848&doi=10.1016%2Fj.scitotenv.2023.168700&partnerID=40&md5=b59e3fa3b544c27642a820c2793b83f9](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85178194848&doi=10.1016%2Fj.scitotenv.2023.168700&partnerID=40&md5=b59e3fa3b544c27642a820c2793b83f9)

22) DOCUMENT TYPE: Article

Y.H., Liu, Yu Hsien, Y., Chen, Yuhsuan, C.M., Chen, Chuan Mu

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Fulminant Leptospirosis Presenting with Rapidly Developing Acute Renal Failure and Multiorgan Failure

(2024) *Biomedicines*, 12 (2), art. no. 435

DOI: 10.3390/biomedicines12020435

[https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85185976746&doi=10.3390%2Fbiomedicines12020435&partnerID=40&md5=46e70be7c566400324efd68f6090955d)

[85185976746&doi=10.3390%2Fbiomedicines12020435&partnerID=40&md5=46e70be7c566400324efd68f6090955d](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85185976746&doi=10.3390%2Fbiomedicines12020435&partnerID=40&md5=46e70be7c566400324efd68f6090955d)

23) DOCUMENT TYPE: Article

OPEN ACCESS: ALL OPEN ACCESS; GOLD OPEN ACCESS; GREEN FINAL OPEN ACCESS; GREEN OPEN ACCESS

V.C., Rodríguez-Rodríguez, Virginia Consuelo, A., Castro-Cordero, Ana, A., Calderón-Rangel, Alfonso, E., Martínez-Ibarra, Eidy, M.F., Yasnot-Acosta, María Fernanda, P., Agudelo-Flórez, Piedad, F.P., Monroy, Fernando P.

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35386829200; 58684617600; 35212937500; 58684460400; 15728902800; 6506752132;

7004575854

Acute human leptospirosis in a Caribbean region of Colombia: From classic to emerging risk factors

(2024) *Zoonoses and Public Health*, 71 (1), pp. 107 - 119

DOI: 10.1111/zph.13089

[https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85175967933&doi=10.1111%2Fzph.13089&partnerID=40&md5=83baf934b140c470c6aa6461f2180ffe)

[85175967933&doi=10.1111%2Fzph.13089&partnerID=40&md5=83baf934b140c470c6aa6461f2180ffe](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85175967933&doi=10.1111%2Fzph.13089&partnerID=40&md5=83baf934b140c470c6aa6461f2180ffe)

24) DOCUMENT TYPE: Article

M., Baharom, Mazni, N.B., Ahmad, Norfazilah Binti, R., Hod, Rozita, M.H., Ja'Afar, Mohd Hasni, F.S., Arsad, Fadly Syah, F.T., Tangang, Fredolin T., R., Ismail, Rohaida, N., Mohamed, Norlen, M.F., Mohd Radi, Mohd Firdaus, Y., Osman, Yelmizaitun
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57221653411; 57219909357; 37072342700; 59158156600; 57273535800; 6602356372;

57200387554; 59880362700; 57202038820; 57832735700

Environmental and Occupational Factors Associated with Leptospirosis: A Systematic Review

(2024) *Heliyon*, 10 (1), art. no. e23473

DOI: 10.1016/j.heliyon.2023.e23473

[https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85180477961&doi=10.1016%2Fj.heliyon.2023.e23473&partnerID=40&md5=45c375631424c08c8c8e35d1f7de9ed7)

[85180477961&doi=10.1016%2Fj.heliyon.2023.e23473&partnerID=40&md5=45c375631424c08c8c8e35d1f7de9ed7](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85180477961&doi=10.1016%2Fj.heliyon.2023.e23473&partnerID=40&md5=45c375631424c08c8c8e35d1f7de9ed7)

25) DOCUMENT TYPE: Article

OPEN ACCESS: ALL OPEN ACCESS; GOLD OPEN ACCESS; GREEN FINAL OPEN ACCESS; GREEN OPEN ACCESS

E., Katsafourou, E., F., Nikolaidou, Foteini, E., Nikolaou, E., N., Gaitanis, N., E., Karakasidis, E., E., Potolidis, Evangelos

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59664048900; 59415220500; 59663708300; 59663852700; 59664049000; 8299785100

Leptospirosis outbreak in Magnesia, Central Greece linked to catastrophic floods

(2024) *Hippokratia*, 28 (3), pp. 129 - 133

[https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85219496865&partnerID=40&md5=22be9c8bcff59e71582720164129f2dd)

[85219496865&partnerID=40&md5=22be9c8bcff59e71582720164129f2dd](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85219496865&partnerID=40&md5=22be9c8bcff59e71582720164129f2dd)

26) DOCUMENT TYPE: Article

J.B.N., Tandirerung, Juan Bill Nehemia, E.T., Japanto, Edwin Timoti, A.H.A., Anisa, Andi Hasri Ainun, H.R., Supit, Hary Rudolf

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59546712300; 59546439300; 59546257600; 59546712400

From a sudden flood to a silent gut: a rare case report of paralytic ileus and pulmonary hemorrhage due to leptospirosis

(2024) Romanian Journal of Infectious Diseases, 27 (4), pp. 348 - 356

DOI: 10.37897/RJID.2024.4.11

[https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85217184348&doi=10.37897%2FRJID.2024.4.11&partnerID=40&md5=58e837bb0797b5db)

[85217184348&doi=10.37897%2FRJID.2024.4.11&partnerID=40&md5=58e837bb0797b5db](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85217184348&doi=10.37897%2FRJID.2024.4.11&partnerID=40&md5=58e837bb0797b5db)
[e4fafa77298ecdaa](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85217184348&doi=10.37897%2FRJID.2024.4.11&partnerID=40&md5=58e837bb0797b5db)

27) DOCUMENT TYPE: Article

OPEN ACCESS: ALL OPEN ACCESS; GOLD OPEN ACCESS

Y., Zhang, Yuchou, M., Yin, Mingjing, H., Wen, Hanchun

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VV-ECMO adjuvant therapy for Leptospira complicated with H1N1 infection: a case report

(2024) Frontiers in Medicine, 11, art. no. 1495324

DOI: 10.3389/fmed.2024.1495324

[https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85216246931&doi=10.3389%2Ffmed.2024.1495324&partnerID=40&md5=e9a926fb040b25)

[85216246931&doi=10.3389%2Ffmed.2024.1495324&partnerID=40&md5=e9a926fb040b25](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85216246931&doi=10.3389%2Ffmed.2024.1495324&partnerID=40&md5=e9a926fb040b25)
[d5ef389423072058ee](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85216246931&doi=10.3389%2Ffmed.2024.1495324&partnerID=40&md5=e9a926fb040b25)

28) DOCUMENT TYPE: Article

OPEN ACCESS: ALL OPEN ACCESS; GOLD OPEN ACCESS

M.M., Vidal del Río, Mildre Mercedes, M.A., Jiménez Villa, Marcelo Alejandro

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Risk of human and animal leptospirosis in Ecuador: a multisectoral approach Riesgo de leptospirosis humana y animal en Ecuador. Enfoque multisectorial

(2024) Revista Cubana de Investigaciones Biomedicas, 43, art. no. e3633

[https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85212879695&partnerID=40&md5=f8b05c607e2a25d047356b25d7883cdf)

[85212879695&partnerID=40&md5=f8b05c607e2a25d047356b25d7883cdf](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85212879695&partnerID=40&md5=f8b05c607e2a25d047356b25d7883cdf)

29) DOCUMENT TYPE: Article

G., Guida Acevedo, Guido, R.M., Franco Delgado, Rafael Martín, R.J., Aguilar

Berrezueta, Roberto Javier, K.J., Castillo Aveiga, Kayke Jeampool

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58496482800; 59483519600; 58782751200; 59484053000

Evaluation of knowledge level about leptospirosis in rural area 'San Gabriel del Baba', Ecuador Evaluación del nivel de conocimiento sobre leptospirosis en zona rural "San Gabriel del Baba", Ecuador

(2024) Revista Cubana de Investigaciones Biomedicas, 43, art. no. e3601

[https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85212823646&partnerID=40&md5=2cdca9a45d481ea83f716f2a066091a9)

[85212823646&partnerID=40&md5=2cdca9a45d481ea83f716f2a066091a9](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85212823646&partnerID=40&md5=2cdca9a45d481ea83f716f2a066091a9)

30) DOCUMENT TYPE: Article

B.B., Foltran, Bruno Botega, A.F., Teixeira, Aline F., E.C., Romero, Eliete Caló, L.G.V., Fernandes, Luis Guilherme Virgilio, A.L.T.O., Nascimento, Ana Lúcia Tabet O.

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57224156942; 56622148200; 7103314188; 59012994400; 7006631164

Leucine-rich repeat proteins of *Leptospira interrogans* that interact to host glycosaminoglycans and integrins

(2024) Frontiers in Microbiology, 15, art. no. 1497712

DOI: 10.3389/fmicb.2024.1497712

[https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85211579700&doi=10.3389%2Ffmicb.2024.1497712&partnerID=40&md5=ac862a86b4793a58a47545bf8e877a76)

[85211579700&doi=10.3389%2Ffmicb.2024.1497712&partnerID=40&md5=ac862a86b4793a58a47545bf8e877a76](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85211579700&doi=10.3389%2Ffmicb.2024.1497712&partnerID=40&md5=ac862a86b4793a58a47545bf8e877a76)

31) DOCUMENT TYPE: Article

OPEN ACCESS: ALL OPEN ACCESS; GOLD OPEN ACCESS

E.L., Soares, Emerson Longaretti, S.R., de Mello Schlemper, Susana Regina, V., Schlemper, Valfredo

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59455718900; 55880518700; 6603169998

Behaviour of Moura breed pigs in silvopastoral systems Comportamento de suínos da raça Moura em sistema silvipastoril

(2024) Ciencia Animal Brasileira, 25, art. no. 79178E

DOI: 10.1590/1809-6891v25e-79178E

[https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85210950971&doi=10.1590%2F1809-6891v25e-79178E&partnerID=40&md5=3b1548344297cf5d1fca331c6936f69b)

[85210950971&doi=10.1590%2F1809-6891v25e-](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85210950971&doi=10.1590%2F1809-6891v25e-79178E&partnerID=40&md5=3b1548344297cf5d1fca331c6936f69b)

[79178E&partnerID=40&md5=3b1548344297cf5d1fca331c6936f69b](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85210950971&doi=10.1590%2F1809-6891v25e-79178E&partnerID=40&md5=3b1548344297cf5d1fca331c6936f69b)

32) DOCUMENT TYPE: Article

OPEN ACCESS: ALL OPEN ACCESS; GOLD OPEN ACCESS

N., Soni, Nirali, M.T., Eyre, Max T., F.N., Souza, Fábio Neves, P.J., Diggle, Peter J., A.I.,

Ko, Albert I., M.E., Begon, Michael E., R.W., Pickup, Roger W., J.E., Childs, James E.,

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59351618100; 57218760337; 57191665343; 7006313409; 7007018347; 7006503936; 7006157306; 7101840871; 56072374200; 55252683700

Disentangling the influence of reservoir abundance and pathogen shedding on zoonotic spillover of the *Leptospira* agent in urban informal settlements

(2024) *Frontiers in Public Health*, 12, art. no. 1447592

DOI: 10.3389/fpubh.2024.1447592

[https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85205474806&doi=10.3389%2Ffpubh.2024.1447592&partnerID=40&md5=18ec023503c145d9dc83109069b181a6)

[85205474806&doi=10.3389%2Ffpubh.2024.1447592&partnerID=40&md5=18ec023503c145d9dc83109069b181a6](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85205474806&doi=10.3389%2Ffpubh.2024.1447592&partnerID=40&md5=18ec023503c145d9dc83109069b181a6)

33) DOCUMENT TYPE: Article

OPEN ACCESS: ALL OPEN ACCESS; GOLD OPEN ACCESS

J., Wenderlein, Jasmin, T., Zitzl, Theresa, N., Simon-Dufay, Nathalie, N., Cachet, Nathalie, N., Pantchev, Nikolá, M., Le Guyader, Marine, C., Fontana, Celia, N., Bomchil, Natalia, J.P., Tronel, Jean Philippe, L., Cupillard, Lionel

AUTHOR FULL NAMES: Wenderlein, Jasmin (57222035624); Zitzl, Theresa (57222528123); Simon-Dufay, Nathalie (57191988965); Cachet, Nathalie (56616243600); Pantchev, Nikolá (23489943400); Le Guyader, Marine (57201410446); Fontana, Celia (57188759876); Bomchil, Natalia (6507578066); Tronel, Jean Philippe (7801492207); Cupillard, Lionel (57194270528)

57222035624; 57222528123; 57191988965; 56616243600; 23489943400; 57201410446; 57188759876; 6507578066; 7801492207; 57194270528

Detection and Identification of Pathogenic *Leptospira* spp. Serogroups in Europe between 2017 and 2020 Applying a Novel Gene-Based Molecular Approach

(2024) *Transboundary and Emerging Diseases*, 2024, art. no. 1101841

DOI: 10.1155/2024/1101841

[https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85202600495&doi=10.1155%2F2024%2F1101841&partnerID=40&md5=83689407a608ac5a68f18b63b3ba7cf8)

[85202600495&doi=10.1155%2F2024%2F1101841&partnerID=40&md5=83689407a608ac5a68f18b63b3ba7cf8](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85202600495&doi=10.1155%2F2024%2F1101841&partnerID=40&md5=83689407a608ac5a68f18b63b3ba7cf8)

34) DOCUMENT TYPE: Article

OPEN ACCESS: ALL OPEN ACCESS; HYBRID GOLD OPEN ACCESS

A., Sharma, Aanchal, M.M., Singh, Madhumeet M., P., Kumar, Pravesh, S.D., Thakur, Sidharath Dev, A., Sharma, Akshay

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57214355959; 8963527700; 57212030187; 42862627200; 57210974626

An investigation on infectious etiologies of bovine abortions in Northern Western Himalayan region of Himachal Pradesh

(2024) Indian Journal of Animal Sciences, 94 (4), pp. 325 - 328
DOI: 10.56093/ijans.v94i4.130222
<https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85190304163&doi=10.56093%2Fijans.v94i4.130222&partnerID=40&md5=5f46357fc343dc8918bc234d823bee6>

35) DOCUMENT TYPE: Article
OPEN ACCESS: ALL OPEN ACCESS; GOLD OPEN ACCESS

X., Lu, Xiao, C., Griebisch, Christine, J.M., Norris, Jacqueline Marie, M.P., Ward, Michael P.
AUTHOR FULL NAMES: Lu, Xiao (57428283600); Griebisch, Christine (35558636100); Norris, Jacqueline Marie (7401776731); Ward, Michael P. (55167062100)
57428283600; 35558636100; 7401776731; 55167062100
Landscape, Socioeconomic, and Meteorological Risk Factors for Canine Leptospirosis in Urban Sydney (2017–2023): A Spatial and Temporal Study
(2023) Veterinary Sciences, 10 (12), art. no. 697
DOI: 10.3390/vetsci10120697
<https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85180213063&doi=10.3390%2Fvetsci10120697&partnerID=40&md5=16f5cd6bc30a87bad63e161fa5d9c240>

36) DOCUMENT TYPE: Article
OPEN ACCESS: ALL OPEN ACCESS; GOLD OPEN ACCESS; GREEN OPEN ACCESS

R., Shirzad, Reza, A.A., Alesheikh, Ali Asghar, M., Asgharzadeh, Mojtaba, B., Hoseini, Benyamin, A., Lotfata, Aynaz
AUTHOR FULL NAMES: Shirzad, Reza (57224978117); Alesheikh, Ali Asghar (57193575088); Asgharzadeh, Mojtaba (57925934500); Hoseini, Benyamin (57205270611); Lotfata, Aynaz (57210283819)
57224978117; 57193575088; 57925934500; 57205270611; 57210283819
Spatio-temporal modeling of human leptospirosis prevalence using the maximum entropy model
(2023) BMC Public Health, 23 (1), art. no. 2521
DOI: 10.1186/s12889-023-17391-z
<https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85179924548&doi=10.1186%2Fs12889-023-17391-z&partnerID=40&md5=b2ea78a9059e1f7824ac1523dd80e38c>

37) DOCUMENT TYPE: Article
OPEN ACCESS: ALL OPEN ACCESS; GOLD OPEN ACCESS; GREEN FINAL OPEN ACCESS; GREEN OPEN ACCESS

Antima, S., Banerjee, Sandip
AUTHOR FULL NAMES: Antima (58690599900); Banerjee, Sandip (55335287000)
58690599900; 55335287000
Modeling the dynamics of leptospirosis in India

(2023) Scientific Reports, 13 (1), art. no. 19791
DOI: 10.1038/s41598-023-46326-2
<https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85176432492&doi=10.1038%2Fs41598-023-46326-2&partnerID=40&md5=8bf00a974be0627963ae8b625bab1204>

38) DOCUMENT TYPE: Article
OPEN ACCESS: ALL OPEN ACCESS; GOLD OPEN ACCESS; GREEN FINAL OPEN ACCESS; GREEN OPEN ACCESS

J., Ji, Jianyu, W., Wang, Wei, S., Xiang, Shulin, X., Wei, Xiutian, G., Pang, Guangbao, H., Shi, Huirong, J., Dong, Jinda, J., Pang, Jing
AUTHOR FULL NAMES: Ji, Jianyu (58689168900); Wang, Wei (56948430000); Xiang, Shulin (57200858062); Wei, Xiutian (58689596500); Pang, Guangbao (58689169000); Shi, Huirong (58688505700); Dong, Jinda (58688946000); Pang, Jing (58689378200)
58689168900; 56948430000; 57200858062; 58689596500; 58689169000; 58688505700; 58688946000; 58689378200

Diagnosis of leptospira by metagenomics next-generation sequencing with extracorporeal membrane oxygenation support: a case report

(2023) BMC Infectious Diseases, 23 (1), art. no. 788
DOI: 10.1186/s12879-023-08793-w
<https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85176354763&doi=10.1186%2Fs12879-023-08793-w&partnerID=40&md5=ca0e359a952b7be26310b1715b822641>

39) DOCUMENT TYPE: Article
OPEN ACCESS: ALL OPEN ACCESS; GOLD OPEN ACCESS; GREEN FINAL OPEN ACCESS; GREEN OPEN ACCESS

A.M., Stark, Astrid M., M., Nohrenberg, Michael, A.D.K., Draper, Anthony D.K., K.E., McMahon, Kimberley E., T.A., Hewitt, Thalia A., K., Lomas, Kelly, V.L., Krause, Vicki Lynn

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58886956300; 57472004700; 57111814600; 58886634200; 58886893500; 58886824900; 20234916800

A cluster of leptospirosis cases associated with crocodile workers in the Northern Territory, Australia, 2022

(2023) Communicable Diseases Intelligence, 47
DOI: 10.33321/cdi.2023.47.70
<https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85184990288&doi=10.33321%2Fcdi.2023.47.70&partnerID=40&md5=ee056991f92f08a6d466685cdf1a843d>

40) DOCUMENT TYPE: Article

OPEN ACCESS: ALL OPEN ACCESS; GOLD OPEN ACCESS

M.A., Blaskovich, Mark A.T., P.N., Harris, Patrick N.A.

AUTHOR FULL NAMES: Blaskovich, Mark A.T. (6603840133); Harris, Patrick N.A. (57192903843)

6603840133; 57192903843

Bugs in floods

(2023) *Microbiology Australia*, 44 (4), pp. 176 - 180

DOI: 10.1071/MA23051

[https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85178631705&doi=10.1071%2FMA23051&partnerID=40&md5=b856e5bb65f54a0db7bba7d0f649fc2b)

[85178631705&doi=10.1071%2FMA23051&partnerID=40&md5=b856e5bb65f54a0db7bba7d0f649fc2b](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85178631705&doi=10.1071%2FMA23051&partnerID=40&md5=b856e5bb65f54a0db7bba7d0f649fc2b)

41) DOCUMENT TYPE: Article

OPEN ACCESS: ALL OPEN ACCESS; GOLD OPEN ACCESS

R., Hosking, Rose, K.S., Smurthwaite, Kayla S., S., Hales, Simon, A.M., Richardson, Alice Marion, S.M., Batikawai, Suliasi Mekerusa, A., Lal, Aparna

AUTHOR FULL NAMES: Hosking, Rose (57967956900); Smurthwaite, Kayla S. (57196053993); Hales, Simon (7004550015); Richardson, Alice Marion (16741697900);

Batikawai, Suliasi Mekerusa (58571764000); Lal, Aparna (55163011100)

57967956900; 57196053993; 7004550015; 16741697900; 58571764000; 55163011100

Climate variability and water-related infectious diseases in Pacific Island Countries and Territories, a systematic review

(2023) *PLOS Climate*, 2 (10), art. no. e0000296

DOI: 10.1371/journal.pclm.0000296

[https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85203130528&doi=10.1371%2Fjournal.pclm.0000296&partnerID=40&md5=a6ea801b2bd60f102aaaa94a290a3df1)

[85203130528&doi=10.1371%2Fjournal.pclm.0000296&partnerID=40&md5=a6ea801b2bd60f102aaaa94a290a3df1](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85203130528&doi=10.1371%2Fjournal.pclm.0000296&partnerID=40&md5=a6ea801b2bd60f102aaaa94a290a3df1)

42) DOCUMENT TYPE: Article

OPEN ACCESS: ALL OPEN ACCESS; GOLD OPEN ACCESS

E.M., Rees, Eleanor M., M.L., Batista, Martin Lotto, M., Kama, Mike, A.J., Kucharski, Adam J., C.L., Lau, Colleen L., R., Lowe, Rachel

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57218207228; 57954755000; 55232631100; 54883807400; 57002151900; 36135810500

Quantifying the relationship between climatic indicators and leptospirosis incidence in Fiji: A modelling study

(2023) *PLOS Global Public Health*, 3 (10 October), art. no. e0002400

DOI: 10.1371/journal.pgph.0002400

[https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85195452311&doi=10.1371%2Fjournal.pgph.0002400&partnerID=40&md5=da60346a7f244578335282b926df39bf)

[85195452311&doi=10.1371%2Fjournal.pgph.0002400&partnerID=40&md5=da60346a7f244578335282b926df39bf](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85195452311&doi=10.1371%2Fjournal.pgph.0002400&partnerID=40&md5=da60346a7f244578335282b926df39bf)

43) DOCUMENT TYPE: Article

OPEN ACCESS: ALL OPEN ACCESS; GOLD OPEN ACCESS; GREEN FINAL OPEN ACCESS; GREEN OPEN ACCESS

J.S., Marić, Jelena S., D., Nedic, Drago, B., Vejnović, Branislav, L., Velić, Lejla, S., Obrenović, Sonja

AUTHOR FULL NAMES: Marić, Jelena S. (57204393219); Nedic, Drago (7801384935); Vejnović, Branislav (56377014300); Velić, Lejla (25623939800); Obrenović, Sonja (6602666458)

57204393219; 7801384935; 56377014300; 25623939800; 6602666458

Seroprevalence of serovars of pathogenic leptospira in dogs and red foxes (*Vulpes Vulpes*) from bosnia and herzegovina

(2023) *Acta Veterinaria*, 73 (3), pp. 389 - 404

DOI: 10.2478/acve-2023-0029

[https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85173521487&doi=10.2478%2Facve-2023-0029&partnerID=40&md5=54bc6a533c7bcde157a445b3a50bbc8f)

[85173521487&doi=10.2478%2Facve-2023-](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85173521487&doi=10.2478%2Facve-2023-0029&partnerID=40&md5=54bc6a533c7bcde157a445b3a50bbc8f)

[0029&partnerID=40&md5=54bc6a533c7bcde157a445b3a50bbc8f](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85173521487&doi=10.2478%2Facve-2023-0029&partnerID=40&md5=54bc6a533c7bcde157a445b3a50bbc8f)

44) DOCUMENT TYPE: Article

OPEN ACCESS: ALL OPEN ACCESS; GOLD OPEN ACCESS

N., Sohn-Hausner, Natacha, L.B., Kmetiuk, Louise Bach, E.C., da Silva, Evelyn Cristine, H., Langoni, Hélio, A.W., Biondo, Alexander Welker

AUTHOR FULL NAMES: Sohn-Hausner, Natacha (58516437100); Kmetiuk, Louise Bach (57195902357); da Silva, Evelyn Cristine (57371553500); Langoni, Hélio (6603491394); Biondo, Alexander Welker (56008856900)

58516437100; 57195902357; 57371553500; 6603491394; 56008856900

One Health Approach to Leptospirosis: Dogs as Environmental Sentinels for Identification and Monitoring of Human Risk Areas in Southern Brazil

(2023) *Tropical Medicine and Infectious Disease*, 8 (9), art. no. 435

DOI: 10.3390/tropicalmed8090435

[https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85172138532&doi=10.3390%2Ftropicalmed8090435&partnerID=40&md5=1f6f608d13186c751216defbef66a95f)

[85172138532&doi=10.3390%2Ftropicalmed8090435&partnerID=40&md5=1f6f608d13186c751216defbef66a95f](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85172138532&doi=10.3390%2Ftropicalmed8090435&partnerID=40&md5=1f6f608d13186c751216defbef66a95f)

45) DOCUMENT TYPE: Article

OPEN ACCESS: ALL OPEN ACCESS; GOLD OPEN ACCESS; GREEN FINAL OPEN ACCESS; GREEN OPEN ACCESS

K., Edwards, Kelly, T.R., Nagy, Tibor R., S., Fabiano, Sarah, J., Jacotin, Junior, D., Ellis, David

AUTHOR FULL NAMES: Edwards, Kelly (57225827589); Nagy, Tibor R. (57893219200); Fabiano, Sarah (59891875900); Jacotin, Junior (58397552700); Ellis, David (57197322099) 57225827589; 57893219200; 59891875900; 58397552700; 57197322099

Leptospirosis in the Air: A Case Review Series During Air Medical Transport in Haiti

(2023) *Air Medical Journal*, 42 (5), pp. 380 - 383

DOI: 10.1016/j.amj.2023.05.009

<https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85163379233&doi=10.1016%2Fj.amj.2023.05.009&partnerID=40&md5=dc8fa14e1a1178ab4c01756d184770e1>

46) DOCUMENT TYPE: Article

K., Kamalzadeh, K., M., Esmaelizad, Majid, J., Ghalani, J., P., Khaki, Pejvak, M., Tebianian, Majid

AUTHOR FULL NAMES: Kamalzadeh, K. (58598948100); Esmaelizad, Majid (12902675000); Ghalani, J. (58599508700); Khaki, Pejvak (8963676700); Tebianian, Majid (13002652700)

58598948100; 12902675000; 58599508700; 8963676700; 13002652700

HIGH EXPRESSION OF LIPL21 PROTEIN OF IRANIAN LEPTOSPIRA INTERROGANS IN E. COLI, APPLICABLE FOR DIAGNOSTIC ELISA (2023) Bulgarian Journal of Veterinary Medicine, 26 (3), pp. 342 - 350

DOI: 10.15547/bjvm.2021-0052

[https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85160194775&doi=10.15547%2Fbjvm.2021-0052&partnerID=40&md5=61e487e0dcb1bb966f5abaecbc53d1e0)

[85160194775&doi=10.15547%2Fbjvm.2021-](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85160194775&doi=10.15547%2Fbjvm.2021-0052&partnerID=40&md5=61e487e0dcb1bb966f5abaecbc53d1e0)

[0052&partnerID=40&md5=61e487e0dcb1bb966f5abaecbc53d1e0](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85160194775&doi=10.15547%2Fbjvm.2021-0052&partnerID=40&md5=61e487e0dcb1bb966f5abaecbc53d1e0)

47) DOCUMENT TYPE: Article

OPEN ACCESS: ALL OPEN ACCESS; GOLD OPEN ACCESS

S.R., Rathinam, Sivakumar R., G.J., Kohila, G. Jeya, P.C., Gowri, Priya Chidambaranathan, K.S., Balagiri, Kandasamy S.

AUTHOR FULL NAMES: Rathinam, Sivakumar R. (57210661056); Kohila, G. Jeya (58510983400); Gowri, Priya Chidambaranathan (57191051759); Balagiri, Kandasamy S. (57212309781)

57210661056; 58510983400; 57191051759; 57212309781

Leptospiral uveitis- "Transition 'from epidemic to endemic form" difficulties in laboratory confirmation

(2023) Indian Journal of Ophthalmology, 71 (8), pp. 3031 - 3038

DOI: 10.4103/IJO.IJO_61_23

[https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85166159404&doi=10.4103%2FIJO.IJO_61_23&partnerID=40&md5=16c45d8675e52c1dad67570b910a8de)

[85166159404&doi=10.4103%2FIJO.IJO_61_23&partnerID=40&md5=16c45d8675e52c1dad67570b910a8de](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85166159404&doi=10.4103%2FIJO.IJO_61_23&partnerID=40&md5=16c45d8675e52c1dad67570b910a8de)

48) DOCUMENT TYPE: Article

OPEN ACCESS: ALL OPEN ACCESS; GOLD OPEN ACCESS; GREEN FINAL OPEN ACCESS; GREEN OPEN ACCESS

N., Sohn-Hausner, Natacha, L.B., Kmetiuk, Louise Bach, A.W., Biondo, Alexander Welker

AUTHOR FULL NAMES: Sohn-Hausner, Natacha (58516437100); Kmetiuk, Louise Bach (57195902357); Biondo, Alexander Welker (56008856900)

58516437100; 57195902357; 56008856900

One Health Approach to Leptospirosis: Human–Dog Seroprevalence Associated to Socioeconomic and Environmental Risk Factors in Brazil over a 20-Year Period (2001–2020)

(2023) *Tropical Medicine and Infectious Disease*, 8 (7), art. no. 356

DOI: 10.3390/tropicalmed8070356

[https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85166420983&doi=10.3390%2Ftropicalmed8070356&partnerID=40&md5=719336616c43c5cb1b0417ce8e31bac1)

[85166420983&doi=10.3390%2Ftropicalmed8070356&partnerID=40&md5=719336616c43c5cb1b0417ce8e31bac1](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85166420983&doi=10.3390%2Ftropicalmed8070356&partnerID=40&md5=719336616c43c5cb1b0417ce8e31bac1)

49) DOCUMENT TYPE: Article

OPEN ACCESS: ALL OPEN ACCESS; GOLD OPEN ACCESS; GREEN FINAL OPEN ACCESS; GREEN OPEN ACCESS

D.A., de Andrade Morais, Davidianne A., B.C., Nunes, Bruno Cesar, R.R., Soares, Rafael Rodrigues, M.D., de Oliveira, Murilo Duarte, D.F., da Costa, Diego Figueiredo, H.G., de Araújo, Hosaneide Gomes, J.P., Araújo Júnior, J. P., C.D., Malossi, Camila Dantas, M.L.C.R., Silva, Maria Luana Cristiny Rodrigues, S.S., de Azevedo, Sergio Santos

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57217645726; 57210110439; 57191431738; 57456161500; 57189056104; 57210428641; 57218362522; 55879694100; 21735433500; 57324382400

Strong Evidence of the Role of Donkeys in the Epidemiology of *Leptospira* spp. in Semiarid Conditions

(2023) *Microorganisms*, 11 (7), art. no. 1853

DOI: 10.3390/microorganisms11071853

[https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85166322070&doi=10.3390%2Fmicroorganisms11071853&partnerID=40&md5=7c88eb13861776e6f19702b069dfe20f)

[85166322070&doi=10.3390%2Fmicroorganisms11071853&partnerID=40&md5=7c88eb13861776e6f19702b069dfe20f](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85166322070&doi=10.3390%2Fmicroorganisms11071853&partnerID=40&md5=7c88eb13861776e6f19702b069dfe20f)

50) DOCUMENT TYPE: Article

OPEN ACCESS: ALL OPEN ACCESS; GOLD OPEN ACCESS; GREEN FINAL OPEN ACCESS; GREEN OPEN ACCESS

C., Cremonese, Cleber, F.N., Souza, Fábio Neves, F.A.G., Palma, Fabiana Almerinda Gonçalves, J.F.A., Sodré, Jonatas Fernandes Araújo, R.L., Brito, Ricardo Lustosa, P.D.S., Ribeiro, Priscyla Dos Santos, J.O., Santana, Juliet Oliveira, R.H., Coelho, Rachel Helena, J.P.A., Ticona, Juan P.Aguilar, R.D.J., Nazaré, Romero De Jesus

AUTHOR FULL NAMES: Cremonese, Cleber (36243199900); Souza, Fábio Neves (57191665343); Palma, Fabiana Almerinda Gonçalves (57222260472); Sodré, Jonatas Fernandes Araújo (58345026900); Brito, Ricardo Lustosa (57213264176); Ribeiro, Priscyla Dos Santos (57301523000); Santana, Juliet Oliveira (57226697829); Coelho,

Rachel Helena (57297925500); Ticona, Juan P. Aguilar (57221753307); Nazaré, Romero De Jesus (57709115800)
36243199900; 57191665343; 57222260472; 58345026900; 57213264176; 57301523000;
57226697829; 57297925500; 57221753307; 57709115800
Simplified sewerage to prevent urban leptospirosis transmission: a cluster non-randomised controlled trial protocol in disadvantaged urban communities of Salvador, Brazil
(2023) *BMJ Open*, 13 (6), art. no. e065009
DOI: 10.1136/bmjopen-2022-065009
<https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85162772649&doi=10.1136%2Fbmjopen-2022-065009&partnerID=40&md5=d37b69ad25106b0ee16968370acc0c93>

51) DOCUMENT TYPE: Article

OPEN ACCESS: ALL OPEN ACCESS; GOLD OPEN ACCESS; GREEN ACCEPTED OPEN ACCESS; GREEN OPEN ACCESS

Y.T., Chiani, Yosena Teresita, P., Jacob, Paulina, G., Mayora, Gisela, D.S., Aquino, Diego Sebastian, R.D., Quintana, Rubén Darío, L.M., Mesa, Leticia M.
AUTHOR FULL NAMES: Chiani, Yosena Teresita (40161256300); Jacob, Paulina (56940039100); Mayora, Gisela (55748476400); Aquino, Diego Sebastian (57208672551); Quintana, Rubén Darío (56257286800); Mesa, Leticia M. (14121945100)
40161256300; 56940039100; 55748476400; 57208672551; 56257286800; 14121945100
Presence of *Leptospira* spp. in a Mosaic of Wetlands Used for Livestock Raising under Differing Hydroclimatic Conditions
(2023) *Applied and Environmental Microbiology*, 89 (6)
DOI: 10.1128/aem.01971-22
<https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85164061290&doi=10.1128%2Faem.01971-22&partnerID=40&md5=039ece36e44c5d2147cf97e64606cbe3>

52) DOCUMENT TYPE: Article

OPEN ACCESS: ALL OPEN ACCESS; GREEN FINAL OPEN ACCESS; GREEN OPEN ACCESS; HYBRID GOLD OPEN ACCESS

J.M., Dreesman, Johannes M., S.E., Toikkanen, Salla E., M., Runge, Martin, L., Hamschmidt, Leonhard, B., Lüsse, Berthold, J.F., Freise, Jona F., J., Ehlers, Joachim, K., Nöckler, Karsten, C., Knorr, Carolin, B., Keller, Barbara
AUTHOR FULL NAMES: Dreesman, Johannes M. (56182295800); Toikkanen, Salla E. (54986725400); Runge, Martin (17535119000); Hamschmidt, Leonhard (14422102400); Lüsse, Berthold (58085446100); Freise, Jona F. (7003381522); Ehlers, Joachim (7005658911); Nöckler, Karsten (55941959000); Knorr, Carolin (58085349700); Keller, Barbara (58371305100)
56182295800; 54986725400; 17535119000; 14422102400; 58085446100; 7003381522; 7005658911; 55941959000; 58085349700; 58371305100
Investigation and response to a large outbreak of leptospirosis in field workers in Lower Saxony, Germany

(2023) *Zoonoses and Public Health*, 70 (4), pp. 315 - 326
DOI: 10.1111/zph.13027
<https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85147157862&doi=10.1111%2Fzph.13027&partnerID=40&md5=1040c1bf33acadaef950fe6b0e29a00b>

53) DOCUMENT TYPE: Article
OPEN ACCESS: ALL OPEN ACCESS; HYBRID GOLD OPEN ACCESS

M., Lotto-Batista, Martin, E.M., Rees, Eleanor M., A.A.A., Gómez, Andrea A. Alejandra, S., López, Soledad, S., Castell, Stefanie, A.J., Kucharski, Adam J., S., Ghozzi, Stéphane, G.V., Müller, Gabriela Viviana, R., Lowe, Rachel

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57222627756; 57218207228; 55429425400; 58251680100; 36443286200; 54883807400; 6508354308; 8674035000; 36135810500

Towards a leptospirosis early warning system in northeastern Argentina

(2023) *Journal of the Royal Society Interface*, 20 (202), art. no. 20230069

DOI: 10.1098/rsif.2023.0069

<https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85159389312&doi=10.1098%2Frsif.2023.0069&partnerID=40&md5=4766ed48cc94319d81fe960cbd2ab892>

54) DOCUMENT TYPE: Article
OPEN ACCESS: ALL OPEN ACCESS; GREEN FINAL OPEN ACCESS; GREEN OPEN ACCESS; HYBRID GOLD OPEN ACCESS

M.S., Abdul Rahman, Mohammad Sabri, S., Khairani-Bejo, Siti, Z., Zakaria, Zunita, L., Hassan, L., M.A., Roslan, Mohd Azri

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57205217579; 15047903000; 36490971800; 15044258900; 56928121800

Detection of *Leptospira wolffii* in Water and Soil on Livestock Farms in Kelantan After a Massive Flood

Pengesanan *Leptospira wolffii* dalam Air dan Tanah di Ladang Ternakan di Kelantan Selepas Banjir Besar

(2023) *Sains Malaysiana*, 52 (5), pp. 1383 - 1395

DOI: 10.17576/jsm-2023-5205-05

<https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85170425083&doi=10.17576%2Fjsm-2023-5205-05&partnerID=40&md5=3a5670dd9b77b625fc0815ddd0c27583>

55) DOCUMENT TYPE: Article

OPEN ACCESS: ALL OPEN ACCESS; GOLD OPEN ACCESS; GREEN ACCEPTED OPEN ACCESS; GREEN OPEN ACCESS

I., Ramos-Tapia, Ignacio, P., Salinas, Pamela, R., Núñez, Reynaldo, D., Cortez, Donna, J., Soto, Jorge, M., Paneque, Manuel

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57210170066; 57205331919; 57196685909; 57208599755; 57205547627; 6701795711

Compositional Changes in Sediment Microbiota Are Associated with Seasonal Variation of the Water Column in High-Altitude Hyperarid Andean Lake Systems (2023) Microbiology Spectrum, 11 (3)

DOI: 10.1128/spectrum.05200-22

[https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85163913340&doi=10.1128%2Fspectrum.05200-22&partnerID=40&md5=d72775417082d8025bd5cdb4f5f662db)

[85163913340&doi=10.1128%2Fspectrum.05200-](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85163913340&doi=10.1128%2Fspectrum.05200-22&partnerID=40&md5=d72775417082d8025bd5cdb4f5f662db)

[22&partnerID=40&md5=d72775417082d8025bd5cdb4f5f662db](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85163913340&doi=10.1128%2Fspectrum.05200-22&partnerID=40&md5=d72775417082d8025bd5cdb4f5f662db)

56) TYPE: Article

OPEN ACCESS: ALL OPEN ACCESS; GOLD OPEN ACCESS; GREEN FINAL OPEN ACCESS; GREEN OPEN ACCESS

S.E., Udayar, Sharvanan Eshwaran, N., Chengalarayappa, Narasimha, A., Madeshan, Ashwini, M., Shivanna, Manjunatha, K., Marella, Krishnaveni

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57469344500; 58241615600; 58242965800; 58370972500; 58242306300

Clinico epidemiological study of human leptospirosis in hilly area of South India-A population based case control study

(2023) Indian Journal of Community Medicine, 48 (2), pp. 316 - 320

DOI: 10.4103/ijcm.ijcm_316_22

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[85158877876&doi=10.4103%2Fijcm.ijcm_316_22&partnerID=40&md5=840b60dc5fd70753c7491ee9e657ebd2](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85158877876&doi=10.4103%2Fijcm.ijcm_316_22&partnerID=40&md5=840b60dc5fd70753c7491ee9e657ebd2)

57) DOCUMENT TYPE: Article

OPEN ACCESS: ALL OPEN ACCESS; GOLD OPEN ACCESS; GREEN FINAL OPEN ACCESS; GREEN OPEN ACCESS

S.K., Motto, Shabani Kiyabo, L.E., Hernández-Castro, Luis Enrique, G.M., Shirima, Gabriel Mkilema, I.J., Mengele, Isaac Joseph, S.F., Bwatota, Shedrack Festo, M.D.,

Bronsvort, Mark D.C., E.T., Lyatuu, Eliamoni Titus, D.M., Komwihangilo, Daniel

Mushumbusi, E.A.J., Cook, Elizabeth Anne Jessie

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(6602328515); Lyatuu, Eliamoni Titus (57219945634); Komwihangilo, Daniel Mushumbusi (22951229100); Cook, Elizabeth Anne Jessie (56966162200) 57364130800; 57195285625; 6507293225; 57203897898; 58029470800; 6602328515; 57219945634; 22951229100; 56966162200
Seroepidemiology of *Leptospira* serovar Hardjo and associated risk factors in smallholder dairy cattle in Tanzania
(2023) PLOS Neglected Tropical Diseases, 17 (4), art. no. e0011199
DOI: 10.1371/journal.pntd.0011199
<https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85151784733&doi=10.1371%2Fjournal.pntd.0011199&partnerID=40&md5=b2b6fceb7714e30c26c79d9235d6cce8>

58) DOCUMENT TYPE: Article

OPEN ACCESS: ALL OPEN ACCESS; GOLD OPEN ACCESS; GREEN FINAL OPEN ACCESS; GREEN OPEN ACCESS

J., Franco, Jackeline, U.K., Aryal, Uma K., H., HogenEsch, Harm, G.E., Moore, George E.

AUTHOR FULL NAMES: Franco, Jackeline (57213012063); Aryal, Uma K. (26424958900); HogenEsch, Harm (16150599500); Moore, George E. (58412528500) 57213012063; 26424958900; 16150599500; 58412528500

Proteomic analysis of canine vaccines
(2023) American Journal of Veterinary Research, 84 (3)
DOI: 10.2460/ajvr.22.11.0192

<https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85149186874&doi=10.2460%2Fajvr.22.11.0192&partnerID=40&md5=522c265ed82e16fcef256f40203200f0>

59) DOCUMENT TYPE: Article

OPEN ACCESS: ALL OPEN ACCESS; HYBRID GOLD OPEN ACCESS

V., Jayaramu, Veianthan, Z.D., Zulkafli, Zed Diyana, S., De Stercke, Simon, W., Buytaert, Wouter, F., Rahmat, Fariq, R.Z., Abdul Rahman, Ribhan Zafira, A.J., Ishak, Asnor Juraiza, W., Tahir, Wardah, J., Ab Rahman, Jamalludin, N.H., Mohd Fuzi, Nik Hafiz

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Leptospirosis modelling using hydrometeorological indices and random forest machine learning

(2023) International Journal of Biometeorology, 67 (3), pp. 423 - 437
DOI: 10.1007/s00484-022-02422-y

<https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85147099122&doi=10.1007%2Fs00484-022-02422-y&partnerID=40&md5=e4c35da0e782365d60a0da4461df0ed5>

60) DOCUMENT TYPE: Article
OPEN ACCESS: ALL OPEN ACCESS

S.T., Rehan, Syeda Tayyaba, E., Ali, Eman, A., Sheikh, Ayesha, A.J., Nashwan, Abdulqadir J.
AUTHOR FULL NAMES: Rehan, Syeda Tayyaba (57374443100); Ali, Eman (57766237500); Sheikh, Ayesha (57802980400); Nashwan, Abdulqadir J. (22985634100) 57374443100; 57766237500; 57802980400; 22985634100
Urban flooding and risk of leptospirosis; Pakistan on the verge of a new disaster: A call for action
(2023) International Journal of Hygiene and Environmental Health, 248, art. no. 114081
DOI: 10.1016/j.ijheh.2022.114081
<https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85143149796&doi=10.1016%2Fj.ijheh.2022.114081&partnerID=40&md5=e429a3c5800f878587cf299eb44164e9>

61) DOCUMENT TYPE: Article
OPEN ACCESS: ALL OPEN ACCESS; HYBRID GOLD OPEN ACCESS

V.A., Mugabe, Vánio Andre, O.F., Inlamea, Osvaldo Frederico, S., Ali, Sádía, P.I., Maholela, Plácida Iliany, B., Melchior, Bibiana, A.F., Muianga, Argentina Felisbela, J.O., Oludele, John O., A., Sumail, Andarusse, V.S., Antonio, Virgilio Santo, V.O., Monteiro, Vanessa Onofre
AUTHOR FULL NAMES: Mugabe, Vánio Andre (57190381625); Inlamea, Osvaldo Frederico (56112351100); Ali, Sádía (57104199500); Maholela, Plácida Iliany (57682577300); Melchior, Bibiana (57794844100); Muianga, Argentina Felisbela (57142496800); Oludele, John O. (57197717711); Sumail, Andarusse (57793726800); Antonio, Virgilio Santo (57195380548); Monteiro, Vanessa Onofre (57188854479) 57190381625; 56112351100; 57104199500; 57682577300; 57794844100; 57142496800; 57197717711; 57793726800; 57195380548; 57188854479
Surveillance for arboviruses and leptospirosis among non-malarial acute febrile illness outpatients in areas affected by Cyclones Idai and Kenneth in Mozambique
(2023) Frontiers in Tropical Diseases, 4, art. no. 1091545
DOI: 10.3389/fitd.2023.1091545
<https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85180465482&doi=10.3389%2Ffitd.2023.1091545&partnerID=40&md5=5e0f1430c659b145e55260dd9f35d503>

62) DOCUMENT TYPE: Article
OPEN ACCESS: ALL OPEN ACCESS; GOLD OPEN ACCESS; GREEN FINAL OPEN ACCESS; GREEN OPEN ACCESS

A., Fatema, Ambreen, M., Ramu, Manjunatha, K.V., Thiruvengadam, Kannan V., I.P., Sunish, Ittoop Pulikkottil, P., Vijayachari, Paluru
AUTHOR FULL NAMES: Fatema, Ambreen (58648186800); Ramu, Manjunatha (58648355800); Thiruvengadam, Kannan V. (57208210497); Sunish, Ittoop Pulikkottil (6603624194); Vijayachari, Paluru (6601955151)
58648186800; 58648355800; 57208210497; 6603624194; 6601955151
Knowledge, attitude, and preventive practices of leptospirosis affected populations in South Andaman, India: A cross-sectional study
(2023) Journal of Health Sciences, 13 (2), pp. 105 - 112
DOI: 10.17532/jhsci.2023.2145
<https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85174163436&doi=10.17532%2Fjhsci.2023.2145&partnerID=40&md5=bd3c5920a8fee9a1d899a3795ab96193>

63) DOCUMENT TYPE: Article

OPEN ACCESS: ALL OPEN ACCESS; GOLD OPEN ACCESS

C., Everekliöglu, Cem, H., Şener, Hidayet, H.K., Sönmez, Hatice Kübra, O.A., Polat, Osman Ahmet, D., Gülmez Sevim, Duygu, H., Arda, Hatice, F., Horozoğlu, Fatih
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7006640699; 57223249168; 57225090634; 55314883600; 55631928500; 25621053000; 9733109900
A novel terminologic “naming-meshing” system using anterior chamber sedimentation for early diagnosis and prompt treatment of ocular or systemic diseases: is it hypopyon or pseudohypopyon?
(2023) International Journal of Ophthalmology, 16 (8), pp. 1337 - 1349
DOI: 10.18240/ijo.2023.08.21
<https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85173693608&doi=10.18240%2Fijo.2023.08.21&partnerID=40&md5=59b29ffe6705af3053d602778b51bd04>

64) DOCUMENT TYPE: Article

OPEN ACCESS: ALL OPEN ACCESS; GOLD OPEN ACCESS; GREEN FINAL OPEN ACCESS; GREEN OPEN ACCESS

E., Kuloğlu, Ersin, K., Issever, Kubilay
AUTHOR FULL NAMES: Kuloğlu, Ersin (57947463200); Issever, Kubilay (57207826720)
57947463200; 57207826720
First report of human infection with *Leptospira interrogans* serovar Bratislava in the Eastern Black Sea region of Turkey
(2023) Revista do Instituto de Medicina Tropical de Sao Paulo, 65, art. no. e48
DOI: 10.1590/S1678-9946202365048

<https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85171238128&doi=10.1590%2FS1678-9946202365048&partnerID=40&md5=c9f7f31ad5deb360bee2ee5ff5285e60>

65) DOCUMENT TYPE: Article

OPEN ACCESS: ALL OPEN ACCESS; GOLD OPEN ACCESS; GREEN FINAL OPEN ACCESS; GREEN OPEN ACCESS

H., Hagiya, Hideharu, T., Koyama, Toshihiro, F., Otsuka, Fumio

AUTHOR FULL NAMES: Hagiya, Hideharu (55295776100); Koyama, Toshihiro

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55295776100; 10238971400; 35426691700

Epidemiological Characteristics and Trends in the Incidence of Leptospirosis in Japan:

A Nationwide, Observational Study from 2006 to 2021

(2023) American Journal of Tropical Medicine and Hygiene, 109 (3), pp. 589 - 594

DOI: 10.4269/ajtmh.23-0131

[https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85170111316&doi=10.4269%2Fajtmh.23-](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85170111316&doi=10.4269%2Fajtmh.23-0131&partnerID=40&md5=764302ad05c17338d5478453ba3841cc)

0131&partnerID=40&md5=764302ad05c17338d5478453ba3841cc

66) DOCUMENT TYPE: Article

Y., Yamamoto, Yukichika, H., Hagiya, Hideharu, R., Hayashi, Ruiko, F., Otsuka, Fumio

AUTHOR FULL NAMES: Yamamoto, Yukichika (57219657586); Hagiya, Hideharu

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57219657586; 55295776100; 57221673940; 35426691700

Case Report: Leptospirosis after a Typhoon Disaster Outside the Endemic Region,

Japan

(2023) American Journal of Tropical Medicine and Hygiene, 109 (3), pp. 587 - 588

DOI: 10.4269/ajtmh.23-0133

[https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85170110791&doi=10.4269%2Fajtmh.23-0133&partnerID=40&md5=459884b1d8a8c48af81ef889a27b4845)

85170110791&doi=10.4269%2Fajtmh.23-

0133&partnerID=40&md5=459884b1d8a8c48af81ef889a27b4845

67) DOCUMENT TYPE: Article

OPEN ACCESS: ALL OPEN ACCESS; GREEN FINAL OPEN ACCESS; GREEN OPEN ACCESS

D.E.P., Sumalapao, Derick Erl P., A.R., Lao, Angelyn Relucio, A.A., Adriano, Athena

Acain, J.C.G., So, Jenny Carmina Gan, N.G., Gloriani, Nina Gonzales

AUTHOR FULL NAMES: Sumalapao, Derick Erl P. (56287762100); Lao, Angelyn

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56287762100; 34976916500; 58534078400; 58534797200; 36080339500

Activation of T-cells and Activity of Macrophages among Smokers with Leptospirosis:

a Synergistic Dynamics in the Impairment of Human Immune System

(2023) Brazilian Archives of Biology and Technology, 66, art. no. e23220183

DOI: 10.1590/1678-4324-2023220183

<https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85167795226&doi=10.1590%2F1678-4324-2023220183&partnerID=40&md5=fa2884bf61d8f11a297d033fe7e1b92e>

68) DOCUMENT TYPE: Article

OPEN ACCESS: ALL OPEN ACCESS; GOLD OPEN ACCESS

M.A.A., Kadir, Muhammad Akram Ab, R., Abdul Manaf, Rosliza, M.Y., Aisah, M. Y., L.I., Ismail, L. I.

AUTHOR FULL NAMES: Kadir, Muhammad Akram Ab (58283512400); Abdul Manaf, Rosliza (57201541003); Aisah, M. Y. (8625546700); Ismail, L. I. (55232596700)
58283512400; 57201541003; 8625546700; 55232596700

Spatio-Temporal Analysis of Leptospirosis Hotspot Areas and Its Association with Hydroclimatic Factors in Selangor, Malaysia: Protocol for an Ecological Cross-sectional Study

(2023) JMIR Research Protocols, 12, art. no. e43712

DOI: 10.2196/43712

<https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85159902951&doi=10.2196%2F43712&partnerID=40&md5=4c58efc320c1419edbffa5702a8f3ed8>

69) DOCUMENT TYPE: Article

OPEN ACCESS: ALL OPEN ACCESS; GOLD OPEN ACCESS; GREEN FINAL OPEN ACCESS; GREEN OPEN ACCESS

M., Mazzanti, Mariana, E.A., Scialfa, Exequiel Alejandro, M.A., Rivero, Mariana Alejandra, J.A., Passucci, Juan Antonio

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Epidemiology of Leptospira spp. infection in a beef cattle area of Argentina

(2023) Frontiers in Veterinary Science, 10, art. no. 1083024

DOI: 10.3389/fvets.2023.1083024

<https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85149802473&doi=10.3389%2Ffvets.2023.1083024&partnerID=40&md5=d0fc532ada3435e5c6f67deef8258a98>

70) DOCUMENT TYPE: Article

OPEN ACCESS: ALL OPEN ACCESS; GOLD OPEN ACCESS; GREEN FINAL OPEN ACCESS; GREEN OPEN ACCESS

K., Kiuno, Kazuki, T., Kato, Takuya, H., Otsubo, Hiroko, R., Kibe, Ryoko, Y., Kataoka, Yasushi, S., Hayama, Shinichi

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58045703300; 26666122400; 7005813393; 8603878100; 17934757900; 15734486600
Epidemiological Study of Pathogenic Leptospira in Raccoons (*Procyon lotor*) in a Suburb of Tokyo, Japan
(2023) *Animals*, 13 (1), art. no. 21
DOI: 10.3390/ani13010021
<https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85145857045&doi=10.3390%2Fani13010021&partnerID=40&md5=1afd97b9831dbe1ca4de78da1cbfc6c8>

71) DOCUMENT TYPE: Article

OPEN ACCESS: ALL OPEN ACCESS; GOLD OPEN ACCESS; GREEN FINAL OPEN ACCESS; GREEN OPEN ACCESS

F., Malalana, Fernando, J.L., Ireland, Joanne L., G.L., Pinchbeck, Gina L., C.M., McGowan, Catherine M.
AUTHOR FULL NAMES: Malalana, Fernando (35223725700); Ireland, Joanne L. (36675036400); Pinchbeck, Gina L. (6602110563); McGowan, Catherine M. (7102107598)
35223725700; 36675036400; 6602110563; 7102107598
Risk factors for a first episode of primary uveitis in the UK and proportion of cases that experience recurrence following this first episode
(2023) *Equine Veterinary Journal*, 55 (1), pp. 42 - 47
DOI: 10.1111/evj.13576
<https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85127456289&doi=10.1111%2Fevj.13576&partnerID=40&md5=ab1bd3f22692b13735dbe01add479ba1>

72) DOCUMENT TYPE: Article

A., Murwani, Arita, H., Ashar, Hadi, G., Apriningtyas Budiyati, Gani
AUTHOR FULL NAMES: Murwani, Arita (59674684900); Ashar, Hadi (57221108773); Apriningtyas Budiyati, Gani (59907314900)
59674684900; 57221108773; 59907314900
Relationship between Knowledge and Preventive Behavior of Leptospirosis in Berbah District Sleman Regency Yogyakarta 2021
(2022) *Indonesian Journal of Tropical and Infectious Disease*, 10 (3), pp. 150 - 157
DOI: 10.20473/ijtid.v10i3.33076
<https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-105005732948&doi=10.20473%2Fijtid.v10i3.33076&partnerID=40&md5=7c6e745b23e1f014177e9ee424ec5bea>

73) DOCUMENT TYPE: Article

OPEN ACCESS: ALL OPEN ACCESS; GOLD OPEN ACCESS

A.C., do Couto, Anahi Chechia, M.L., Gravinatti, Mara Lúcia, M., Pellizzaro, Maysa, L.B., Kmetiuk, Louise Bach, A.C., Yamakawa, Ana Carolina, E.C., da Silva, Evelyn Cristine, L.G., Felipetto, Laís Giuliani, H., Langoni, Hélio, A., de Souza Leandro, André, C.E., de Santi, Carlos Eduardo

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One health approach on serosurvey of anti-*Leptospira* spp. in homeless persons and their dogs in South Brazil

(2022) *One Health*, 15, art. no. 100421

DOI: 10.1016/j.onehlt.2022.100421

[https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85135768544&doi=10.1016%2Fj.onehlt.2022.100421&partnerID=40&md5=4e2af5f692082833acc3954f9aeedfc9)

[85135768544&doi=10.1016%2Fj.onehlt.2022.100421&partnerID=40&md5=4e2af5f692082833acc3954f9aeedfc9](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85135768544&doi=10.1016%2Fj.onehlt.2022.100421&partnerID=40&md5=4e2af5f692082833acc3954f9aeedfc9)

74) DOCUMENT TYPE: Article

OPEN ACCESS: ALL OPEN ACCESS; GREEN FINAL OPEN ACCESS; GREEN OPEN ACCESS

A., Phosri, Arthit

AUTHOR FULL NAMES: Phosri, Arthit (57193878711)

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Effects of rainfall on human leptospirosis in Thailand: evidence of multi-province study using distributed lag non-linear model

(2022) *Stochastic Environmental Research and Risk Assessment*, 36 (12), pp. 4119 - 4132

DOI: 10.1007/s00477-022-02250-x

[https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85131534549&doi=10.1007%2Fs00477-022-02250-x&partnerID=40&md5=4c94cd45baf827a8760303d32a95f2d9)

[85131534549&doi=10.1007%2Fs00477-022-02250-](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85131534549&doi=10.1007%2Fs00477-022-02250-x&partnerID=40&md5=4c94cd45baf827a8760303d32a95f2d9)

[x&partnerID=40&md5=4c94cd45baf827a8760303d32a95f2d9](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85131534549&doi=10.1007%2Fs00477-022-02250-x&partnerID=40&md5=4c94cd45baf827a8760303d32a95f2d9)

75) DOCUMENT TYPE: Article

OPEN ACCESS: ALL OPEN ACCESS; BRONZE OPEN ACCESS; GREEN ACCEPTED OPEN ACCESS; GREEN FINAL OPEN ACCESS; GREEN OPEN ACCESS

S., Chadsuthi, Sudarat, K., Chalvet-Monfray, Karine, S., Geawduanglek, Suchada, P., Wongnak, Phrutsamon, J., Cappelle, Julien

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33067633200; 6602803804; 40161313900; 57217678155; 24449355500

Spatial-temporal patterns and risk factors for human leptospirosis in Thailand, 2012–2018

(2022) *Scientific Reports*, 12 (1), art. no. 5066

DOI: 10.1038/s41598-022-09079-y
<https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85127028654&doi=10.1038%2Fs41598-022-09079-y&partnerID=40&md5=f95f892a885e481ef7bc39b734a57935>

76) DOCUMENT TYPE: Article

OPEN ACCESS: ALL OPEN ACCESS; GOLD OPEN ACCESS; GREEN ACCEPTED OPEN ACCESS; GREEN FINAL OPEN ACCESS; GREEN OPEN ACCESS

C., Taunton, Caroline, C.E., Hayek, Carol El, E.J., Field, Emma J., S., Rubenach, Sally, J.V., Esmonde, Juliet V., S., Smith, Simon, A., Preston-Thomas, Annie
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57938462700; 57218857309; 36559033400; 58117710200; 56601334900; 57191380806; 22939215100

Undetected serovars: leptospirosis cases in the Cairns region during the 2021 wet season

(2022) Communicable Diseases Intelligence, 46

DOI: 10.33321/cdi.2022.46.70

<https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85142132144&doi=10.33321%2Fcdi.2022.46.70&partnerID=40&md5=b1fe3770fd835cff63089c395518ce80>

77) DOCUMENT TYPE: Article

OPEN ACCESS: ALL OPEN ACCESS; GOLD OPEN ACCESS

A., Artus, Aileen, I.J., Schafer, Ilana J., C.M., Cossaboom, Caitlin M., D.L., Haberling, Dana L., R.L., Galloway, Renee Lynn, G., Sutherland, Graham, A.S., Browne, Andrew Springer, J., Roth, Joseph, V., France, Valicia, H.M., Cranford, Hannah M.
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57196326271; 56135868700; 53979508200; 23481667700; 7102801269; 57973951300; 56988787100; 55360905700; 57973991300; 57216795626

Seroprevalence, distribution, and risk factors for human leptospirosis in the United States Virgin Islands

(2022) PLOS Neglected Tropical Diseases, 16 (11), art. no. e0010880

DOI: 10.1371/journal.pntd.0010880

<https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85140767928&doi=10.1371%2Fjournal.pntd.0010880&partnerID=40&md5=1f9e8835a9139e233585438140cb8703>

78) DOCUMENT TYPE: Article

OPEN ACCESS: ALL OPEN ACCESS; GOLD OPEN ACCESS; GREEN FINAL OPEN ACCESS; GREEN OPEN ACCESS

S., Vardoulakis, Sotiris, V., Matthews, V., R.S., Bailie, Ross Stewart, W., Hu, Wenbiao, L.S., Carulla, Luis Salvador, A.L., Barratt, Alexandra L., C.M.Y., Chu, Cordia Ming Yeuk

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16835481000; 55963732900; 58364153600; 57218248248; 57201763249; 7004367799; 56435044600

Building resilience to Australian flood disasters in the face of climate change (2022) *Medical Journal of Australia*, 217 (7), pp. 342 - 345

DOI: 10.5694/mja2.51595

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[85134318502&doi=10.5694%2Fmja2.51595&partnerID=40&md5=a81c5a38c4054b5ce35c3ae1fd3b9518](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85134318502&doi=10.5694%2Fmja2.51595&partnerID=40&md5=a81c5a38c4054b5ce35c3ae1fd3b9518)

79) DOCUMENT TYPE: Article

OPEN ACCESS: ALL OPEN ACCESS; GREEN FINAL OPEN ACCESS; GREEN OPEN ACCESS; HYBRID GOLD OPEN ACCESS

J.N., Warnasekara, Janith Niwanthaka, S.B., Agampodi, Suneth Buddhika, N.R., Abeynayake, N. R.

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SARIMA and ARDL models for predicting leptospirosis in Anuradhapura district Sri Lanka

(2022) *PLOS ONE*, 17 (10 October), art. no. e0275447

DOI: 10.1371/journal.pone.0275447

[https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85140022574&doi=10.1371%2Fjournal.pone.0275447&partnerID=40&md5=7f9b8091fad7b0f7402b722fbff12948)

[85140022574&doi=10.1371%2Fjournal.pone.0275447&partnerID=40&md5=7f9b8091fad7b0f7402b722fbff12948](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85140022574&doi=10.1371%2Fjournal.pone.0275447&partnerID=40&md5=7f9b8091fad7b0f7402b722fbff12948)

80) DOCUMENT TYPE: Article

OPEN ACCESS: ALL OPEN ACCESS; GOLD OPEN ACCESS; GREEN ACCEPTED OPEN ACCESS; GREEN FINAL OPEN ACCESS; GREEN OPEN ACCESS

D.C., Kligerman, Débora Cynamon, T.A., de Oliveira Cardoso, Telma Abdalla, S.C., Cohen, Simone Cynamon, D.C.B.D., Azevedo, Déborah Chein Bueno De, G.D.A., Toledo, Graziella De Araújo, A.P.C.B.D., Azevedo, Ana Paula Chein Bueno De, S.M., Charlesworth, Susanne M.

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15820869300; 53872392600; 21833564900; 57926929600; 57926915900; 57212628892;
6603736355
Methodology for a Comprehensive Health Impact Assessment in Water Supply and Sanitation Programmes for Brazil
(2022) International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health, 19 (19), art. no. 12776
DOI: 10.3390/ijerph191912776
<https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85139811715&doi=10.3390%2Fijerph191912776&partnerID=40&md5=ccc5ea2b0529da4454da3005ebb6f070>

81) DOCUMENT TYPE: Article

OPEN ACCESS: ALL OPEN ACCESS; GOLD OPEN ACCESS; GREEN FINAL OPEN ACCESS; GREEN OPEN ACCESS

J.E., Sykes, Jane Emily, D.A., Haake, David A., C.D., Gamage, Chandika Damesh, W.Z., Mills, W. Zach, J.E., Nally, Jarlath E.
AUTHOR FULL NAMES: Sykes, Jane Emily (7102756842); Haake, David A. (7006383677); Gamage, Chandika Damesh (35867068300); Mills, W. Zach (57915576000); Nally, Jarlath E. (7005617276)
7102756842; 7006383677; 35867068300; 57915576000; 7005617276
A global one health perspective on leptospirosis in humans and animals
(2022) Journal of the American Veterinary Medical Association, 260 (13), pp. 1589 - 1596
DOI: 10.2460/javma.22.06.0258
<https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85139248305&doi=10.2460%2Fjavma.22.06.0258&partnerID=40&md5=f80170f125a22ef80fb450c8c496adc2>

82) DOCUMENT TYPE: Article

OPEN ACCESS: ALL OPEN ACCESS; HYBRID GOLD OPEN ACCESS

M.T., Eyre, Max T., F.N., Souza, Fábio Neves, T.S.D.A., Carvalho-Pereira, Ticiania Soares De Andrade, N.R.R., Nery, Nivison Ruy Rocha, D.S., de Oliveira, Daiana Santos, J.S., Cruz, Jaqueline Silva, G.A.D., Sacramento, Gielson Almeida Do, H., Khalil, Hussein, E.A., Wunder, Elsie Augusto, K.P., Hacker, Kathryn P.
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57218760337; 57191665343; 55252683700; 57086829100; 56706945700; 56767538800; 57144485300; 56072374200; 14008124800; 55883619100

Linking rattiness, geography and environmental degradation to spillover *Leptospira* infections in marginalised urban settings: An eco-epidemiological community-based cohort study in Brazil
(2022) *eLife*, 11, art. no. e73120
DOI: 10.7554/eLife.73120
<https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85139816487&doi=10.7554%2FeLife.73120&partnerID=40&md5=69f3e58c8619580af48dc1a75e2dd8ab>

83) DOCUMENT TYPE: Article

OPEN ACCESS: ALL OPEN ACCESS; GOLD OPEN ACCESS; GREEN ACCEPTED OPEN ACCESS; GREEN FINAL OPEN ACCESS; GREEN OPEN ACCESS

V., Sluydts, Vincent, S.R., Sarathchandra, Siriwardana Rampalage, A.P., Piscitelli, Anna Pia, N., van Houtte, Natalie, S., Gryseels, Sophie, A., Mayer-Scholl, Anne, N.S., Bier, Nadja Seyhan, N.M., Htwe, Nyo Me, J., Jacob, Jens
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Ecology and distribution of *Leptospira* spp., reservoir hosts and environmental interaction in Sri Lanka, with identification of a new strain
(2022) *PLOS Neglected Tropical Diseases*, 16 (9), art. no. e0010757
DOI: 10.1371/journal.pntd.0010757
<https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85139375841&doi=10.1371%2Fjournal.pntd.0010757&partnerID=40&md5=d0b0beb3c4db85c71e64977942c66dbd>

84) DOCUMENT TYPE: Article

OPEN ACCESS: ALL OPEN ACCESS; GOLD OPEN ACCESS; GREEN FINAL OPEN ACCESS; GREEN OPEN ACCESS

Y.M., Mohammadi, Yeganeh Malek, P., Khaki, Pejvak, S., Moradi Bidhendi, S., M., Nofeli, Mojtaba
AUTHOR FULL NAMES: Mohammadi, Yeganeh Malek (57847710200); Khaki, Pejvak (8963676700); Moradi Bidhendi, S. (16041398600); Nofeli, Mojtaba (57199865451) 57847710200; 8963676700; 16041398600; 57199865451
Evaluation of the Presence of Gene Encoding Loa22 in Pathogenic *Leptospira* Serovars
(2022) *Iranian Journal of Medical Microbiology*, 16 (5), pp. 392 - 398
DOI: 10.30699/ijmm.16.5.1
<https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85136120618&doi=10.30699%2Fijmm.16.5.1&partnerID=40&md5=bf9a1d17925259470d1b64480d9fa047>

85) DOCUMENT TYPE: Article

B.L., Gabriel-Véjar, Blanca Lilia, D., Vázquez-Luna, Dinora, D.I., Martínez-Herrera, David Itzcoatl, J.A., Villagómez-Cortés, José Alfredo, O.R., Leyva-Ovalle, Otto Raúl, J.I., Torres-Barranca, Jorge Isaac, H., Zarza Villanueva, Heliot

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57579626500; 36613770100; 57191381052; 26532125300; 36094203800; 8361405200; 57580039100

Spatial distribution models of seroreactive sheep to *Leptospira* spp. in Veracruz, Mexico

(2022) *Transboundary and Emerging Diseases*, 69 (5), pp. e1913 - e1922

DOI: 10.1111/tbed.14526

[https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85128406884&doi=10.1111%2Ftbed.14526&partnerID=40&md5=20f7cf7831b18c036425016d50cee61e)

[85128406884&doi=10.1111%2Ftbed.14526&partnerID=40&md5=20f7cf7831b18c036425016d50cee61e](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85128406884&doi=10.1111%2Ftbed.14526&partnerID=40&md5=20f7cf7831b18c036425016d50cee61e)

86) DOCUMENT TYPE: Article

OPEN ACCESS: ALL OPEN ACCESS; GOLD OPEN ACCESS

A.N., Marteli, Alice Nardoni, L.A., Guasselli, Laurindo Antônio, D., Diament, Décio, G.O., Wink, Gabriele Ozório, V.V., Vieira Vasconcelos, Vitor Vieira

AUTHOR FULL NAMES: Marteli, Alice Nardoni (57398969400); Guasselli, Laurindo Antônio (26664549000); Diament, Décio (6506027380); Wink, Gabriele Ozório (57987593600); Vieira Vasconcelos, Vitor Vieira (55788419400)

57398969400; 26664549000; 6506027380; 57987593600; 55788419400

Spatio-temporal analysis of leptospirosis in Brazil and its relationship with flooding

(2022) *Geospatial Health*, 17 (2), art. no. 1128

DOI: 10.4081/gh.2022.1128

[https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85143087777&doi=10.4081%2Fgh.2022.1128&partnerID=40&md5=cf0b869c6f9d10c6730c81f98f210d84)

[85143087777&doi=10.4081%2Fgh.2022.1128&partnerID=40&md5=cf0b869c6f9d10c6730c81f98f210d84](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85143087777&doi=10.4081%2Fgh.2022.1128&partnerID=40&md5=cf0b869c6f9d10c6730c81f98f210d84)

87) DOCUMENT TYPE: Article

OPEN ACCESS: ALL OPEN ACCESS; GOLD OPEN ACCESS

Y.I., Golovin, Yuri I., A.O., Zhigachev, Alexander O., N.L., Klyachko, Natalia L., D.Y., Golovin, Dmitry Yu

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7006092259; 57205357762; 35579859900; 7004150534

Controlled localization of magnetic nanoparticle mechanical activation in suspension exposed to alternating magnetic field using gradient magnetic field

(2022) *Journal of Nanoparticle Research*, 24 (8), art. no. 167

DOI: 10.1007/s11051-022-05501-8

<https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85135705579&doi=10.1007%2Fs11051-022-05501-8&partnerID=40&md5=6951f222818e61a83737a31740072d7f>

88) DOCUMENT TYPE: Article

L., Mejía, Lorena, B., Prado, Belén, P.A., Cardenas, Paul Andres, G.A., Trueba, Gabriel A., F.G., González-Candelas, F. Gónzá

AUTHOR FULL NAMES: Mejía, Lorena (55340919900); Prado, Belén (57467856400); Cardenas, Paul Andres (36747997600); Trueba, Gabriel A. (6701724881); González-Candelas, F. Gónzá (7004300258)

55340919900; 57467856400; 36747997600; 6701724881; 7004300258

The impact of genetic recombination on pathogenic *Leptospira*

(2022) *Infection, Genetics and Evolution*, 102, art. no. 105313

DOI: 10.1016/j.meegid.2022.105313

[https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85132352518&doi=10.1016%2Fj.meegid.2022.105313&partnerID=40&md5=35b2bf23580efd3b5d27c8336b5522f2)

[85132352518&doi=10.1016%2Fj.meegid.2022.105313&partnerID=40&md5=35b2bf23580efd3b5d27c8336b5522f2](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85132352518&doi=10.1016%2Fj.meegid.2022.105313&partnerID=40&md5=35b2bf23580efd3b5d27c8336b5522f2)

89) DOCUMENT TYPE: Article

OPEN ACCESS: ALL OPEN ACCESS; GOLD OPEN ACCESS

L., Douchet, Léa, C., Goarant, Cyrille, M., Mangeas, Morgan, C.E.R., Menkès,

Christophe Eugène Raoul, S., Hinjoy, Soawapak, V., Herbreteau, Vincent

AUTHOR FULL NAMES: Douchet, Léa (57222718557); Goarant, Cyrille (6603498952);

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57222718557; 6603498952; 6508084191; 7102890924; 23987745100; 12142204300

Unraveling the invisible leptospirosis in mainland Southeast Asia and its fate under climate change

(2022) *Science of the Total Environment*, 832, art. no. 155018

DOI: 10.1016/j.scitotenv.2022.155018

[https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85128976481&doi=10.1016%2Fj.scitotenv.2022.155018&partnerID=40&md5=b8c3e717a37c243a79401b5c44822cae)

[85128976481&doi=10.1016%2Fj.scitotenv.2022.155018&partnerID=40&md5=b8c3e717a37c243a79401b5c44822cae](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85128976481&doi=10.1016%2Fj.scitotenv.2022.155018&partnerID=40&md5=b8c3e717a37c243a79401b5c44822cae)

90) DOCUMENT TYPE: Article

OPEN ACCESS: ALL OPEN ACCESS; GREEN ACCEPTED OPEN ACCESS; GREEN FINAL OPEN ACCESS; GREEN OPEN ACCESS; HYBRID GOLD OPEN ACCESS

L.T.P., Mai, Le Thi Phuong, L.P., Dung, Luu Phuong, T.N.P., Mai, Tran Ngoc Phuong,

N.T.M., Hanh, Nguyen Thi My, P.D., Than, Phan Dang, D., van Tran, Dinh, N.T.,

Quyet, Nguyen Tu, H., Hoang, Haihai, D.B., Ngoc, Do Bich, P., Hai, Phamthanh

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Nguyen Tu (57207997470); Hoang, Haihai (59454667100); Ngoc, Do Bich (57673270100); Hai, Phamthanh (57672437500)

57534998800; 47860951500; 57216438569; 59349184500; 56818846600; 55938124400; 57207997470; 59454667100; 57673270100; 57672437500

Characteristics of human leptospirosis in three different geographical and climatic zones of Vietnam: a hospital-based study

(2022) International Journal of Infectious Diseases, 120, pp. 113 - 120

DOI: 10.1016/j.ijid.2022.04.011

[https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85129746251&doi=10.1016%2Fj.ijid.2022.04.011&partnerID=40&md5=abdc879cd256e171aabbdbfb7783b72)

[85129746251&doi=10.1016%2Fj.ijid.2022.04.011&partnerID=40&md5=abdc879cd256e171aabbdbfb7783b72](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85129746251&doi=10.1016%2Fj.ijid.2022.04.011&partnerID=40&md5=abdc879cd256e171aabbdbfb7783b72)

91) DOCUMENT TYPE: Article

OPEN ACCESS: ALL OPEN ACCESS; GOLD OPEN ACCESS

L., Chou, Lifang, T., Chen, Tingwen, H.Y., Yang, Huang Yu, Y., Tian, Yachung, M.Y., Chang, M. Y., C., Hung, Chengchieh, C.H., Lai, Chih Ho, S., Hsu, Shenhsing, C., Tsai, Chungying, Y., Ko, Yiching

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36924249100; 36551939900; 54390408000; 7402840520; 7404504561; 8266357600; 35285784900; 8689272500; 54892630000; 15733061000

Implication of the IL-10-Expression Signature in the Pathogenicity of Leptospira-Infected Macrophages

(2022) Microbiology Spectrum, 10 (3)

DOI: 10.1128/spectrum.02595-21

[https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85133215256&doi=10.1128%2Fspectrum.02595-21&partnerID=40&md5=bce5aced177ded02b6f057b31424a85f)

[85133215256&doi=10.1128%2Fspectrum.02595-](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85133215256&doi=10.1128%2Fspectrum.02595-21&partnerID=40&md5=bce5aced177ded02b6f057b31424a85f)

[21&partnerID=40&md5=bce5aced177ded02b6f057b31424a85f](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85133215256&doi=10.1128%2Fspectrum.02595-21&partnerID=40&md5=bce5aced177ded02b6f057b31424a85f)

92) DOCUMENT TYPE: Article

OPEN ACCESS: ALL OPEN ACCESS; GOLD OPEN ACCESS; GREEN FINAL OPEN ACCESS; GREEN OPEN ACCESS

A.A.A., Gómez, Andrea A. Alejandra, M.S., López, María Soledad, G.V., Müller, Gabriela Viviana, L.R., López, Leonardo Rafael, W.F., Sione, Walter Fabián, L.L., Giovanini, Leonardo L.

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55429425400; 7404124163; 8674035000; 57220772829; 24071886600; 6602698837

Modeling of leptospirosis outbreaks in relation to hydroclimatic variables in the northeast of Argentina

(2022) Heliyon, 8 (6), art. no. e09758

DOI: 10.1016/j.heliyon.2022.e09758

[https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85132506639&doi=10.1016%2Fj.heliyon.2022.e09758&partnerID=40&md5=90ec6347fd35c43af4932c363a35b701)

[85132506639&doi=10.1016%2Fj.heliyon.2022.e09758&partnerID=40&md5=90ec6347fd35c43af4932c363a35b701](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85132506639&doi=10.1016%2Fj.heliyon.2022.e09758&partnerID=40&md5=90ec6347fd35c43af4932c363a35b701)

93) DOCUMENT TYPE: Article

OPEN ACCESS: ALL OPEN ACCESS; GOLD OPEN ACCESS; GREEN ACCEPTED OPEN ACCESS; GREEN FINAL OPEN ACCESS; GREEN OPEN ACCESS

M.K., Sreelakshmi, M. K., S., Kuruvilla, Suneesh, R., Subramaniam, R., P., Latti, Pooja, R., Venkitachalam, Ramanarayanan

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57224444100; 57194712960; 57211396683; 57211389370; 57193532440

An Analysis of Leptospirosis Control in a Flood-Affected Region of Kerala and the Role of Accredited Social Health Activists-A Questionnaire Study

(2022) Disaster Medicine and Public Health Preparedness, 16 (3), pp. 1123 - 1127

DOI: 10.1017/dmp.2021.71

[https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85107558702&doi=10.1017%2Fdmp.2021.71&partnerID=40&md5=a697927a8335fa35cdf80597f823e213)

[85107558702&doi=10.1017%2Fdmp.2021.71&partnerID=40&md5=a697927a8335fa35cdf80597f823e213](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85107558702&doi=10.1017%2Fdmp.2021.71&partnerID=40&md5=a697927a8335fa35cdf80597f823e213)

94) DOCUMENT TYPE: Article

S., Nelson, Sarah, A.P., Jenkins, Aaron Peter, S.D., Jupiter, Stacy D., P.H.J., Horwitz, Pierre H.J., S., Mangubhai, Sangeeta, S., Abimbola, Seye, A., Ratu, Anaseini, T., Naivalulevu, Timoci, J.A., Negin, Joel A.

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Predicting climate-sensitive water-related disease trends based on health, seasonality and weather data in Fiji

(2022) Journal of Climate Change and Health, 6, art. no. 100112

DOI: 10.1016/j.joclim.2022.100112

[https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85151668624&doi=10.1016%2Fj.joclim.2022.100112&partnerID=40&md5=7d2f8707b916502316121cd5e8608478)

[85151668624&doi=10.1016%2Fj.joclim.2022.100112&partnerID=40&md5=7d2f8707b916502316121cd5e8608478](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85151668624&doi=10.1016%2Fj.joclim.2022.100112&partnerID=40&md5=7d2f8707b916502316121cd5e8608478)

95) DOCUMENT TYPE: Article

OPEN ACCESS: ALL OPEN ACCESS; GOLD OPEN ACCESS

G.G., Aliaga-Samanez, Gabriela Guadalupe, J., Lescano, Jesus, M., Quevedo-Urday, Miryam, G.S., Salvatierra Rodríguez, Guillermo Santos, M., Erkenwick Watsa, Mrinalini, J.E., Calderón-Escalante, John Edwin, G., Erkenwick, Gideon
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57223151837; 57223167331; 55991649100; 57223147845; 57223175097; 57223159247; 55365929000

First detection of antibodies against *Leptospira* among free-ranging neotropical non-human primates in the Peruvian Amazon lowland rainforest

(2022) *Transboundary and Emerging Diseases*, 69 (3), pp. 1458 - 1465

DOI: 10.1111/tbed.14112

[https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85105034070&doi=10.1111%2Ftbed.14112&partnerID=40&md5=78a0a465dcc396d27a5f86cf40913cdc)

[85105034070&doi=10.1111%2Ftbed.14112&partnerID=40&md5=78a0a465dcc396d27a5f86cf40913cdc](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85105034070&doi=10.1111%2Ftbed.14112&partnerID=40&md5=78a0a465dcc396d27a5f86cf40913cdc)

96) DOCUMENT TYPE: Article

D.R., Brown, Damien R., R., Peiris, Ruwani, C., Waller, Claire, E.M., Stedman, Elizabeth M., S.E., Fitzpatrick, Susanne E., V.L., Krause, Vicki Lynn, A.D.K., Draper, Anthony D.K.

AUTHOR FULL NAMES: Brown, Damien R. (57638546300); Peiris, Ruwani (57510792300); Waller, Claire (57641081500); Stedman, Elizabeth M. (57640585300); Fitzpatrick, Susanne E. (57639570900); Krause, Vicki Lynn (20234916800); Draper, Anthony D.K. (57111814600)

57638546300; 57510792300; 57641081500; 57640585300; 57639570900; 20234916800; 57111814600

An outbreak of leptospirosis associated with cattle workers during the wet season, in the Northern Territory of Australia, 2021

(2022) *Communicable Diseases Intelligence*, 46

DOI: 10.33321/cdi.2022.46.23

[https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85128835688&doi=10.33321%2Fcdi.2022.46.23&partnerID=40&md5=43276c53c68605400dcab539052b3e4d)

[85128835688&doi=10.33321%2Fcdi.2022.46.23&partnerID=40&md5=43276c53c68605400dcab539052b3e4d](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85128835688&doi=10.33321%2Fcdi.2022.46.23&partnerID=40&md5=43276c53c68605400dcab539052b3e4d)

97) DOCUMENT TYPE: Article

OPEN ACCESS: ALL OPEN ACCESS; GOLD OPEN ACCESS

Y., Yanagihara, Yasutake, S.Y.A.M., Villanueva, Sharon Yvette Angelina M., N., Nomura, Naoki, M., Ohno, Marumi, T., Sekiya, Toshiki, C., Handabile, Chimuka, M., Shingai, Masashi, H., Higashi, Hideaki, S., Yoshida, Shinichi, T., Masuzawa, Toshiyuki
AUTHOR FULL NAMES: Yanagihara, Yasutake (35515355800); Villanueva, Sharon Yvette Angelina M. (7004327679); Nomura, Naoki (36932453100); Ohno, Marumi (35079083300); Sekiya, Toshiki (55413293100); Handabile, Chimuka (57224306210);

Shingai, Masashi (6602419533); Higashi, Hideaki (55618297800); Yoshida, Shinichi (35449620400); Masuzawa, Toshiyuki (7202640565)
35515355800; 7004327679; 36932453100; 35079083300; 55413293100; 57224306210;
6602419533; 55618297800; 35449620400; 7202640565

Leptospira Is an Environmental Bacterium That Grows in Waterlogged Soil
(2022) Microbiology Spectrum, 10 (2)

DOI: 10.1128/spectrum.02157-21

[https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85129258633&doi=10.1128%2Fspectrum.02157-21&partnerID=40&md5=c6072a392166b1a844abb5c6f7578c2d)

[85129258633&doi=10.1128%2Fspectrum.02157-](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85129258633&doi=10.1128%2Fspectrum.02157-21&partnerID=40&md5=c6072a392166b1a844abb5c6f7578c2d)

[21&partnerID=40&md5=c6072a392166b1a844abb5c6f7578c2d](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85129258633&doi=10.1128%2Fspectrum.02157-21&partnerID=40&md5=c6072a392166b1a844abb5c6f7578c2d)

98) DOCUMENT TYPE: Article

OPEN ACCESS: ALL OPEN ACCESS; GREEN FINAL OPEN ACCESS; GREEN OPEN ACCESS

G.M., da Cunha, Geraldo Marcelo, F., Costa, Federico, G.S., Ribeiro, Guilherme S., M.S., de Sá Carvalho, Marília Sá, R.B., Reis, Renato Barbosa, N.R.R., Nery, Nivison Ruy Rocha, L., Pischel, Lauren, E.L., Gouveia, Edilane Lins, A.C., Santos, Andréia C., A.R.P., Queiroz, Adriano R.P.

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8595056000; 55378617300; 56253006800; 35556783900; 24071814900; 57086829100;

57195942801; 7004383402; 57206249784; 57225722766

Rainfall and other meteorological factors as drivers of urban transmission of leptospirosis

(2022) PLOS Neglected Tropical Diseases, 16 (4), art. no. e0007507

DOI: 10.1371/journal.pntd.0007507

[https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85128794658&doi=10.1371%2Fjournal.pntd.0007507&partnerID=40&md5=2ab31bdf9186aff80c5f374e7e8bc37e)

[85128794658&doi=10.1371%2Fjournal.pntd.0007507&partnerID=40&md5=2ab31bdf9186aff80c5f374e7e8bc37e](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85128794658&doi=10.1371%2Fjournal.pntd.0007507&partnerID=40&md5=2ab31bdf9186aff80c5f374e7e8bc37e)

99) DOCUMENT TYPE: Article

OPEN ACCESS: ALL OPEN ACCESS; GOLD OPEN ACCESS; GREEN ACCEPTED OPEN ACCESS; GREEN FINAL OPEN ACCESS; GREEN OPEN ACCESS

C., Bertholom, Chantal

AUTHOR FULL NAMES: Bertholom, Chantal (22633261800)
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Leptospirosis, epidemiology and diagnosis of an emerging zoonosis La leptospirose, épidémiologie et diagnostic d'une zoonose émergente

(2022) Option/Bio, 32 (647-648), pp. 19 - 20

DOI: 10.1016/S0992-5945(22)00049-6

<https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85128288823&doi=10.1016%2FS0992-5945%2822%2900049-6&partnerID=40&md5=ccc06cd491acd864aa5113ce4c99b7ad>

100) DOCUMENT TYPE: Article

E., Cano-Perez, Eder, S., Loyola, Steev, F., Espitia-Almeida, Fabian, J., Torres-Pacheco, Jaison, D.I., Malambo-Garcia, Dacia Isabel, D.E., Gómez-Camargo, Doris Esther
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57220152867; 57188739176; 57189052044; 57220193478; 56669825600; 53982777400
Climatic Variability and Human Leptospirosis Cases in Cartagena, Colombia: A 10-Year Ecological Study
(2022) American Journal of Tropical Medicine and Hygiene, 106 (3), pp. 785 - 791
DOI: 10.4269/ajtmh.21-0890
<https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85126152611&doi=10.4269%2Fajtmh.21-0890&partnerID=40&md5=0263bf96d99af516080026dc3222b8f5>

101) DOCUMENT TYPE: Article

OPEN ACCESS: ALL OPEN ACCESS; GREEN FINAL OPEN ACCESS; GREEN OPEN ACCESS

G.R., da Cunha, Graziela Ribeiro, M., Pellizzaro, Maysa, C.M., Martins, Camila Marinelli, S.M., Rocha, Suzana Maria, A.C., Yamakawa, Ana Carolina, E.C., da Silva, Evelyn Cristine, A.P., dos Santos, Andrea P., V.M., Morikawa, Vivien Midori, H., Langoni, Hélio, A.W., Biondo, Alexander Welker
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57190295406; 56582138000; 55314452300; 57216816668; 57208862975; 57371553500; 24401080800; 55201243200; 6603491394; 56008856900
Serological survey of anti-Leptospira spp. antibodies in individuals with animal hoarding disorder and their dogs in a major city of Southern Brazil
(2022) Veterinary Medicine and Science, 8 (2), pp. 530 - 536
DOI: 10.1002/vms3.704
<https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85125381071&doi=10.1002%2Fvms3.704&partnerID=40&md5=197fa3648c70cdcc734c82f57ca2d780>

102) DOCUMENT TYPE: Article

OPEN ACCESS: ALL OPEN ACCESS; GOLD OPEN ACCESS; GREEN FINAL OPEN ACCESS; GREEN OPEN ACCESS

A.C.T.R.B., Costa, Anna Cecília Trolesi Reis Borges, C.R., Pereira, Carine Rodrigues, T., Safadi, Thelma, M.B., Heinemann, Marcos Bryan, E.M., Dorneles, E. M.S.

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57438331700; 57204124118; 14049041500; 7102919201; 41861285000

Climate influence the human leptospirosis cases in Brazil, 2007-2019: A time series analysis

(2022) Transactions of the Royal Society of Tropical Medicine and Hygiene, 116 (2), pp. 124 - 132

DOI: 10.1093/trstmh/trab092

[https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85123968490&doi=10.1093%2Ftrstmh%2Ftrab092&partnerID=40&md5=a9188968a00f5b5678361cdc3d71f4a4)

[85123968490&doi=10.1093%2Ftrstmh%2Ftrab092&partnerID=40&md5=a9188968a00f5b5678361cdc3d71f4a4](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85123968490&doi=10.1093%2Ftrstmh%2Ftrab092&partnerID=40&md5=a9188968a00f5b5678361cdc3d71f4a4)

103) DOCUMENT TYPE: Article

A., Bećirović, Amela, A., Trnacevic, Alma, A., Dubinovic-Rekic, Amela, F., Dzafić, Fejzo

AUTHOR FULL NAMES: Bećirović, Amela (57195242789); Trnacevic, Alma (57210443092); Dubinovic-Rekic, Amela (57207930409); Dzafić, Fejzo (26641065400)

57195242789; 57210443092; 57207930409; 26641065400

Floods Associated with Environmental Factors and Leptospirosis: our Experience at

Tuzla Canton, Bosnia and Herzegovina

(2022) Materia Socio-Medica, 34 (3), pp. 193 - 196

DOI: 10.5455/msm.2022.34.193-196

[https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85167341833&doi=10.5455%2Fmsm.2022.34.193-196&partnerID=40&md5=e12e14f5fd8823c2c063545d43fb92dc)

[85167341833&doi=10.5455%2Fmsm.2022.34.193-196&partnerID=40&md5=e12e14f5fd8823c2c063545d43fb92dc](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85167341833&doi=10.5455%2Fmsm.2022.34.193-196&partnerID=40&md5=e12e14f5fd8823c2c063545d43fb92dc)

104) DOCUMENT TYPE: Article

OPEN ACCESS: ALL OPEN ACCESS; GREEN FINAL OPEN ACCESS; GREEN OPEN ACCESS

L.M.S.B., Rocha, Laysa Mayara Soares Brito, P.J.À., de Faria, Pedro Jorge Àlvares, R.R., Soares, Rafael Rodrigues, J.P.D., Araujo-Junior, João Pessoa De, C.D., Malossi, Camila Dantas, L.S., Ullmann, Leila S., M.L.C.R., Silva, Maria Luana Cristiny Rodrigues, S.S., Dos Santos Higino, Severino Silvano, S.S., de Azevedo, Sergio Santos, C.J., Alves, Clebert José

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57202020097; 57210112070; 57191431738; 59157839100; 55879694100; 56841381600; 21735433500; 57226614998; 57324382400; 26654053700

Leptospira spp. of the Urinary Tract of Female Carrier Goats in Semi-Arid Conditions
(2022) Acta Scientiae Veterinariae, 50, art. no. 1872

DOI: 10.22456/1679-9216.124079

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[85138206730&doi=10.22456%2F1679-](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85138206730&doi=10.22456%2F1679-9216.124079&partnerID=40&md5=8bbf49a2b2fca75a8cfa7120d99b8445)

[9216.124079&partnerID=40&md5=8bbf49a2b2fca75a8cfa7120d99b8445](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85138206730&doi=10.22456%2F1679-9216.124079&partnerID=40&md5=8bbf49a2b2fca75a8cfa7120d99b8445)

105) DOCUMENT TYPE: Article

OPEN ACCESS: ALL OPEN ACCESS; GOLD OPEN ACCESS

E.M., Rees, Eleanor M., C.L., Lau, Colleen L., M., Kama, Mike, S.A., Reid, Simon Andrew, R., Lowe, Rachel, A.J., Kucharski, Adam J.

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(57218207228); 57002151900; 55232631100; 7201777637; 36135810500; 54883807400

Estimating the duration of antibody positivity and likely time of Leptospira infection

using data from a cross-sectional serological study in Fiji
(2022) PLOS Neglected Tropical Diseases, 16 (6), art. no. e0010506

DOI: 10.1371/JOURNAL.PNTD.0010506

[https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85133103197&doi=10.1371%2FJOURNAL.PNTD.0010506&partnerID=40&md5=cbffb49b015818d5665aee1c487e1cd9)

[85133103197&doi=10.1371%2FJOURNAL.PNTD.0010506&partnerID=40&md5=cbffb49](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85133103197&doi=10.1371%2FJOURNAL.PNTD.0010506&partnerID=40&md5=cbffb49b015818d5665aee1c487e1cd9)

[b015818d5665aee1c487e1cd9](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85133103197&doi=10.1371%2FJOURNAL.PNTD.0010506&partnerID=40&md5=cbffb49b015818d5665aee1c487e1cd9)

106) DOCUMENT TYPE: Article

OPEN ACCESS: ALL OPEN ACCESS; GOLD OPEN ACCESS; GREEN ACCEPTED

OPEN ACCESS; GREEN FINAL OPEN ACCESS; GREEN OPEN ACCESS

P., Hernández-Rodríguez, Patricia, B., Trujillo-Rojas, Brayam

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One health: a comprehensive approach to improve prevention and control strategies in

Leptospirosis
(2022) Revista de Ciencias Agroveterinarias, 21 (1), pp. 71 - 78

DOI: 10.5965/223811712112022071

[https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85127193536&doi=10.5965%2F223811712112022071&partnerID=40&md5=bf70992c9ff39e064ee5576697032618)

[85127193536&doi=10.5965%2F223811712112022071&partnerID=40&md5=bf70992c9ff39](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85127193536&doi=10.5965%2F223811712112022071&partnerID=40&md5=bf70992c9ff39e064ee5576697032618)

[e064ee5576697032618](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85127193536&doi=10.5965%2F223811712112022071&partnerID=40&md5=bf70992c9ff39e064ee5576697032618)

107) DOCUMENT TYPE: Article

OPEN ACCESS: ALL OPEN ACCESS; GOLD OPEN ACCESS

A.E.P., Silva, Ana Elisa Pereira, M.d.R.D.d.O., Latorre, Maria do Rosario Dias de

Oliveira, F.C., Neto, Francisco Chiaravalloti, G.M.d.S., Conceição, Gleice Margarete de

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57188571715; 35447169500; 57214172040; 35450464300

Temporal trends in leptospirosis incidence and association with climatic and environmental factors in the state of Santa Catarina, Brazil Tendência temporal da leptospirose e sua associação com variáveis climáticas e ambientais em Santa Catarina, Brasil

(2022) *Ciencia e Saude Coletiva*, 27 (3), pp. 849 - 860

DOI: 10.1590/1413-81232022273.45982020

[https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85126993853&doi=10.1590%2F1413-81232022273.45982020&partnerID=40&md5=ac09ce04bf2269842791c8131575a958)

[85126993853&doi=10.1590%2F1413-](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85126993853&doi=10.1590%2F1413-81232022273.45982020&partnerID=40&md5=ac09ce04bf2269842791c8131575a958)

[81232022273.45982020&partnerID=40&md5=ac09ce04bf2269842791c8131575a958](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85126993853&doi=10.1590%2F1413-81232022273.45982020&partnerID=40&md5=ac09ce04bf2269842791c8131575a958)

108) DOCUMENT TYPE: Article

OPEN ACCESS: ALL OPEN ACCESS; GOLD OPEN ACCESS

A., Retnowati, Ambar, A., Indrawati, Agustin, U.K., Hadi, Upik Kesumawati, S., Safika, Safika, S.M., Noor, Susan M.

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57453891300; 57115388700; 7004202457; 57574640500; 57212565894

Distribution Serovar and Risk Factors on the Incidence of Canine Leptospirosis after Flood in Jakarta, Indonesia Taburan Serovar dan Faktor Risiko terhadap Kejadian Leptospirosis Anjing Selepas Banjir di Jakarta, Indonesia

(2022) *Sains Malaysiana*, 51 (1), pp. 261 - 269

DOI: 10.17576/jsm-2022-5101-21

[https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85124665330&doi=10.17576%2Fjsm-2022-5101-21&partnerID=40&md5=086b74bfa522145f1e9facbba22743a8)

[85124665330&doi=10.17576%2Fjsm-2022-5101-](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85124665330&doi=10.17576%2Fjsm-2022-5101-21&partnerID=40&md5=086b74bfa522145f1e9facbba22743a8)

[21&partnerID=40&md5=086b74bfa522145f1e9facbba22743a8](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85124665330&doi=10.17576%2Fjsm-2022-5101-21&partnerID=40&md5=086b74bfa522145f1e9facbba22743a8)

109) DOCUMENT TYPE: Article

OPEN ACCESS: ALL OPEN ACCESS; GOLD OPEN ACCESS; GREEN ACCEPTED OPEN ACCESS; GREEN OPEN ACCESS

M., Convertino, Matteo, A., Reddy, A., Y., Liu, Y., C.A., Muñoz-Zanzi, Claudia A.

AUTHOR FULL NAMES: Convertino, Matteo (57203266050); Reddy, A. (59845809400); Liu, Y. (57205567422); Muñoz-Zanzi, Claudia A. (6602544065)

57203266050; 59845809400; 57205567422; 6602544065

Eco-epidemiological scaling of Leptospirosis: Vulnerability mapping and early warning forecasts

(2021) *Science of the Total Environment*, 799, art. no. 149102

DOI: 10.1016/j.scitotenv.2021.149102

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[85112485211&doi=10.1016%2Fj.scitotenv.2021.149102&partnerID=40&md5=f267da6c065b15f1c02fdb6b28a4c729](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85112485211&doi=10.1016%2Fj.scitotenv.2021.149102&partnerID=40&md5=f267da6c065b15f1c02fdb6b28a4c729)

110) DOCUMENT TYPE: Article

V., Mittal, Vineeta, P., Singh, Peetam, S., Shukla, Surabhi, R., Karoli, Ritu
AUTHOR FULL NAMES: Mittal, Vineeta (37016459400); Singh, Peetam (57212592096);
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37016459400; 57212592096; 57222222082; 36052902200
Scrub typhus: An under-reported and emerging threat - hospital based study from
central and eastern Uttar Pradesh, India
(2021) Journal of Vector Borne Diseases, 58 (4), pp. 323 - 328
DOI: 10.4103/0972-9062.318311
<https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85127652708&doi=10.4103%2F0972-9062.318311&partnerID=40&md5=271757a41ea410d26ab664937bb79390>

111) DOCUMENT TYPE: Article

OPEN ACCESS: ALL OPEN ACCESS; GOLD OPEN ACCESS

M., Sevillano, Maria, S., Vosloo, Solize, I., Cotto, Irmarié, Z., Dai, Zihan, T., Jiang, Tao,
J.M., Santiago-Santana, José M., I.Y., Padilla, Ingrid Y., Z.Y., Rosario-Pabón, Zaira Y.,
C.M., Vélez-Vega, Carmen Milagros, J.F., Cordero, José F.
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(57189952195); Cotto, Irmarié (57211604435); Dai, Zihan (57211607730); Jiang, Tao
(57201856624); Santiago-Santana, José M. (35180335300); Padilla, Ingrid Y.
(14069097900); Rosario-Pabón, Zaira Y. (56676307100); Vélez-Vega, Carmen Milagros
(42162227400); Cordero, José F. (57208384016)
57218565864; 57189952195; 57211604435; 57211607730; 57201856624; 35180335300;
14069097900; 56676307100; 42162227400; 57208384016
Spatial-temporal targeted and non-targeted surveys to assess microbiological
composition of drinking water in Puerto Rico following Hurricane Maria
(2021) Water Research X, 13, art. no. 100123
DOI: 10.1016/j.wroa.2021.100123
<https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85122804385&doi=10.1016%2Fj.wroa.2021.100123&partnerID=40&md5=6a656ffa298546306961ed8b36458574>

112) DOCUMENT TYPE: Article

OPEN ACCESS: ALL OPEN ACCESS; GOLD OPEN ACCESS; GREEN ACCEPTED
OPEN ACCESS; GREEN FINAL OPEN ACCESS; GREEN OPEN ACCESS

J.D., da Silva, José Dêvede, M.P., Viana, Maira Pôrto, L.G., Lima Pereira Calado, Lucas
Gonzales, A.M.C., Lima, Ana Milena Cesar, F.S., Fernandes Alves, Francisco Selmo,
R.R., Pinheiro, Raymundo Rinaldo, D.F., da Costa, Diego Figueiredo, G.C., Pinheiro da
Silva, Glaucenyra Cecília, S.S., de Azevedo, Sergio Santos, C.J., Alves, Clebert José
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Raymundo Rizaldo (7004083193); da Costa, Diego Figueiredo (57189056104); Pinheiro da Silva, Glaucenyra Cecília (57209509633); de Azevedo, Sergio Santos (57324382400); Alves, Clebert José (26654053700)

57211373435; 57210120171; 57324382300; 57195724574; 35751167200; 7004083193; 57189056104; 57209509633; 57324382400; 26654053700

Cross-sectional survey for sheep leptospirosis in the northeast region of Brazil

(2021) Preventive Veterinary Medicine, 197, art. no. 105525

DOI: 10.1016/j.prevetmed.2021.105525

[https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85118529569&doi=10.1016%2Fj.prevetmed.2021.105525&partnerID=40&md5=de7541126b55e1344d69afc573f1830a)

[85118529569&doi=10.1016%2Fj.prevetmed.2021.105525&partnerID=40&md5=de7541126b55e1344d69afc573f1830a](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85118529569&doi=10.1016%2Fj.prevetmed.2021.105525&partnerID=40&md5=de7541126b55e1344d69afc573f1830a)

113) DOCUMENT TYPE: Article

Y., Ma, Yan, G., Destouni, Georgia, Z., Kalantari, Zahra, A.W., Werner-Omazic, Anna Werner, B., Evengård, Birgitta, C., Berggren, Camilla, T.K.E., Thierfelder, Tomas K.E. AUTHOR FULL NAMES: Ma, Yan (57211190811); Destouni, Georgia (7004302008); Kalantari, Zahra (21742320500); Werner-Omazic, Anna Werner (55790201200); Evengård, Birgitta (55950257700); Berggren, Camilla (57208321731); Thierfelder, Tomas K.E. (6603320488)

57211190811; 7004302008; 21742320500; 55790201200; 55950257700; 57208321731; 6603320488

Linking climate and infectious disease trends in the Northern/Arctic Region

(2021) Scientific Reports, 11 (1), art. no. 20678

DOI: 10.1038/s41598-021-00167-z

[https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85117735613&doi=10.1038%2Fs41598-021-00167-z&partnerID=40&md5=874913f29263d753923d9530067811ac)

[85117735613&doi=10.1038%2Fs41598-021-00167-z&partnerID=40&md5=874913f29263d753923d9530067811ac](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85117735613&doi=10.1038%2Fs41598-021-00167-z&partnerID=40&md5=874913f29263d753923d9530067811ac)

114) DOCUMENT TYPE: Article

OPEN ACCESS: ALL OPEN ACCESS; GOLD OPEN ACCESS; GREEN FINAL OPEN ACCESS; GREEN OPEN ACCESS

D.M., Vega Ocasio, Denisse M., J.G., Perez-Ramos, José G., T.D., Dye, Timothy D.

AUTHOR FULL NAMES: Vega Ocasio, Denisse M. (57208530682); Perez-Ramos, José G. (57212565719); Dye, Timothy D. (7005345674)

57208530682; 57212565719; 7005345674

“Y no quedó nada, nada de la casa, todo salió volando” (And there was nothing left, nothing of the house, everything flew away): a critical medical ecological perspective on the lived experience of hurricane María in Puerto Rico

(2021) BMC Public Health, 21 (1), art. no. 1833

DOI: 10.1186/s12889-021-11847-w

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[85116801096&doi=10.1186%2Fs12889-021-11847-w&partnerID=40&md5=f7d8253fa59e7cc27917a668044dcd50](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85116801096&doi=10.1186%2Fs12889-021-11847-w&partnerID=40&md5=f7d8253fa59e7cc27917a668044dcd50)

115) DOCUMENT TYPE: Article

OPEN ACCESS: ALL OPEN ACCESS; GOLD OPEN ACCESS; GREEN FINAL OPEN ACCESS; GREEN OPEN ACCESS

N.D.B., Ehelepola, N. D.B., K.A.M., Ariyaratne, Kusalika A.M., A.M.S.M.C.M., Aththanayake, A. M.S.M.C.M., S.M.K.B., Samarakoon, S. M.K.B., H.M.A., Thilakarathna, H. M.Arjuna

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57190576897; 57190570257; 57224095876; 35956839500; 57224077370

The correlation between three teleconnections and leptospirosis incidence in the Kandy District, Sri Lanka, 2004–2019

(2021) Tropical Medicine and Health, 49 (1), art. no. 43

DOI: 10.1186/s41182-021-00325-z

[https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85106963074&doi=10.1186%2Fs41182-021-00325-z&partnerID=40&md5=80a75b3a04bf0b9a18937213865cb148)

[85106963074&doi=10.1186%2Fs41182-021-00325-](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85106963074&doi=10.1186%2Fs41182-021-00325-z&partnerID=40&md5=80a75b3a04bf0b9a18937213865cb148)

[z&partnerID=40&md5=80a75b3a04bf0b9a18937213865cb148](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85106963074&doi=10.1186%2Fs41182-021-00325-z&partnerID=40&md5=80a75b3a04bf0b9a18937213865cb148)

116) DOCUMENT TYPE: Article

OPEN ACCESS: ALL OPEN ACCESS; GOLD OPEN ACCESS; GREEN FINAL OPEN ACCESS; GREEN OPEN ACCESS

S., Maleki, Shahram, A., Zakian, Amir, G.R., Abdollahpour, Gholamreza R.

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57223053125; 56148237000; 7801422582

Seroepidemiology of leptospira interrogans infection in ruminants of Lorestan Province: A cross-sectional study

(2021) Journal of Veterinary Research, 75 (4), pp. 486 - 497

DOI: 10.22059/JVR.2019.269334.2869

[https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85104570402&doi=10.22059%2FJVR.2019.269334.2869&partnerID=40&md5=a3dece1fba)

[85104570402&doi=10.22059%2FJVR.2019.269334.2869&partnerID=40&md5=a3dece1fba](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85104570402&doi=10.22059%2FJVR.2019.269334.2869&partnerID=40&md5=a3dece1fba)
[d6d9b954a2154e1f1b53a4](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85104570402&doi=10.22059%2FJVR.2019.269334.2869&partnerID=40&md5=a3dece1fba)

117) DOCUMENT TYPE: Article

S., Chadsuthi, Sudarat, K., Chalvet-Monfray, Karine, A., Wiratsudakul, Anuwat, C., Modchang, Charin

AUTHOR FULL NAMES: Chadsuthi, Sudarat (33067633200); Chalvet-Monfray, Karine

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33067633200; 6602803804; 37023697200; 8370771600

The effects of flooding and weather conditions on leptospirosis transmission in Thailand

(2021) Scientific Reports, 11 (1), art. no. 1486

DOI: 10.1038/s41598-020-79546-x

<https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85100111480&doi=10.1038%2Fs41598-020-79546-x&partnerID=40&md5=48e1f450d7d08eb4b436e2c071acbb1c>

118) DOCUMENT TYPE: Article

OPEN ACCESS: ALL OPEN ACCESS; GOLD OPEN ACCESS; GREEN FINAL OPEN ACCESS; GREEN OPEN ACCESS

E.B., Miller, Erin B., V.A., Barragán, Verónica Alexandra, J., Chiriboga, Jorge, C., Weddell, Chad, L., Luna, Ligia, D.J., Jiménez, Dulce J., J., Aleman, John, J.R., Mihaljevic, Joseph R., S.M., Olivas, Sonora M., J.C., Marks, Jane Claire

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57191614607; 24767738100; 56404471200; 57221329339; 57190279432; 57218200552; 57221327009; 54989421400; 56080125600; 7402797143

Leptospira in river and soil in a highly endemic area of Ecuador
(2021) BMC Microbiology, 21 (1), art. no. 17

DOI: 10.1186/s12866-020-02069-y

[https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85098881417&doi=10.1186%2Fs12866-020-02069-y&partnerID=40&md5=68941f4423e84dd965c65c35ef93414a)

[85098881417&doi=10.1186%2Fs12866-020-02069-](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85098881417&doi=10.1186%2Fs12866-020-02069-y&partnerID=40&md5=68941f4423e84dd965c65c35ef93414a)

[y&partnerID=40&md5=68941f4423e84dd965c65c35ef93414a](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85098881417&doi=10.1186%2Fs12866-020-02069-y&partnerID=40&md5=68941f4423e84dd965c65c35ef93414a)

119) DOCUMENT TYPE: Article

OPEN ACCESS: ALL OPEN ACCESS; GOLD OPEN ACCESS; GREEN FINAL OPEN ACCESS; GREEN OPEN ACCESS

M.M., Obaidat, Mohammad M., L., Malania, Lile, A.E., Bani Salman, Alaa E., A., Dreyfus, Anou, R.J., Arner, Ryan J., A.A., Roess, Amira A.

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56252880900; 26429802800; 56412009200; 56027707900; 57209860381; 6506150180

Seroprevalence and risk factors of Leptospira sp. Among different groups in the Jordanian population: First study

(2021) Transactions of the Royal Society of Tropical Medicine and Hygiene, 115 (11), pp. 1260 - 1264

DOI: 10.1093/trstmh/trab147

[https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85119594586&doi=10.1093%2Ftrstmh%2Ftrab147&partnerID=40&md5=97f469f491ab426b1a5eddf7465c8180)

[85119594586&doi=10.1093%2Ftrstmh%2Ftrab147&partnerID=40&md5=97f469f491ab426b1a5eddf7465c8180](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85119594586&doi=10.1093%2Ftrstmh%2Ftrab147&partnerID=40&md5=97f469f491ab426b1a5eddf7465c8180)

120) DOCUMENT TYPE: Article

OPEN ACCESS: ALL OPEN ACCESS; BRONZE OPEN ACCESS

N.L., Syakbanah, Nur Lathifah, A., Fuad, Anis
AUTHOR FULL NAMES: Syakbanah, Nur Lathifah (58667800000); Fuad, Anis
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HUMAN LEPTOSPIROSIS OUTBREAK: A YEAR AFTER THE 'CEMPAKA'
TROPICAL CYCLONE
(2021) *Jurnal Kesehatan Lingkungan*, 13 (4), pp. 211 - 218
DOI: 10.20473/jkl.v13i4.2021.211-218
<https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85143048734&doi=10.20473%2Fjkl.v13i4.2021.211-218&partnerID=40&md5=0341965adcf8024563bb1b48ea74b189>

121) DOCUMENT TYPE: Article
OPEN ACCESS: ALL OPEN ACCESS; GOLD OPEN ACCESS

D.A., Haake, David A., R.L., Galloway, Renee Lynn
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Leptospiral Infections in Humans
(2021) *Clinical Microbiology Newsletter*, 43 (20), pp. 173 - 180
DOI: 10.1016/j.clinmicnews.2021.09.002
<https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85116398946&doi=10.1016%2Fj.clinmicnews.2021.09.002&partnerID=40&md5=ce459e1fd8202e2464799ef0b0f34735>

122) DOCUMENT TYPE: Article

K., Jeske, Kathrin, D., Emirhar, Duygu, J.T., García, Jesús T., D., González-Barrio,
David, P.P., Olea, Pedro P., F.R., Fons, Francisco Ruiz, J., Schulz, Jana, A., Mayer-Scholl,
Anne, G., Heckel, Gerald, R.G., Ulrich, Rainer Günter
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(57191224254); Mayer-Scholl, Anne (8105296400); Heckel, Gerald (6602994529); Ulrich,
Rainer Günter (7201561767)
57195929275; 57211907410; 32867673500; 57214284673; 7801594197; 26537334600;
57191224254; 8105296400; 6602994529; 7201561767
Frequent leptospira spp. Detection but absence of tula orthohantavirus in microtus
spp. voles, Northwestern Spain
(2021) *Journal of Wildlife Diseases*, 57 (4), pp. 733 - 742
DOI: 10.7589/JWD-D-20-00109
<https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85115740604&doi=10.7589%2FJWD-D-20-00109&partnerID=40&md5=b91a9a95b7f22cb6846036e5fd064866>

123) DOCUMENT TYPE: Article

A.S., Tabucanon, Allan Sriratana, K.H., Kurisu, Kiyo H., K., Hanaki, Keisuke
AUTHOR FULL NAMES: Tabucanon, Allan Sriratana (57213594148); Kurisu, Kiyo H.
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57213594148; 37063481000; 7005876233
Assessment and mitigation of tangible flood damages driven by climate change in a
tropical city: Hat Yai Municipality, southern Thailand
(2021) *Science of the Total Environment*, 789, art. no. 147983
DOI: 10.1016/j.scitotenv.2021.147983
[https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-
85107673726&doi=10.1016%2Fj.scitotenv.2021.147983&partnerID=40&md5=dae33e8537
2ee81d86a79c44c6bd5560](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85107673726&doi=10.1016%2Fj.scitotenv.2021.147983&partnerID=40&md5=dae33e85372ee81d86a79c44c6bd5560)

124) DOCUMENT TYPE: Article

OPEN ACCESS: ALL OPEN ACCESS; BRONZE OPEN ACCESS

S., Selvarajah, Sujitha, S., Ran, Shaolu, N.W., Roberts, Nia Wyn, M., Nair, Manisha
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57217227092; 57223855551; 7202129640; 57200584349
Leptospirosis in pregnancy: A systematic review
(2021) *PLOS Neglected Tropical Diseases*, 15 (9), art. no. e0009747
DOI: 10.1371/journal.pntd.0009747
[https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-
85116450755&doi=10.1371%2Fjournal.pntd.0009747&partnerID=40&md5=02f3219167ed
ae2d3b9ee22514347d76](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85116450755&doi=10.1371%2Fjournal.pntd.0009747&partnerID=40&md5=02f3219167edae2d3b9ee22514347d76)

125) DOCUMENT TYPE: Article

OPEN ACCESS: ALL OPEN ACCESS; GOLD OPEN ACCESS; GREEN FINAL OPEN
ACCESS; GREEN OPEN ACCESS

M., Guzmán Pérez, Marta, J.J., Blanch-Sancho, José Javier, J.C., Segura-Luque, Juan
Carlos, F.G., Mateos-Rodríguez, Fernando González, E.M., Martínez-Alfaro, Elisa
Martnez, J., Solís García del Pozo, Julián
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57253141600; 6603151945; 6507449740; 7005919327; 6701589854; 55928085400
Current evidence on the antimicrobial treatment and chemoprophylaxis of human
leptospirosis: A meta-analysis
(2021) *Pathogens*, 10 (9), art. no. 1125
DOI: 10.3390/pathogens10091125
[https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-
85114611245&doi=10.3390%2Fpathogens10091125&partnerID=40&md5=850b456e56b16
262dbde41ce9407fe4c](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85114611245&doi=10.3390%2Fpathogens10091125&partnerID=40&md5=850b456e56b16262dbde41ce9407fe4c)

126) DOCUMENT TYPE: Article

OPEN ACCESS: ALL OPEN ACCESS; GOLD OPEN ACCESS; GREEN FINAL OPEN ACCESS; GREEN OPEN ACCESS

J., Viroj, Jaruwat, J., Claude, Julien, C., Lajaunie, Claire, J., Cappelle, Julien, A., Kritiyakan, Anamika, P., Thuainan, Pornsit, W., Chewnarupai, Worachet, S., Morand, Serge

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57225210958; 57214204474; 56523046200; 24449355500; 26032623400; 57225211496; 57225209991; 7006833126

Agro-environmental determinants of leptospirosis: A retrospective spatiotemporal analysis (2004–2014) in Mahasarakham Province (Thailand)

(2021) Tropical Medicine and Infectious Disease, 6 (3), art. no. 115

DOI: 10.3390/tropicalmed6030115

[https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85109483306&doi=10.3390%2Ftropicalmed6030115&partnerID=40&md5=0948113f5de4dcd564fa27a8ad1b901f)

[85109483306&doi=10.3390%2Ftropicalmed6030115&partnerID=40&md5=0948113f5de4dcd564fa27a8ad1b901f](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85109483306&doi=10.3390%2Ftropicalmed6030115&partnerID=40&md5=0948113f5de4dcd564fa27a8ad1b901f)

127) DOCUMENT TYPE: Article

OPEN ACCESS: ALL OPEN ACCESS; GOLD OPEN ACCESS; GREEN FINAL OPEN ACCESS; GREEN OPEN ACCESS

C., Taylor, Collette, D.C., Brodbelt, David C., B.A., Dobson, Barnaby A., B., Catchpole, Briän, D.G., O'Neill, Dan G., K.B., Stevens, Kim B.

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55865041800; 6603119980; 57204562563; 7003749480; 59157668000; 7202441130

Spatio-temporal distribution and agroecological factors associated with canine leptospirosis in Great Britain

(2021) Preventive Veterinary Medicine, 193, art. no. 105407

DOI: 10.1016/j.prevetmed.2021.105407

[https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85109160894&doi=10.1016%2Fj.prevetmed.2021.105407&partnerID=40&md5=b4b89c1e62b6c5c2c48e48b695fdf0c6)

[85109160894&doi=10.1016%2Fj.prevetmed.2021.105407&partnerID=40&md5=b4b89c1e62b6c5c2c48e48b695fdf0c6](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85109160894&doi=10.1016%2Fj.prevetmed.2021.105407&partnerID=40&md5=b4b89c1e62b6c5c2c48e48b695fdf0c6)

128) DOCUMENT TYPE: Article

OPEN ACCESS: ALL OPEN ACCESS; GREEN FINAL OPEN ACCESS; GREEN OPEN ACCESS; HYBRID GOLD OPEN ACCESS

C.M., Monteiro, Caio Márcio, L.L., Ferreira, Lorena Lopes, L.G.F., de Paula, Luiza Gabriella Ferreira, J.G., de Oliveira Filho, Jaires Gomes, F., de Oliveira Silva, Fernanda, E.R., Muniz, Elen Regozino, K.M.F., Menezes, Karolina Martins Ferreira, F.R., de

Camargo, Fabrício Rômulo, R., de Oliveira Nonato, Rhayssa, D.B., Martins, Danieli Brolo

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57194282732; 36025270400; 57204167901; 56490551400; 57216857816; 57193230478; 57204159988; 57224627315; 57224630871; 15765676200

Thymol and eugenol microemulsion for *Rhipicephalus sanguineus* sensu lato control: Formulation development, field efficacy, and safety on dogs

(2021) *Veterinary Parasitology*, 296, art. no. 109501

DOI: 10.1016/j.vetpar.2021.109501

[https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85108072877&doi=10.1016%2Fj.vetpar.2021.109501&partnerID=40&md5=85e112fc01c8fe5f8f0a59e6c4413582)

[85108072877&doi=10.1016%2Fj.vetpar.2021.109501&partnerID=40&md5=85e112fc01c8fe5f8f0a59e6c4413582](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85108072877&doi=10.1016%2Fj.vetpar.2021.109501&partnerID=40&md5=85e112fc01c8fe5f8f0a59e6c4413582)

129) DOCUMENT TYPE: Article

D., Rajput, Deepak, A.K., Gupta, Amit Kumar, S.S., Verma, Siddharth Shankar, G.S., Barabari, Geetha Sindhuri, A.A., Wani, Ajaz Ahmed, N., Kumar, Navin

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57215379868; 57214417135; 57218998598; 57221863547; 57221806450; 58704794900

Jaundice and Thrombocytopenia in an acute abdomen with concurrent Appendicitis and spontaneous Rectal perforation: An unusual presentation of human leptospirosis (2021) *Tropical Doctor*, 51 (3), pp. 427 - 431

DOI: 10.1177/0049475520981298

[https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85100511742&doi=10.1177%2F0049475520981298&partnerID=40&md5=e02a975d123b3ccad54a34f060dc2c63)

[85100511742&doi=10.1177%2F0049475520981298&partnerID=40&md5=e02a975d123b3ccad54a34f060dc2c63](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85100511742&doi=10.1177%2F0049475520981298&partnerID=40&md5=e02a975d123b3ccad54a34f060dc2c63)

130) DOCUMENT TYPE: Article

H., Houéménou, Honoré, P., Gauthier, Philippe, G., Houemenou, Gualbert, D., Mama, Daouda, A., Alassane, Abdoukarim, A.A., Socohou, Akilou Amadou, H.J., Dossou, Henri Joel, S.A., Badou, Sylvestre Adjakou, M., Picardeau, Mathieu, S., Tweed, S.

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Dossou, Henri Joel (57210969875); Badou, Sylvestre Adjakou (57211592777); Picardeau, Mathieu (6701694004); Tweed, S. (10340525800)

57212533212; 35821506800; 56470737500; 26425227700; 56497957600; 58740022200; 57210969875; 57211592777; 6701694004; 10340525800

Pathogenic *Leptospira* and water quality in African cities: A case study of Cotonou, Benin

(2021) *Science of the Total Environment*, 774, art. no. 145541

DOI: 10.1016/j.scitotenv.2021.145541

[https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85101332219&doi=10.1016%2Fj.scitotenv.2021.145541&partnerID=40&md5=324318f130bbf7d06d683b8d979b1102)

[85101332219&doi=10.1016%2Fj.scitotenv.2021.145541&partnerID=40&md5=324318f130bbf7d06d683b8d979b1102](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85101332219&doi=10.1016%2Fj.scitotenv.2021.145541&partnerID=40&md5=324318f130bbf7d06d683b8d979b1102)

131) DOCUMENT TYPE: Article

OPEN ACCESS: ALL OPEN ACCESS; GREEN FINAL OPEN ACCESS; GREEN OPEN ACCESS

G.F., Mgode, Georgies F., G.G., Mhamphi, Ginethon G., A.W., Massawe, Apia W., R.S., Machang'u, Robert S.

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Leptospira seropositivity in humans, livestock and wild animals in a semi-arid area of Tanzania

(2021) *Pathogens*, 10 (6), art. no. 696

DOI: 10.3390/pathogens10060696

[https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85108241449&doi=10.3390%2Fpathogens10060696&partnerID=40&md5=aaf18edc8f3e1623f8ba505d80f7dd34)

[85108241449&doi=10.3390%2Fpathogens10060696&partnerID=40&md5=aaf18edc8f3e1623f8ba505d80f7dd34](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85108241449&doi=10.3390%2Fpathogens10060696&partnerID=40&md5=aaf18edc8f3e1623f8ba505d80f7dd34)

132) DOCUMENT TYPE: Article

OPEN ACCESS: ALL OPEN ACCESS; GOLD OPEN ACCESS; GREEN FINAL OPEN ACCESS; GREEN OPEN ACCESS

J.N., Warnasekara, Janith Niwanthaka, S.B., Agampodi, Suneth Buddhika, R., Rupika Abeynayake, R.

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Time series models for prediction of leptospirosis in different climate zones in Sri Lanka

(2021) *PLOS ONE*, 16 (5 May), art. no. e0248032

DOI: 10.1371/journal.pone.0248032

[https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85106222333&doi=10.1371%2Fjournal.pone.0248032&partnerID=40&md5=825c8e930fa36606edd8a3ef5359e27d)

[85106222333&doi=10.1371%2Fjournal.pone.0248032&partnerID=40&md5=825c8e930fa36606edd8a3ef5359e27d](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85106222333&doi=10.1371%2Fjournal.pone.0248032&partnerID=40&md5=825c8e930fa36606edd8a3ef5359e27d)

133) DOCUMENT TYPE: Article

OPEN ACCESS: ALL OPEN ACCESS; GOLD OPEN ACCESS; GREEN ACCEPTED OPEN ACCESS; GREEN FINAL OPEN ACCESS; GREEN OPEN ACCESS

A.C., Peterson, Anna C., B.M., Gherzi, Bruno M., C., Riegel, Claudia, E.A., Wunder, Elsie Augusto, J.E., Childs, James E., M.J., Blum, Michael J.
AUTHOR FULL NAMES: Peterson, Anna C. (23994346000); Gherzi, Bruno M. (26649833600); Riegel, Claudia (22235613900); Wunder, Elsie Augusto (14008124800); Childs, James E. (7101840871); Blum, Michael J. (7202379952)
23994346000; 26649833600; 22235613900; 14008124800; 7101840871; 7202379952
Amplification of pathogenic *Leptospira* infection with greater abundance and co-occurrence of rodent hosts across a counter-urbanizing landscape
(2021) *Molecular Ecology*, 30 (9), pp. 2145 - 2161
DOI: 10.1111/mec.15710
<https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85096822237&doi=10.1111%2Fmec.15710&partnerID=40&md5=953e17bf9c7e50d30862924ba4ddb68>

134) DOCUMENT TYPE: Article

O.I., Zakharova, Olga I., F.I., Korennoy, F. I., I.V., Iashin, Ivan V., N.N., Toropova, Nadezhda N., A., Gogin, Andrey, D.V., Kolbasov, Denis V., G.V., Surkova, Galina V., S.M., Malkhazova, Svetlana M., A.A., Blokhin, Andrey A.
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57217229441; 46461328200; 57223125575; 57217239016; 55548937900; 48061254400; 6603986062; 6602455823; 57211407925
Ecological and Socio-Economic Determinants of Livestock Animal Leptospirosis in the Russian Arctic
(2021) *Frontiers in Veterinary Science*, 8, art. no. 658675
DOI: 10.3389/fvets.2021.658675
<https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85104960235&doi=10.3389%2Ffvets.2021.658675&partnerID=40&md5=2a978b7e75485430d2e5c26298892fc8>

135) DOCUMENT TYPE: Article

OPEN ACCESS: ALL OPEN ACCESS; GOLD OPEN ACCESS; GREEN FINAL OPEN ACCESS; GREEN OPEN ACCESS

I., Manabella Salcedo, Iris, J., Frascina, Jimena, M., Busch, María, J.S., Guidobono, Juan Santiago, J.M., Únzaga, Juan Manuel, A., Dellarupe, Andrea, M.I., Farace, María Isabel, N.C., Pini, Noemí C., V.A., León, Vanina Andrea
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57221924020; 54929670300; 7202387141; 23972849400; 6507558687; 56047161700; 7004657163; 6601971046; 26040843200

Role of *Mus musculus* in the transmission of several pathogens in poultry farms
(2021) *International Journal for Parasitology: Parasites and Wildlife*, 14, pp. 130 - 136
DOI: 10.1016/j.ijppaw.2021.01.007
<https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85100660273&doi=10.1016%2Fj.ijppaw.2021.01.007&partnerID=40&md5=58c5a70f1200e2fca6ee549e9e9834a5>

136) DOCUMENT TYPE: Article

OPEN ACCESS: ALL OPEN ACCESS; GOLD OPEN ACCESS; GREEN FINAL OPEN ACCESS; GREEN OPEN ACCESS

I.M., Keenum, Ishi M., M., Crespo-Medina, Melitza, E.D., Garner, Emily D., K.J., Pieper, Kelsey J., M.F., Blair, Matthew Forrest, E.G., Milligan, Erin G., A.J., Pruden, Amy J., G.I., Ramírez-Toro, Graciela I., W.J., Rhoads, William Joseph
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57211778392; 16306387100; 56197020800; 56825362600; 57205615249; 57221999050; 57049332700; 16455186200; 55538037800

Source-to-Tap Assessment of Microbiological Water Quality in Small Rural Drinking Water Systems in Puerto Rico Six Months after Hurricane Maria
(2021) *Environmental Science and Technology*, 55 (6), pp. 3775 - 3785
DOI: 10.1021/acs.est.0c08814
<https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85102964082&doi=10.1021%2Facs.est.0c08814&partnerID=40&md5=161f181416fc27ce87f2b1c696768e98>

137) DOCUMENT TYPE: Article

M.S., Abdul Rahman, Mohammad Sabri, S., Khairani-Bejo, Siti, Z., Zakaria, Zunita, L., Hassan, L., M., Azri Roslan, Mohd
AUTHOR FULL NAMES: Abdul Rahman, Mohammad Sabri (57205217579); Khairani-Bejo, Siti (15047903000); Zakaria, Zunita (36490971800); Hassan, L. (15044258900); Azri Roslan, Mohd (57223013875)
57205217579; 15047903000; 36490971800; 15044258900; 57223013875
Seroprevalence and distribution of leptospiral serovars in livestock (cattle, goats, and sheep) in flood-prone Kelantan, Malaysia
(2021) *Journal of Veterinary Research (Poland)*, 65 (1), pp. 53 - 58
DOI: 10.2478/jvetres-2021-0003
<https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85104376782&doi=10.2478%2Fjvetres-2021-0003&partnerID=40&md5=4e0c719bcbba79de6639358f69db61f1>

138) DOCUMENT TYPE: Article

OPEN ACCESS: ALL OPEN ACCESS; GOLD OPEN ACCESS; GREEN ACCEPTED OPEN ACCESS; GREEN FINAL OPEN ACCESS; GREEN OPEN ACCESS

L.A., Bernardez, Leticia Alonso, L.E.L., de Oliveira, Luis Eduardo L., L.R.P., De Andrade Lima, Luiz Rogério Pinho

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Acid mine drainage at the Bahia Gold Belt (Brazil): microbial isolation and characterization

(2021) Environmental Monitoring and Assessment, 193 (2), art. no. 60

DOI: 10.1007/s10661-021-08844-2

[https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85100125440&doi=10.1007%2Fs10661-021-08844-2&partnerID=40&md5=b9b8f8839f8e081471888ea82321707b)

[85100125440&doi=10.1007%2Fs10661-021-08844-](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85100125440&doi=10.1007%2Fs10661-021-08844-2&partnerID=40&md5=b9b8f8839f8e081471888ea82321707b)

[2&partnerID=40&md5=b9b8f8839f8e081471888ea82321707b](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85100125440&doi=10.1007%2Fs10661-021-08844-2&partnerID=40&md5=b9b8f8839f8e081471888ea82321707b)

139) DOCUMENT TYPE: Article

J.D., Gutiérrez, J. D.

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Effects of meteorological factors on human leptospirosis in Colombia

(2021) International Journal of Biometeorology, 65 (2), pp. 257 - 263

DOI: 10.1007/s00484-020-02028-2

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[85092338850&doi=10.1007%2Fs00484-020-02028-](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85092338850&doi=10.1007%2Fs00484-020-02028-2&partnerID=40&md5=2559d32f28c1c15af2617d8717022057)

[2&partnerID=40&md5=2559d32f28c1c15af2617d8717022057](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85092338850&doi=10.1007%2Fs00484-020-02028-2&partnerID=40&md5=2559d32f28c1c15af2617d8717022057)

140) DOCUMENT TYPE: Article

L., Biscornet, Leon, C., Révillion, Christophe, S., Jégo, Sylvaine, E., Lagadec, Erwan, Y., Gomard, Yann, G., Le Minter, Gildas, G.J., Rocamora, Gérard J., V., Guernier-Cambert, Vanina, J., Mélade, Julien, K., Dellagi, Koussay

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Yann (55364102000); Le Minter, Gildas (56539904200); Rocamora, Gérard J.

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Dellagi, Koussay (57207521526)

49460889200; 55843840500; 41461135400; 37072590600; 55364102000; 56539904200;

8099888900; 8600056000; 56147925500; 57207521526

Predicting the presence of leptospires in rodents from environmental indicators opens up opportunities for environmental monitoring of human leptospirosis

(2021) Remote Sensing, 13 (2), art. no. 325, pp. 1 - 19

DOI: 10.3390/rs13020325

[https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85099782138&doi=10.3390%2Fr13020325&partnerID=40&md5=edd147d0407dcae0defc21cb61a6a81a)

[85099782138&doi=10.3390%2Fr13020325&partnerID=40&md5=edd147d0407dcae0defc](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85099782138&doi=10.3390%2Fr13020325&partnerID=40&md5=edd147d0407dcae0defc21cb61a6a81a)

[21cb61a6a81a](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85099782138&doi=10.3390%2Fr13020325&partnerID=40&md5=edd147d0407dcae0defc21cb61a6a81a)

141) DOCUMENT TYPE: Article
OPEN ACCESS: ALL OPEN ACCESS; GOLD OPEN ACCESS; GREEN FINAL OPEN ACCESS; GREEN OPEN ACCESS

N.V., Breneva, N. V., S.V., Balakhonov, Sergey V., A.Y., Nikitin, A. Ya, I., Meltsov, Ivan, M.B., Sharakshanov, Munko B., V.V., Kuzmenkov, V. V., E.A., Sidorova, Elena A., A.V., Sevostyanova, A. V., S.S., Kulikalova, S. S., A.V., Mazepa, A. V.
AUTHOR FULL NAMES: Breneva, N. V. (6505879157); Balakhonov, Sergey V. (6602291694); Nikitin, A. Ya (57189099460); Meltsov, Ivan (57201722629); Sharakshanov, Munko B. (56495502200); Kuzmenkov, V. V. (59206640400); Sidorova, Elena A. (55354705000); Sevostyanova, A. V. (59206640500); Kulikalova, S. S. (59207916300); Mazepa, A. V. (59207370100)
6505879157; 6602291694; 57189099460; 57201722629; 56495502200; 59206640400; 55354705000; 59206640500; 59207916300; 59207370100
DETECTING AND PREDICTING RISKS RELAYED TO SPREAD OF NATURAL FOCI INFECTIONS ON FLOOD-AFFECTED TERRITORIES IN IRKUTSK REGION
(2021) Health Risk Analysis, 2021 (2), pp. 94 - 104
DOI: 10.21668/health.risk/2021.2.09.eng
<https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85156186863&doi=10.21668%2Fhealth.risk%2F2021.2.09.eng&partnerID=40&md5=e728beb76d094f29be51d4311e74f4cf>

142) DOCUMENT TYPE: Article
OPEN ACCESS: ALL OPEN ACCESS; GOLD OPEN ACCESS

T., Pustahija, Tatjana, V., Vukovic, Vladimir, M., Ristić, Miodjub, S.S., Savić, Sara S., Ž., Grgić, Živoslav, S., Rajčević, Smiljana, M., Strbac, Mirjana, T., Tomasevic, Tanja, S.N., Medić, Snežana N.
AUTHOR FULL NAMES: Pustahija, Tatjana (57208215604); Vukovic, Vladimir (56545340100); Ristić, Miodjub (38562085400); Savić, Sara S. (36728048800); Grgić, Živoslav (7003389037); Rajčević, Smiljana (54890716100); Strbac, Mirjana (57199730270); Tomasevic, Tanja (57207299337); Medić, Snežana N. (25224686600)
57208215604; 56545340100; 38562085400; 36728048800; 7003389037; 54890716100; 57199730270; 57207299337; 25224686600
EPIDEMIOLOGICAL CHARACTERISTICS OF LEPTOSPIROSIS IN VOJVODINA, SERBIA, 2009-2018, FROM THE ASPECT OF ONE HEALTH EPIDEMIOLOŠKE KARAKTERISTIKE LEPTOSPIROZE U VOJVODINI, SRBIJA, U PERIODU 2009-2018 – SA ASPEKTA JEDNOG ZDRAVLJA
(2021) Archives of Veterinary Medicine, 14 (1), pp. 69 - 84
DOI: 10.46784/eavm.v14i1.267
<https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85151022536&doi=10.46784%2Favm.v14i1.267&partnerID=40&md5=388b4a060659f712b3eb29d858b61847>

143) DOCUMENT TYPE: Article
OPEN ACCESS: ALL OPEN ACCESS; GOLD OPEN ACCESS

J.D., da Silva, José Dêvede, M.P., Viana, Maira Pôrto, L.G.L.P., Calado, Lucas Gonzales Lima Pereira, A.M.C., Lima, Ana Milena Cesar, F.S.F., Alves, Francisco Selmo Fernandes, R.R., Pinheiro, Raymundo Rizaldo, D.F., da Costa, Diego Figueiredo, G.C.P., da Silva, Glaucenyra Cecília Pinheiro, S.S., de Azevedo, Sergio Santos, C.J., Alves, Clebert José

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57211373435; 57210120171; 57224910178; 57195724574; 7005934306; 7004083193;

57189056104; 56121910800; 57324382400; 26654053700

Spatial Distribution of Serologically Reactive Sheep to *Leptospira* spp. in the Northeast Region of Brazil

(2021) *Acta Scientiae Veterinariae*, 49, art. no. 1837

DOI: 10.22456/1679-9216.118915

[https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85122820596&doi=10.22456%2F1679-9216.118915&partnerID=40&md5=cdf0fd46dd060b6a39816cd2b570b867)

85122820596&doi=10.22456%2F1679-

9216.118915&partnerID=40&md5=cdf0fd46dd060b6a39816cd2b570b867

144) DOCUMENT TYPE: Article

OPEN ACCESS: ALL OPEN ACCESS; GOLD OPEN ACCESS

R., Rajendran, Ramasamy, S.R., Karmakar, S. R., V.K., Garg, Vinay Kumar, R., Viswanathan, Rajlakshmi, K., Zaman, Kamran, S.B., Anusree, S. B., K., Regu, K., S.N., Sharma, Surender Nath

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8209036700; 57229976900; 57150152500; 35338601100; 56526374500; 57218892919;

15050966900; 7405877880

Post flood study on the incidence of leptospirosis in Alappuzha district of Kerala, India (2021) *Journal of Communicable Diseases*, 53 (3), pp. 127 - 134

DOI: 10.24321/0019.5138.202148

[https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85121425443&doi=10.24321%2F0019.5138.202148&partnerID=40&md5=595f2d2cb96ce1c53bbde322c76f5b14)

85121425443&doi=10.24321%2F0019.5138.202148&partnerID=40&md5=595f2d2cb96ce1c53bbde322c76f5b14

145) DOCUMENT TYPE: Article

OPEN ACCESS: ALL OPEN ACCESS; HYBRID GOLD OPEN ACCESS

N., Gupta, Nitin, W., Wilson, William, P., Ravindra, Prithvishree, S., Joylin, Sowmya, R., Bhat, Rachana, K., Saravu, Kavitha

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57208496731; 57196244733; 36149740000; 57223374500; 57219089480; 16834027500
Clinical profile, management and outcome of patients with leptospirosis during the times of covid-19 pandemic: A prospective study from a tertiary care centre in south india

(2021) Infezioni in Medicina, 29 (3), pp. 393 - 401

DOI: 10.53854/liim-2903-10

[https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85115350452&doi=10.53854%2Fliim-2903-10&partnerID=40&md5=d3bcc4f980446d4bd56f9b0da0992e10)

85115350452&doi=10.53854%2Fliim-2903-

10&partnerID=40&md5=d3bcc4f980446d4bd56f9b0da0992e10

146) DOCUMENT TYPE: Article

OPEN ACCESS: ALL OPEN ACCESS; BRONZE OPEN ACCESS; GREEN FINAL OPEN ACCESS; GREEN OPEN ACCESS

T., Jayakrishnan, Thayyil, S.V., Koramboor, Swathi Vipinan, A., Thottathan, Athira
AUTHOR FULL NAMES: Jayakrishnan, Thayyil (56700046900); Koramboor, Swathi Vipinan (57250564900); Thottathan, Athira (57251144700)

56700046900; 57250564900; 57251144700

Post flood chemoprophylaxis with doxycycline for leptospirosis in an endemic area; case control study

(2021) National Journal of Community Medicine, 12 (8), pp. 215 - 220

DOI: 10.5455/njcm.20210721054913

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85114514839&doi=10.5455%2Fnjcm.20210721054913&partnerID=40&md5=037af8f589db42a4065298fd7e12555f

147) DOCUMENT TYPE: Article

OPEN ACCESS: ALL OPEN ACCESS; GOLD OPEN ACCESS

A., Bhalraj, Abhineshwary, A.B., Azmi, Amirah Binti, M.H., Mohd, Mohd Hafiz
AUTHOR FULL NAMES: Bhalraj, Abhineshwary (57212460827); Azmi, Amirah Binti (57194234621); Mohd, Mohd Hafiz (57193909062)

57212460827; 57194234621; 57193909062

Analytical and Numerical Solutions of Leptospirosis Model

(2021) International Journal of Mathematics and Computer Science, 16 (3), pp. 949 - 961

[https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85111771416&partnerID=40&md5=d04fa2db2798567ffc0a2f5f4624181b)

85111771416&partnerID=40&md5=d04fa2db2798567ffc0a2f5f4624181b

148) DOCUMENT TYPE: Article

R.S.D., Moraes, Reiner Silveira De, A.F., Romani, Alana Flávia, A.V.C., do Amaral, Andréia Vitor Couto, D.Q., Cagnini, Didier Quevedo, L.S., Bonfim, Leuton Scharles, M.M., Andraschko, Mariana Moreira

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22985832100; 7102126069; 56009169200; 8663882700; 57219448744; 56011136400

Calcinosis Cutis with Large Extension and Uncommon Location in a Dog

(2021) Acta Scientiae Veterinariae, 49, art. no. 595

DOI: 10.22456/1679-9216.106730

[https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85108356205&doi=10.22456%2F1679-9216.106730&partnerID=40&md5=e0a7361afd3b1249ee62cfb53ae36256)

85108356205&doi=10.22456%2F1679-

9216.106730&partnerID=40&md5=e0a7361afd3b1249ee62cfb53ae36256

149) DOCUMENT TYPE: Article

OPEN ACCESS: ALL OPEN ACCESS; GOLD OPEN ACCESS

K.O., Douglas, Kirk Osmond, T.A., Samuels, Thelma Alafia, R.P., Ihezor-Ejiofor, Rommel Paneth, O.P., Vapalahti, Olli P., T.A., Sironen, Tarja A., M., Gittens-St.Hilaire, Marquita

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Serological evidence of human orthohantavirus infections in Barbados, 2008 to 2016

(2021) Pathogens, 10 (5), art. no. 571

DOI: 10.3390/pathogens10050571

[https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85106564108&doi=10.3390%2Fpathogens10050571&partnerID=40&md5=6083ee6ecfe548a18cc88de952dbd9c8)

85106564108&doi=10.3390%2Fpathogens10050571&partnerID=40&md5=6083ee6ecfe548a18cc88de952dbd9c8

150) DOCUMENT TYPE: Article

OPEN ACCESS: ALL OPEN ACCESS; GOLD OPEN ACCESS; GREEN FINAL OPEN ACCESS; GREEN OPEN ACCESS

R., Gracie, Renata, D.R., Xavier, Diego Ricardo, R.D.A., Medronho, Roberto De Andrade

AUTHOR FULL NAMES: Gracie, Renata (13205380200); Xavier, Diego Ricardo (55974415800); Medronho, Roberto De Andrade (21834194200) 13205380200; 55974415800; 21834194200

Floods and leptospirosis in Brazilian municipalities from 2003 to 2013: Use of data

mining techniques Inundações e leptospirose nos municípios brasileiros no período de 2003 a 2013: Utilização de técnicas de mineração de dados

(2021) Cadernos de Saude Publica, 37 (5), art. no. e00100119

DOI: 10.1590/0102-311X00100119

[https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85106203558&doi=10.1590%2F0102-311X00100119&partnerID=40&md5=166100eb5a3302249746e8dde0096368)

85106203558&doi=10.1590%2F0102-

311X00100119&partnerID=40&md5=166100eb5a3302249746e8dde0096368

151) DOCUMENT TYPE: Article
OPEN ACCESS: ALL OPEN ACCESS; GOLD OPEN ACCESS

R., Kira, Rosdi, L.M., Bilung, Lesley Maurice, R., Ngui, Romano, K.A., Apun, Kasing Ak, L., Suut, L.

AUTHOR FULL NAMES: Kira, Rosdi (57203892345); Bilung, Lesley Maurice (8983954700); Ngui, Romano (24598021000); Apun, Kasing Ak (6507666614); Suut, L. (55976680500)

57203892345; 8983954700; 24598021000; 6507666614; 55976680500

Spatially varying correlation between environmental conditions and human leptospirosis in Sarawak, Malaysia

(2021) Tropical Biomedicine, 38 (2), pp. 31 - 39

DOI: 10.47665/TB.38.2.034

[https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85105767135&doi=10.47665%2FTB.38.2.034&partnerID=40&md5=b70170441e10e8df87859feb5737a3b9)

[85105767135&doi=10.47665%2FTB.38.2.034&partnerID=40&md5=b70170441e10e8df87859feb5737a3b9](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85105767135&doi=10.47665%2FTB.38.2.034&partnerID=40&md5=b70170441e10e8df87859feb5737a3b9)

152) DOCUMENT TYPE: Article
OPEN ACCESS: ALL OPEN ACCESS; BRONZE OPEN ACCESS; GREEN ACCEPTED OPEN ACCESS; GREEN OPEN ACCESS

J.P.D.O., Sena, Jaricélia Patrícia De Oliveira, J.M., de Moraes Neto, João Miguel, D.B., Lucena, Daisy Beserra

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General vulnerability index regarding the municipalities in brazilian semi-arid region
Índice de vulnerabilidade geral dos municípios do semiárido brasileiro

(2021) Revista Brasileira de Geografia Física, 14 (1), pp. 310 - 321

DOI: 10.26848/rbgf.v14.1.p310-321

[https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85105125423&doi=10.26848%2Frbgf.v14.1.p310-321&partnerID=40&md5=9ebdae38a6f3d2b0f4b1316b458659ff)

[85105125423&doi=10.26848%2Frbgf.v14.1.p310-321&partnerID=40&md5=9ebdae38a6f3d2b0f4b1316b458659ff](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85105125423&doi=10.26848%2Frbgf.v14.1.p310-321&partnerID=40&md5=9ebdae38a6f3d2b0f4b1316b458659ff)

153) DOCUMENT TYPE: Article
OPEN ACCESS: ALL OPEN ACCESS; GOLD OPEN ACCESS

E.D.M., Teixeira, Elisa De Menezes, R.O., Rodrigues, Rogério O., V.B.D., Rosa, Verônica Bueno Da, A.C.C., Bertagnolli, Angélica Cavalheiro Cavalheiro

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57223136578; 57201301732; 59789847600; 7801310907

Anti-Leptospira spp antibodies in cart horses of the city of Guaíba, Rio Grande do sul State, Brazil
Anticorpos anti-Leptospira spp em cavalos carroceiros da cidade de Guaíba, Rio Grande do Sul, Brasil

(2021) Acta Veterinaria Brasilica, 15 (1), pp. 5 - 8

DOI: 10.21708/AVB.2021.15.1.9618

<https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85104947602&doi=10.21708%2FAVB.2021.15.1.9618&partnerID=40&md5=42100f0a9dde144c55c3363232ee8e11>

154) DOCUMENT TYPE: Article
OPEN ACCESS: ALL OPEN ACCESS; GOLD OPEN ACCESS

B., Li, Binbin, C., Bao, Chunmiao

AUTHOR FULL NAMES: Li, Binbin (57217019949); Bao, Chunmiao (57222994924)
57217019949; 57222994924

Disparity in clinical characteristics between 2019 novel coronavirus pneumonia and leptospirosis

(2021) Open Medicine (Poland), 16 (1), pp. 494 - 497

DOI: 10.1515/med-2021-0262

[https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85104321862&doi=10.1515%2Fmed-2021-0262&partnerID=40&md5=0e4a7a218e47e57628ea5f57f386e50c)

[85104321862&doi=10.1515%2Fmed-2021-](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85104321862&doi=10.1515%2Fmed-2021-0262&partnerID=40&md5=0e4a7a218e47e57628ea5f57f386e50c)

[0262&partnerID=40&md5=0e4a7a218e47e57628ea5f57f386e50c](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85104321862&doi=10.1515%2Fmed-2021-0262&partnerID=40&md5=0e4a7a218e47e57628ea5f57f386e50c)

155) DOCUMENT TYPE: Article
OPEN ACCESS: ALL OPEN ACCESS; GOLD OPEN ACCESS; GREEN FINAL OPEN ACCESS; GREEN OPEN ACCESS

R.M., Parameswaran, Rajeshkumar M., S.P., Sundaran, Sushama P., R.T., Parakkadavath, Rakesh T.

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BreaDoxy sandwich for leptospirosis prophylaxis

(2021) Tropical Doctor, 51 (1), pp. 102 - 103

DOI: 10.1177/0049475520959909

[https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85091680044&doi=10.1177%2F0049475520959909&partnerID=40&md5=bdd359a0a7c941ff41778dbf4e50467f)

[85091680044&doi=10.1177%2F0049475520959909&partnerID=40&md5=bdd359a0a7c941ff41778dbf4e50467f](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85091680044&doi=10.1177%2F0049475520959909&partnerID=40&md5=bdd359a0a7c941ff41778dbf4e50467f)

156) DOCUMENT TYPE: Article

L.S., Dos Santos Medeiros, Luciana S., S.C., Braga Domingos, Susan Christina, M.I.N.D., Azevedo, Maria Isabel Nogueira Di, R.C., Peruquetti, Rui Carlos, N.F., de Albuquerque, Narianne Ferreira, P.S., D'Andrea, Paulo Sergio, A.L.D.M., Botelho, André Luis De Moura, C.F., Crisóstomo, Charle Ferreira, A.S., Vieira, Anahí Souto, G.M.D.S., Martins, Gabriel Mendes De Souza

AUTHOR FULL NAMES: Dos Santos Medeiros, Luciana S. (22980324700); Braga Domingos, Susan Christina (57220814748); Azevedo, Maria Isabel Nogueira Di (57220810318); Peruquetti, Rui Carlos (6506445590); de Albuquerque, Narianne Ferreira (57193111740); D'Andrea, Paulo Sergio (7005979862); Botelho, André Luis De Moura

(59626447700); Crisóstomo, Charle Ferreira (57202781794); Vieira, Anahí Souto (36191386000); Martins, Gabriel Mendes De Souza (25959265200) 22980324700; 57220814748; 57220810318; 6506445590; 57193111740; 7005979862; 59626447700; 57202781794; 36191386000; 25959265200
Small Mammals as Carriers/Hosts of *Leptospira* spp. in the Western Amazon Forest (2020) *Frontiers in Veterinary Science*, 7, art. no. 569004
DOI: 10.3389/fvets.2020.569004
<https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85097669071&doi=10.3389%2Ffvets.2020.569004&partnerID=40&md5=21a8646d836a491acd426990dddb4d9b>

157) DOCUMENT TYPE: Article
OPEN ACCESS: ALL OPEN ACCESS; GOLD OPEN ACCESS; GREEN FINAL OPEN ACCESS; GREEN OPEN ACCESS

E.L., Emmanuel, Edward L.
AUTHOR FULL NAMES: Emmanuel, Edward L. (58629601800) 58629601800
Factors Contributing to the Occurrence of Leptospirosis, and the Impact on Public Health in Saint Lucia 2008-2019 (2020) *Texila International Journal of Public Health*, 8 (4)
DOI: 10.21522/TIJPH.2013.08.04.Art008
<https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85173061172&doi=10.21522%2FTIJPH.2013.08.04.Art008&partnerID=40&md5=4fbe37af2e4f9da5b2956530f52f2008>

158) DOCUMENT TYPE: Article
OPEN ACCESS: ALL OPEN ACCESS; BRONZE OPEN ACCESS

G., Chery, Gemma, L., Francis, Lorraine, S.A., Hunte, Shelly Ann, P., Leon, Phil
AUTHOR FULL NAMES: Chery, Gemma (57221281813); Francis, Lorraine (59094653200); Hunte, Shelly Ann (57218443437); Leon, Phil (57203515761) 57221281813; 59094653200; 57218443437; 57203515761
Epidemiology of human leptospirosis in Saint Lucia, 2010–2017 (2020) *Revista Panamericana de Salud Publica/Pan American Journal of Public Health*, 44, art. no. e160, pp. 1 - 8
DOI: 10.26633/RPSP.2020.163
<https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85098730129&doi=10.26633%2FRPSP.2020.163&partnerID=40&md5=d533198b5f1947590c91a4f9e38c855a>

159) DOCUMENT TYPE: Article
OPEN ACCESS: ALL OPEN ACCESS; GOLD OPEN ACCESS; GREEN FINAL OPEN ACCESS; GREEN OPEN ACCESS

F., Rahmat, Fariq, Z.D., Zulkafli, Zed Diyana, A.J., Ishak, Asnor Juraiza, S.B., Mohd Noor, S. B., H., Yahaya, Hazlina, A.S., Masrani, Afiqah Syamimi

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Exploratory Data Analysis and Artificial Neural Network for Prediction of Leptospirosis Occurrence in Seremban, Malaysia Based on Meteorological Data (2020) *Frontiers in Earth Science*, 8, art. no. 377
DOI: 10.3389/feart.2020.00377
<https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85097255305&doi=10.3389%2Ffeart.2020.00377&partnerID=40&md5=be3cc5e46f98423a8283fa1e35e22761>

160) DOCUMENT TYPE: Article

OPEN ACCESS: ALL OPEN ACCESS; GOLD OPEN ACCESS

A.M.K., Mohan Rao, A. M.K.

AUTHOR FULL NAMES: Mohan Rao, A. M.K. (36840700000)

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Rodent control a tool for prevention of leptospirosis - A success story on human leptospirosis with gujarat state

(2020) *Journal of Communicable Diseases*, 52 (3), pp. 38 - 42

DOI: 10.24321/0019.5138.202028

[https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85096870368&doi=10.24321%2F0019.5138.202028&partnerID=40&md5=2116ccf3058bbd263652b8a1f23e645a)

[85096870368&doi=10.24321%2F0019.5138.202028&partnerID=40&md5=2116ccf3058bbd263652b8a1f23e645a](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85096870368&doi=10.24321%2F0019.5138.202028&partnerID=40&md5=2116ccf3058bbd263652b8a1f23e645a)

161) DOCUMENT TYPE: Article

OPEN ACCESS: ALL OPEN ACCESS; HYBRID GOLD OPEN ACCESS

R., Dorsch, Roswitha, J.E., Ojeda, Javier E., M.A., Salgado, Miguel Angel, G.E., Monti, Gustavo Enrique, B., Collado, Bernardita, C., Tomckowiack, Camilo, C., Tejada, Carlos, A., Muller, Ananda, T., Eberhard, Theo, H.L.B.M., Klaasen, Henricus Leo Bernardus Maria

AUTHOR FULL NAMES: Dorsch, Roswitha (55922762400); Ojeda, Javier E.

(36696784400); Salgado, Miguel Angel (8642484900); Monti, Gustavo Enrique

(8977170000); Collado, Bernardita (57210113422); Tomckowiack, Camilo (57204803703);

Tejada, Carlos (57190441787); Muller, Ananda (57188627519); Eberhard, Theo

(57219601143); Klaasen, Henricus Leo Bernardus Maria (36934572600)

55922762400; 36696784400; 8642484900; 8977170000; 57210113422; 57204803703;

57190441787; 57188627519; 57219601143; 36934572600

Cats shedding pathogenic *Leptospira* spp.-An underestimated zoonotic risk?

(2020) *PLOS ONE*, 15 (10 October), art. no. e0239991

DOI: 10.1371/journal.pone.0239991

[https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85094102742&doi=10.1371%2Fjournal.pone.0239991&partnerID=40&md5=29b48adc0557eb4075b29b365a2441ca)

[85094102742&doi=10.1371%2Fjournal.pone.0239991&partnerID=40&md5=29b48adc0557eb4075b29b365a2441ca](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85094102742&doi=10.1371%2Fjournal.pone.0239991&partnerID=40&md5=29b48adc0557eb4075b29b365a2441ca)

162) DOCUMENT TYPE: Article

OPEN ACCESS: ALL OPEN ACCESS; GOLD OPEN ACCESS; GREEN FINAL OPEN ACCESS; GREEN OPEN ACCESS

D.S., de Oliveira, Daiana Santos, V.A., Querino, Vladimir Airam, Y.S., Lee, Yeonsoo Sara, G.M., da Cunha, Geraldo Marcelo, N.R.R., Nery, Nivison Ruy Rocha, L.W., Perelo, Louisa Wessels, J.C.R., Alva, Juan Carlos Rossi, A.I., Ko, Albert I., M.G., Reis, Mitermayer G., A., Casanovas-Massana, Arnau

AUTHOR FULL NAMES: de Oliveira, Daiana Santos (56706945700); Querino, Vladimir Airam (57198517099); Lee, Yeonsoo Sara (57218578432); da Cunha, Geraldo Marcelo (8595056000); Nery, Nivison Ruy Rocha (57086829100); Perelo, Louisa Wessels (35362230700); Alva, Juan Carlos Rossi (56723876100); Ko, Albert I. (7007018347); Reis, Mitermayer G. (35459915300); Casanovas-Massana, Arnau (35386067500) 56706945700; 57198517099; 57218578432; 8595056000; 57086829100; 35362230700; 56723876100; 7007018347; 35459915300; 35386067500

Relationship between physicochemical characteristics and pathogenic leptospira in Urban Slum Waters

(2020) Tropical Medicine and Infectious Disease, 5 (3), art. no. 5030146

DOI: 10.3390/TROPICALMED5030146

[https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85092327874&doi=10.3390%2FTROPICALMED5030146&partnerID=40&md5=8371539740528c9fb84360d76c2ea584)

[85092327874&doi=10.3390%2FTROPICALMED5030146&partnerID=40&md5=8371539740528c9fb84360d76c2ea584](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85092327874&doi=10.3390%2FTROPICALMED5030146&partnerID=40&md5=8371539740528c9fb84360d76c2ea584)

163) DOCUMENT TYPE: Article

OPEN ACCESS: ALL OPEN ACCESS; GOLD OPEN ACCESS; GREEN FINAL OPEN ACCESS; GREEN OPEN ACCESS

Y.S., Kamath, Yogish Subraya, A., Rizvi, Alisha, T., Ravikumar, T., S., Vishwanath, Shashidhar

AUTHOR FULL NAMES: Kamath, Yogish Subraya (55308957400); Rizvi, Alisha (57218616992); Ravikumar, T. (57218621954); Vishwanath, Shashidhar (35996058600) 55308957400; 57218616992; 57218621954; 35996058600

Leptospiral uveitis in coastal Karnataka: A case report

(2020) Indian Journal of Ophthalmology, 68 (9), pp. 1975 - 1976

DOI: 10.4103/ijo.IJO_267_20

[https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85089803844&doi=10.4103%2Fijo.IJO_267_20&partnerID=40&md5=f0290573557db6468a1c6ddf30e897d1)

[85089803844&doi=10.4103%2Fijo.IJO_267_20&partnerID=40&md5=f0290573557db6468a1c6ddf30e897d1](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85089803844&doi=10.4103%2Fijo.IJO_267_20&partnerID=40&md5=f0290573557db6468a1c6ddf30e897d1)

164) DOCUMENT TYPE: Article

OPEN ACCESS: ALL OPEN ACCESS; GOLD OPEN ACCESS; GREEN FINAL OPEN ACCESS; GREEN OPEN ACCESS

G.M., Rodamilans, Gustavo Macedo, M.S., Fonseca, Máisa Santos, L.N., Paz, Lucas Nogueira, C.C., Fernandez, Clara Couto, I.B., Biondi, Ilka Borges, R.M., Lira-Da-Silva, Rejâne Maria, R.J., Meyer, Roberto José, M.H., Hanzen Pinna, Melissa Hanzen, R.W., Portela, Ricardo Wagner

AUTHOR FULL NAMES: Rodamilans, Gustavo Macedo (57217067807); Fonseca, Máisa Santos (57212476415); Paz, Lucas Nogueira (57192557684); Fernandez, Clara Couto (57212684942); Biondi, Ilka Borges (14025412000); Lira-Da-Silva, Rejâne Maria (6507319221); Meyer, Roberto José (8581385400); Hanzen Pinna, Melissa Hanzen (37068063600); Portela, Ricardo Wagner (6701656359)

57217067807; 57212476415; 57192557684; 57212684942; 14025412000; 6507319221; 8581385400; 37068063600; 6701656359

Leptospira interrogans in wild Boa constrictor snakes from Northeast Brazil peri-urban rainforest fragments

(2020) Acta Tropica, 209, art. no. 105572

DOI: 10.1016/j.actatropica.2020.105572

[https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85086043540&doi=10.1016%2Fj.actatropica.2020.105572&partnerID=40&md5=b954ebed4a40cced9cce1fcb21b9600f)

[85086043540&doi=10.1016%2Fj.actatropica.2020.105572&partnerID=40&md5=b954ebed4a40cced9cce1fcb21b9600f](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85086043540&doi=10.1016%2Fj.actatropica.2020.105572&partnerID=40&md5=b954ebed4a40cced9cce1fcb21b9600f)

165) DOCUMENT TYPE: Article

OPEN ACCESS: ALL OPEN ACCESS; HYBRID GOLD OPEN ACCESS

S., Thiruvengadam, S., M., Sultana, Mazher

AUTHOR FULL NAMES: Thiruvengadam, S. (57197997767); Sultana, Mazher (57196005786)

57197997767; 57196005786

Adversities of monsoon rain in chennai (Tn) and isolation of pathogenic leptospire from the environment and screen the effect of sodium hypochlorite

(2020) Disaster Advances, 13 (8), pp. 64 - 71

[https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85089618107&partnerID=40&md5=eb7fd82322bebfe1f664a38edd19abbb)

[85089618107&partnerID=40&md5=eb7fd82322bebfe1f664a38edd19abbb](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85089618107&partnerID=40&md5=eb7fd82322bebfe1f664a38edd19abbb)

166) DOCUMENT TYPE: Article

P.W., Dhewantara, Pandji Wibawa, W., Zhang, Wenyi, A.A., Mamun, Abdullah Al, W., Yin, Wenwu, F., Ding, Fan, D., Guo, Danhuai, W., Hu, Wenbiao, R.J., Soares Magalhães, Ricardo J.

AUTHOR FULL NAMES: Dhewantara, Pandji Wibawa (57200842699); Zhang, Wenyi (57215374020); Mamun, Abdullah Al (55666602500); Yin, Wenwu (7202298949); Ding, Fan (57204065568); Guo, Danhuai (32667731300); Hu, Wenbiao (57218248248); Soares Magalhães, Ricardo J. (8863883300)

57200842699; 57215374020; 55666602500; 7202298949; 57204065568; 32667731300;

57218248248; 8863883300

Spatial distribution of leptospirosis incidence in the Upper Yangtze and Pearl River Basin, China: Tools to support intervention and elimination

(2020) Science of the Total Environment, 725, art. no. 138251

DOI: 10.1016/j.scitotenv.2020.138251

[https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85083011099&doi=10.1016%2Fj.scitotenv.2020.138251&partnerID=40&md5=999f7867934d54e53bb745ab1eba00)

[85083011099&doi=10.1016%2Fj.scitotenv.2020.138251&partnerID=40&md5=999f7867934d54e53bb745ab1eba00](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85083011099&doi=10.1016%2Fj.scitotenv.2020.138251&partnerID=40&md5=999f7867934d54e53bb745ab1eba00)

167) DOCUMENT TYPE: Article

A.A., Koval, Ariel Alejandro, B.F., Brihuega, Bibiana Felicitas, S., Grune Löffler, Sylvia, S., López, S., M., Saint Martin, Marcos, G.G., Lagioia, Gustavo Germán, J.R., Insaugarat, Juan Ramón

AUTHOR FULL NAMES: Koval, Ariel Alejandro (55317360600); Brihuega, Bibiana Felicitas (23003360500); Grune Löffler, Sylvia (55748438400); López, S. (57214452208); Saint Martin, Marcos (57214450840); Lagioia, Gustavo Germán (57214473568); Insaugarat, Juan Ramón (57193885108)
55317360600; 23003360500; 55748438400; 57214452208; 57214450840; 57214473568; 57193885108

First isolation of *Leptospira borgpetersenii* serovar Hardjo type Hardjo Bovis from a clinical case in cattle in Argentina Primer aislamiento de *Leptospira borgpetersenii* serovar Hardjo tipo Hardjo Bovis a partir de un caso clínico en Argentina (2020) Revista Argentina de Microbiología, 52 (3), pp. 198 - 201

DOI: 10.1016/j.ram.2019.10.002

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[85078760601&doi=10.1016%2Fj.ram.2019.10.002&partnerID=40&md5=b8983bff8b82273f0fe6a6aa90304f29](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85078760601&doi=10.1016%2Fj.ram.2019.10.002&partnerID=40&md5=b8983bff8b82273f0fe6a6aa90304f29)

168) DOCUMENT TYPE: Article

OPEN ACCESS: ALL OPEN ACCESS; GOLD OPEN ACCESS; GREEN FINAL OPEN ACCESS; GREEN OPEN ACCESS

T.J., Moreira-Marques, Torcato Jose, P.O., Nascimento, Paula Oliveira, A.T., Almeida, André Traça, V., Tosatto, Valentina

AUTHOR FULL NAMES: Moreira-Marques, Torcato Jose (57217171999); Nascimento, Paula Oliveira (57207862032); Almeida, André Traça (43761002500); Tosatto, Valentina (57188691435)

57217171999; 57207862032; 43761002500; 57188691435

Weil's disease in a young homeless man living in Lisbon (2020) BMJ Case Reports, 13 (6), art. no. 2019233543

DOI: 10.1136/bcr-2019-233543

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[85086602490&doi=10.1136%2Fbcr-2019-233543&partnerID=40&md5=37137962e7e4f293028403073358c0f8](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85086602490&doi=10.1136%2Fbcr-2019-233543&partnerID=40&md5=37137962e7e4f293028403073358c0f8)

169) DOCUMENT TYPE: Article

OPEN ACCESS: ALL OPEN ACCESS; GREEN FINAL OPEN ACCESS; GREEN OPEN ACCESS

O.I., Zakharova, Olga I., F.I., Korennoy, F. I., N.N., Toropova, Nadezhda N., O.A., Burova, Olga A., A.A., Blokhin, Andrey A.

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57217229441; 46461328200; 57217239016; 57275590400; 57211407925

Environmental risk of leptospirosis in animals: The case of the Republic of Sakha (Yakutia), Russian Federation
(2020) Pathogens, 9 (6), art. no. 504, pp. 1 - 18
DOI: 10.3390/pathogens9060504
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170) DOCUMENT TYPE: Article

OPEN ACCESS: ALL OPEN ACCESS; GOLD OPEN ACCESS; GREEN FINAL OPEN ACCESS; GREEN OPEN ACCESS

S., Rattanavong, Sayaphet, A., Dubot-Pérès, Audrey, M., Mayxay, Mayfong, M., Vongsouvath, Manivanh, S.J., Lee, Sue J., J., Cappelle, Julien, P.N., Newton, Paul N., D.M., Parker, Daniel M.
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55401700000; 25636861700; 6603556481; 15046069600; 35272455900; 24449355500; 57202763590; 57203492419

Spatial epidemiology of japanese encephalitis virus and other infections of the central nervous system infections in lao pdr (2003– 2011): A retrospective analysis
(2020) PLOS Neglected Tropical Diseases, 14 (5), art. no. e0008333, pp. 1 - 18
DOI: 10.1371/journal.pntd.0008333
<https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85086052515&doi=10.1371%2Fjournal.pntd.0008333&partnerID=40&md5=fb2b4f9501a2615a2be30110e35b9e66>

171) DOCUMENT TYPE: Article

OPEN ACCESS: ALL OPEN ACCESS; GOLD OPEN ACCESS; GREEN ACCEPTED OPEN ACCESS; GREEN FINAL OPEN ACCESS; GREEN OPEN ACCESS

S., Rajapakse, Senaka, P.N., Weeratunga, Praveen Nilendra, K., Balaji, Krishan, K.C., Ramchandani, Kyra Charmaine, U.S., de Silva, Udani Savbhagya, S.A., Ranasinghe, Shenali Avishka, D., Gunarathne, Dinesh, P.P.B., Wijerathne, Pasindu P.B., N., Fernando, Narmada, S.M., Handunnetti, Shiroma Mangalika
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6602985633; 55498370600; 57197984932; 57217039403; 57217039658; 57217039740; 57217038888; 57217038546; 56215009400; 6602770633
Seroprevalence of leptospirosis in an endemic mixed urban and semi-urban setting— a community-based study in the district of Colombo, Sri Lanka

(2020) PLOS Neglected Tropical Diseases, 14 (5), art. no. e0008309, pp. 1 - 19
DOI: 10.1371/journal.pntd.0008309
<https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85085904507&doi=10.1371%2Fjournal.pntd.0008309&partnerID=40&md5=6c3350e6f6a1f1ce6ce570188767b99a>

172) DOCUMENT TYPE: Article
OPEN ACCESS: ALL OPEN ACCESS; GOLD OPEN ACCESS; GREEN FINAL OPEN ACCESS; GREEN OPEN ACCESS

H., Zhang, Hui, C., Zhang, Cuicai, Y., Zhu, Yongzhang, K.M., Mehmood, Khalid M., J., Liu, Jinjing, S.P., McDonough, Sean P., Z., Tang, Zhaoxin, Y., Chang, Yungfu
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57188987145; 36083704200; 7406069313; 39561380000; 57205586355; 7004454383; 37056640800; 57102142600
Leptospirosis trends in China, 2007–2018: A retrospective observational study
(2020) Transboundary and Emerging Diseases, 67 (3), pp. 1119 - 1128
DOI: 10.1111/tbed.13437
<https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85076719554&doi=10.1111%2Ftbed.13437&partnerID=40&md5=d1858d57dfbfc06c70b45517c014fe1a>

173) DOCUMENT TYPE: Article

S.R., Jobin, S. R., J.W., Prakash, J. W.
AUTHOR FULL NAMES: Jobin, S. R. (56074426900); Prakash, J. W. (57209693365)
56074426900; 57209693365
Outbreak of leptospirosis in Kerala, India after floods: A survey
(2020) Plant Archives, 20 (1), pp. 2560 - 2562
<https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85086360033&partnerID=40&md5=e2e5c4994ef5f50aa03cf7ea02c5195c>

174) DOCUMENT TYPE: Article

F.S., Mohd-Taib, Farah Shafawati, S.N., Ishak, Siti Nabilah, M.A., Yusof, Muhammad Afif, N.N., Azhari, Nurul Natasya, A., Md-Lasim, Asmalia, S., Md-Nor, Shukor, S.A., Mohd Sah, Shahrul Anuar, V.K., Neela, Vasantha Kumari
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55249735600; 57201152279; 57201669412; 57203635024; 57205744064; 11141565000; 36678070400; 8554400700

Leptospirosis: An insight into community structure of small mammal's host in urban environment

(2020) *Tropical Biomedicine*, 37 (1), pp. 142 - 154

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[85090724806&partnerID=40&md5=e874455d63a97bd119b7b1478a8ac924](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85090724806&partnerID=40&md5=e874455d63a97bd119b7b1478a8ac924)

175) DOCUMENT TYPE: Article

C., Tsai, Chiata, J., Lin, Jiunnong, C., Lee, Chenhsiang, W., Sun, Wu, Y., Chang, Yichin, Y.H., Chen, Yen Hsu, C., Lai, Chunghsu

AUTHOR FULL NAMES: Tsai, Chiata (55503144200); Lin, Jiunnong (35237920200); Lee, Chenhsiang (35233755800); Sun, Wu (55220234500); Chang, Yichin (57208652315);

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55503144200; 35237920200; 35233755800; 55220234500; 57208652315; 7601434795;

8966931100

The epidemiology, characteristics and outbreaks of human leptospirosis and the association with animals in Taiwan, 2007–2014: A nationwide database study

(2020) *Zoonoses and Public Health*, 67 (2), pp. 156 - 166

DOI: 10.1111/zph.12667

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[85077911550&doi=10.1111%2Fzph.12667&partnerID=40&md5=1a193b1703da4770bbd8b148ad4677ff](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85077911550&doi=10.1111%2Fzph.12667&partnerID=40&md5=1a193b1703da4770bbd8b148ad4677ff)

176) DOCUMENT TYPE: Article

J.O., García-Méndez, Jorge Oscar, E.E., Cervera-Ceballos, Eduardo Emir, D., Atilano-López, Daniel, S., Arroyo-Escalante, Sara, D., Moncada-Barrón, David, M., Leyva-Leyva, Margarita, R., Hernández-Castro, Rigoberto, E.M., Carrillo-Casas, Erika Margarita

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Margarita (57213452392); Hernández-Castro, Rigoberto (56000771700); Carrillo-Casas,

Erika Margarita (24179032300)

55232377500; 9233165100; 57189030564; 36479837700; 7801384542; 57213452392;

56000771700; 24179032300

Leptospirosis in an asplenic patient -case report

(2020) *BMC Infectious Diseases*, 20 (1), art. no. 186

DOI: 10.1186/s12879-020-4869-3

[https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85080873254&doi=10.1186%2Fs12879-020-4869-3&partnerID=40&md5=2499a5273f82056ec68983f1fb85efc8)

[85080873254&doi=10.1186%2Fs12879-020-4869-](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85080873254&doi=10.1186%2Fs12879-020-4869-3&partnerID=40&md5=2499a5273f82056ec68983f1fb85efc8)

[3&partnerID=40&md5=2499a5273f82056ec68983f1fb85efc8](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85080873254&doi=10.1186%2Fs12879-020-4869-3&partnerID=40&md5=2499a5273f82056ec68983f1fb85efc8)

177) DOCUMENT TYPE: Article

OPEN ACCESS: ALL OPEN ACCESS; GOLD OPEN ACCESS; GREEN FINAL OPEN ACCESS; GREEN OPEN ACCESS

N.N.A., Baki, Nurul Najian Aminuddin, M.R., Mohd Ali, Mohammad Ridhuan, E.N.S.A., Rahman, Engku Nur Syafirah Abd, N.Y., Yusof, Nik Yuszrin, N., Ismail, Nabilah, C., Yean Yean, Chan
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57218170221; 57196220663; 59810510600; 57202651043; 57192409521; 7403676352
Detection and distribution of putative pathogenicity-associated genes among serologically important *Leptospira* strains and post-flood environmental isolates in Malaysia
(2020) Malaysian Journal of Microbiology, 16 (1), pp. 17 - 28
DOI: 10.21161/mjm.180208
<https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85088115731&doi=10.21161%2Fmjm.180208&partnerID=40&md5=a56b212b58732dbc03f73e33ff539631>

178) DOCUMENT TYPE: Article

OPEN ACCESS: ALL OPEN ACCESS; GOLD OPEN ACCESS

A.L., Katelaris, Anthea L., K.M., Glasgow, Keira M., K., Lawrence, Kerryn, P.W., Corben, Paul W., A., Zheng, Anthony, S., Sumithra, Suhasini, J.A., Turahui, John A., J., Terry, Janet, D.J., van den Berg, Debra J., D., Hennessy, Daneeta
AUTHOR FULL NAMES: Katelaris, Anthea L. (49561460400); Glasgow, Keira M. (57207757267); Lawrence, Kerryn (58380295100); Corben, Paul W. (22937168400); Zheng, Anthony (57207876216); Sumithra, Suhasini (57211460693); Turahui, John A. (24468980800); Terry, Janet (7103365549); van den Berg, Debra J. (57191831912); Hennessy, Daneeta (57220447356)
49561460400; 57207757267; 58380295100; 22937168400; 57207876216; 57211460693; 24468980800; 7103365549; 57191831912; 57220447356
Investigation and response to an outbreak of leptospirosis among raspberry workers in Australia, 2018
(2020) Zoonoses and Public Health, 67 (1), pp. 35 - 43
DOI: 10.1111/zph.12652
<https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85074051075&doi=10.1111%2Fzph.12652&partnerID=40&md5=b4bfcf9f1b0bc87a144a154a4b6da4ec>

179) DOCUMENT TYPE: Article

OPEN ACCESS: ALL OPEN ACCESS; GREEN FINAL OPEN ACCESS; GREEN OPEN ACCESS

A.G., Jüttemann, Andreas Gerd
AUTHOR FULL NAMES: Jüttemann, Andreas Gerd (56096828300)
56096828300
The history of Silesian slime fever Die Geschichte des Schlesischen Schlammfiebers
(2020) Arbeitsmedizin Sozialmedizin Umweltmedizin, 2020 (12), pp. 776 - 781

DOI: 10.17147/ASU-2012-8789

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180) DOCUMENT TYPE: Article

OPEN ACCESS: ALL OPEN ACCESS; GOLD OPEN ACCESS

O.Y., Galatiuk, Oleksandr Y., A., Kalnaus, A., T.A., Romanishina, Tatiana A., S., Pavlenko, S.

AUTHOR FULL NAMES: Galatiuk, Oleksandr Y. (59617157400); Kalnaus, A. (57314646300); Romanishina, Tatiana A. (57201912132); Pavlenko, S. (57315683100) 59617157400; 57314646300; 57201912132; 57315683100

Features of joint flow of leptospirosis and rhinopneumonia of horses in equestrian conditions ОСОБЛИВОСТІ СУМІСНОГО ПЕРЕБІГУ ЛЕПТОСПИРОЗУ ТА РИНОПНЕВМОНІЇ КОНЕЙ В УМОВАХ КІННОГО ЗАВОДУ

(2020) Scientific Horizons, (4), pp. 82 - 88

DOI: 10.33249/2663-2144-2020-89-4-82-88

<https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85118100318&doi=10.33249%2F2663-2144-2020-89-4-82-88&partnerID=40&md5=ac565d1d4da0b8aa40d055cef84ec3fa>

181) DOCUMENT TYPE: Article

OPEN ACCESS: ALL OPEN ACCESS; GOLD OPEN ACCESS

A.E.P., Silva, Ana Elisa Pereira, G.M.d.S., Conceição, Gleice Margarete de Souza, F., Chiaravalloti-Neto, Francisco

AUTHOR FULL NAMES: Silva, Ana Elisa Pereira (57188571715); Conceição, Gleice Margarete de Souza (35450464300); Chiaravalloti-Neto, Francisco (6603270926) 57188571715; 35450464300; 6603270926

Spatial analysis and factors associated with leptospirosis in Santa Catarina, Brazil, 2001-2015

(2020) Revista da Sociedade Brasileira de Medicina Tropical, 53, pp. e20200466

DOI: 10.1590/0037-8682-0466-2020

<https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85098606626&doi=10.1590%2F0037-8682-0466-2020&partnerID=40&md5=90eddb7645772d272ef04a807d6bcf3d>

182) DOCUMENT TYPE: Article

OPEN ACCESS: ALL OPEN ACCESS; GOLD OPEN ACCESS; GREEN FINAL OPEN ACCESS; GREEN OPEN ACCESS

A.E.P., Silva, Ana Elisa Pereira, F.C., Neto, Francisco Chiaravalloti, G.M.d.S., Conceição, Gleice Margarete de Souza

AUTHOR FULL NAMES: Silva, Ana Elisa Pereira (57188571715); Neto, Francisco Chiaravalloti (57214172040); Conceição, Gleice Margarete de Souza (35450464300) 57188571715; 57214172040; 35450464300

Leptospirosis and its spatial and temporal relations with natural disasters in six municipalities of Santa Catarina State, Brazil from 2000 to 2016
(2020) *Geospatial Health*, 15 (2), art. no. 903, pp. 225 - 235
DOI: 10.4081/gh.2020.903
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183) DOCUMENT TYPE: Article
OPEN ACCESS: ALL OPEN ACCESS; GOLD OPEN ACCESS; GREEN FINAL OPEN ACCESS; GREEN OPEN ACCESS

A., Luenam, Amornrat, N., Puttanapong, Nattapong
AUTHOR FULL NAMES: Luenam, Amornrat (57201418598); Puttanapong, Nattapong (57074837000)
57201418598; 57074837000
Modelling and analyzing spatial clusters of leptospirosis based on satellite-generated measurements of environmental factors in Thailand during 2013-2015
(2020) *Geospatial Health*, 15 (2), art. no. 856, pp. 217 - 224
DOI: 10.4081/gh.2020.856
<https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85097415189&doi=10.4081%2Fgh.2020.856&partnerID=40&md5=0688bae64c65c757f005da6ea1102255>

184) DOCUMENT TYPE: Article
OPEN ACCESS: ALL OPEN ACCESS; GOLD OPEN ACCESS

I.K.F., de Sousa, Isadora Karolina Freitas, R.L.C., Silva, Rebeca Larissa Castro, R.D.S., Sousa, Rejane Dos Santos, C.E.M., Vieira, Cláudia Elisa Martins, S.N., de Melo, Sérgio Novais, G.P., Quevedo, Géorgea Portella, A.E.V., Laer, Ana Eucares Von, L.T., Lovato, Luciane Teresinha, A.A., Tonin, A. A.
AUTHOR FULL NAMES: de Sousa, Isadora Karolina Freitas (55889149300); Silva, Rebeca Larissa Castro (57220208512); Sousa, Rejane Dos Santos (59113896900); Vieira, Cláudia Elisa Martins (57220211366); de Melo, Sérgio Novais (55861120700); Quevedo, Géorgea Portella (57220209598); Laer, Ana Eucares Von (57220204568); Lovato, Luciane Teresinha (6701832650); Tonin, A. A. (57208158868)
55889149300; 57220208512; 59113896900; 57220211366; 55861120700; 57220209598; 57220204568; 6701832650; 57208158868
Frequency of leptospirosis in horses in manaus and metropolitan region in Amazonas State, Brazil
Frequência de leptospirose em equinos de manaus e região metropolitana no Estado do Amazonas, Brasil
(2020) *Brazilian Journal of Veterinary Research and Animal Science*, 57 (4), art. no. e172607, pp. 1 - 7
DOI: 10.11606/issn.1678-4456.bjvras.2020.172607
<https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85097296101&doi=10.11606%2Fissn.1678-4456.bjvras.2020.172607&partnerID=40&md5=87aca6a8cb8b522f64be0139daaab95a>

185) DOCUMENT TYPE: Article
OPEN ACCESS: ALL OPEN ACCESS; GOLD OPEN ACCESS

R.A., Cerveira, Rodrigo Arcoverde, L.O., Ferreira, Luan Oliveira, E.F., de Oliveira, Edwiges Fátima, H.K.D.S., Felipe, Hanna Katharine Dos Santos, M.C.A., Almeida, Marcelli Carolini Alves, S.S.C., Lima, Sandra Souza C., K.T.S., Ribeiro, Karla Tereza Silva

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Spatio-temporal analysis of leptospirosis in eastern amazon, state of Pará, Brazil
Análise espaço-temporal da leptospirose na amazônia oriental, estado do Pará, Brasil
(2020) Revista Brasileira de Epidemiologia, 23, art. no. E200041, pp. 1 - 11

DOI: 10.1590/1980-549720200041

[https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85085961643&doi=10.1590%2F1980-](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85085961643&doi=10.1590%2F1980-549720200041&partnerID=40&md5=1b1dda49c437f11d49dd20d26cfd692)

[549720200041&partnerID=40&md5=1b1dda49c437f11d49dd20d26cfd692](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85085961643&doi=10.1590%2F1980-549720200041&partnerID=40&md5=1b1dda49c437f11d49dd20d26cfd692)

186) DOCUMENT TYPE: Article
OPEN ACCESS: ALL OPEN ACCESS; GOLD OPEN ACCESS; GREEN FINAL OPEN ACCESS; GREEN OPEN ACCESS

F.A., Arogundade, Fatiu Abiola, B.A., Omotoso, Bolanle Aderonke, A.A., Sanusi, Abubarkar Abefe, R.A., Balogun, Rasheed Abiodun

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6602847928; 56155729100; 6601954456; 6701577599

Burden and etiopathogenesis of acute kidney injury in the tropics

(2020) Clinical Nephrology, 93 (1), pp. S8 - S16

DOI: 10.5414/CNP92S102

[https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85084784165&doi=10.5414%2FCNP92S102&partnerID=40&md5=8e55fb7d4ee310821ca5310b6b2f1196)

[85084784165&doi=10.5414%2FCNP92S102&partnerID=40&md5=8e55fb7d4ee310821ca5310b6b2f1196](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85084784165&doi=10.5414%2FCNP92S102&partnerID=40&md5=8e55fb7d4ee310821ca5310b6b2f1196)

187) DOCUMENT TYPE: Article

E., Bierque, Emilie, R., Thibeaux, Roman, D., Girault, Dominique, M.E., Soupé-Gilbert, Marie Estelle, C., Goarant, Cyrille

AUTHOR FULL NAMES: Bierque, Emilie (57193510347); Thibeaux, Roman (41662312500); Girault, Dominique (57193227377); Soupé-Gilbert, Marie Estelle (55777279000); Goarant, Cyrille (6603498952)

57193510347; 41662312500; 57193227377; 55777279000; 6603498952

A systematic review of *Leptospira* in water and soil environments

(2020) PLOS ONE, 15 (1), art. no. e0227055

DOI: 10.1371/journal.pone.0227055

[https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85078477816&doi=10.1371%2Fjournal.pone.0227055&partnerID=40&md5=91740afa6f94bbca088fb2711a4ff2ff)

[85078477816&doi=10.1371%2Fjournal.pone.0227055&partnerID=40&md5=91740afa6f94bbca088fb2711a4ff2ff](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85078477816&doi=10.1371%2Fjournal.pone.0227055&partnerID=40&md5=91740afa6f94bbca088fb2711a4ff2ff)

188) DOCUMENT TYPE: Article

OPEN ACCESS: ALL OPEN ACCESS; GOLD OPEN ACCESS; GREEN FINAL OPEN ACCESS; GREEN OPEN ACCESS

K.P., Hacker, Kathryn P., G.A.D., Sacramento, Gielson Almeida Do, J.S., Cruz, Jaqueline Silva, D.S., de Oliveira, Daiana Santos, N.R.R., Nery, Nivison Ruy Rocha, J.C., Lindow, Janet C., M.G.S., Carvalho, Mayara G.S., J.E., Hagan, José Edward, P.J., Diggle, Peter J., M.E., Begon, Michael E.

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Influence of rainfall on leptospira infection and disease in a tropical urban setting, Brazil

(2020) Emerging Infectious Diseases, 26 (2), pp. 311 - 314

DOI: 10.3201/eid2602.190102

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[85078185456&doi=10.3201%2Feid2602.190102&partnerID=40&md5=3ae0795ca99682cd469b7f5ef7b2f1c4](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85078185456&doi=10.3201%2Feid2602.190102&partnerID=40&md5=3ae0795ca99682cd469b7f5ef7b2f1c4)

189) DOCUMENT TYPE: Article

OPEN ACCESS: ALL OPEN ACCESS; GOLD OPEN ACCESS; GREEN FINAL OPEN ACCESS; GREEN OPEN ACCESS

K., Cucchi, Karina, R., Liu, Runyou, P.A., Collender, Philip A., Q., Cheng, Qu, C., Li, Charles, C.M., Hoover, Christopher M., H.H., Chang, Howard H., S., Liang, Song, C., Yang, Changhong, J.V., Remais, Justin V.

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57196421695; 57215319025; 56938851400; 57209881071; 57209886823; 39561136400; 36771346500; 55506203600; 57310464500; 6504709208

Hydroclimatic drivers of highly seasonal leptospirosis incidence suggest prominent soil reservoir of pathogenic *Leptospira* spp. In rural western China

(2019) PLOS Neglected Tropical Diseases, 13 (12), art. no. e0007968

DOI: 10.1371/JOURNAL.PNTD.0007968

<https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85077761582&doi=10.1371%2FJOURNAL.PNTD.0007968&partnerID=40&md5=21498a895fe03ab6e225530044ea6989>

85077761582&doi=10.1371%2FJOURNAL.PNTD.0007968&partnerID=40&md5=21498a895fe03ab6e225530044ea6989

190) DOCUMENT TYPE: Article

OPEN ACCESS: ALL OPEN ACCESS; GOLD OPEN ACCESS; GREEN FINAL OPEN ACCESS; GREEN OPEN ACCESS

S., Corvaro, Sara

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Water efficiency and economic assessment of domestic rainwater harvesting systems in buildings with one-to three-floor elevations

(2019) *Water Supply*, 19 (8), pp. 2422 - 2434

DOI: 10.2166/ws.2019.124

<https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85076619554&doi=10.2166%2Fws.2019.124&partnerID=40&md5=15356c76b513e844cac0a3c0a833cf47>

85076619554&doi=10.2166%2Fws.2019.124&partnerID=40&md5=15356c76b513e844cac0a3c0a833cf47

191) DOCUMENT TYPE: Article

OPEN ACCESS: ALL OPEN ACCESS; BRONZE OPEN ACCESS

L.H., Nau, Lisa H., D., Emirhar, Duygu, A., Obiegala, Anna, M., Mylius, Maren, M., Runge, Martin, J., Jacob, Jens, N.S., Bier, Nadja Seyhan, K., Nöckler, Karsten, C., Imholt, Christian, D.A., Below, Diana Alexandra

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57211909799; 57211907410; 56601363300; 56076155800; 17535119000; 56962770000;

55756847100; 55941959000; 36627180300; 57211909305

Leptospirosis in Germany: current knowledge on pathogen species, reservoir hosts,

and disease in humans and animals Leptospirose in Deutschland: Aktuelle

Erkenntnisse zu Erregerspezies, Reservoirwirten und Erkrankungen bei Mensch und Tier

(2019) *Bundesgesundheitsblatt - Gesundheitsforschung - Gesundheitsschutz*, 62 (12),

pp. 1510 - 1521

DOI: 10.1007/s00103-019-03051-4

<https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85075309561&doi=10.1007%2Fs00103-019-03051-4&partnerID=40&md5=aeb669236e6170ac7fb850927bda472c>

85075309561&doi=10.1007%2Fs00103-019-03051-

4&partnerID=40&md5=aeb669236e6170ac7fb850927bda472c

192) DOCUMENT TYPE: Article

OPEN ACCESS: ALL OPEN ACCESS; HYBRID GOLD OPEN ACCESS

Y., Nikaido, Yasuhiko, M., Ogawa, Midori, K., Fukuda, Kazumasa, M., Yokoyama, Mitsuru, T., Kanemaru, Takaaki, T., Nakayama, Toshiyuki, M., Saito, Mitsumasa
AUTHOR FULL NAMES: Nikaido, Yasuhiko (57581530000); Ogawa, Midori (19335437300); Fukuda, Kazumasa (35268388600); Yokoyama, Mitsuru (57200183986); Kanemaru, Takaaki (6701473302); Nakayama, Toshiyuki (56437164600); Saito, Mitsumasa (7404972747)
57581530000; 19335437300; 35268388600; 57200183986; 6701473302; 56437164600; 7404972747

Transbronchial invasion and proliferation of leptospira interrogans in lung without inflammatory cell infiltration in a hamster model

(2019) Infection and Immunity, 87 (12), art. no. e00727-19

DOI: 10.1128/IAI.00727-19

[https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85075221107&doi=10.1128%2FIAI.00727-19&partnerID=40&md5=720d381ded9c9b24af767a6ceddea475)

[85075221107&doi=10.1128%2FIAI.00727-](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85075221107&doi=10.1128%2FIAI.00727-19&partnerID=40&md5=720d381ded9c9b24af767a6ceddea475)

[19&partnerID=40&md5=720d381ded9c9b24af767a6ceddea475](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85075221107&doi=10.1128%2FIAI.00727-19&partnerID=40&md5=720d381ded9c9b24af767a6ceddea475)

193) DOCUMENT TYPE: Article

OPEN ACCESS: ALL OPEN ACCESS; BRONZE OPEN ACCESS; GREEN FINAL OPEN ACCESS; GREEN OPEN ACCESS

M.S., López, María Soledad, G.V., Müller, Gabriela Viviana, M.A., Lovino, Miguel Angel, A.A.A., Gómez, Andrea A. Alejandra, W.F., Sione, Walter Fabián, L., Aragonés Pomares, Luis

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7404124163; 8674035000; 56450921600; 55429425400; 24071886600; 57190686111

Spatio-temporal analysis of leptospirosis incidence and its relationship with hydroclimatic indicators in northeastern Argentina

(2019) Science of the Total Environment, 694, art. no. 133651

DOI: 10.1016/j.scitotenv.2019.133651

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[85070366641&doi=10.1016%2Fj.scitotenv.2019.133651&partnerID=40&md5=0e16a7a46e318f47e1e7dabcee80cf07](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85070366641&doi=10.1016%2Fj.scitotenv.2019.133651&partnerID=40&md5=0e16a7a46e318f47e1e7dabcee80cf07)

194) DOCUMENT TYPE: Article

Y., Sato, Yukuto, M., Mizuyama, Masaru, M., Sato, Megumi, T., Minamoto, Toshifumi, R., Kimura, Ryouyusuke, C., Toma, Claudia

AUTHOR FULL NAMES: Sato, Yukuto (23393502000); Mizuyama, Masaru (55519698200); Sato, Megumi (24074837000); Minamoto, Toshifumi (25639837900); Kimura, Ryouyusuke (7201883169); Toma, Claudia (57210368337)

23393502000; 55519698200; 24074837000; 25639837900; 7201883169; 57210368337

Environmental DNA metabarcoding to detect pathogenic Leptospira and associated organisms in leptospirosis-endemic areas of Japan

(2019) Scientific Reports, 9 (1), art. no. 6575

DOI: 10.1038/s41598-019-42978-1

<https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85064903525&doi=10.1038%2Fs41598-019-42978-1&partnerID=40&md5=ed20b7d0f4c880e66bd29e54c3c3536e>

195) DOCUMENT TYPE: Article

OPEN ACCESS: ALL OPEN ACCESS; GOLD OPEN ACCESS; GREEN FINAL OPEN ACCESS; GREEN OPEN ACCESS

A.M., Smith, Amanda M., A.G., Arruda, Andréia G., M.D., Evason, Michelle D., J.S., Weese, Jeffrey Scott, T.E., Wittum, Thomas E., D.A., Szlosek, Donald A., J.W., Stull, Jason W.

AUTHOR FULL NAMES: Smith, Amanda M. (57211802171); Arruda, Andréia G. (56543006000); Evason, Michelle D. (7801537524); Weese, Jeffrey Scott (56702153300); Wittum, Thomas E. (7004009529); Szlosek, Donald A. (57115470000); Stull, Jason W. (14036670000)

57211802171; 56543006000; 7801537524; 56702153300; 7004009529; 57115470000; 14036670000

A cross-sectional study of environmental, dog, and human-related risk factors for positive canine leptospirosis PCR test results in the United States, 2009 to 2016 (2019) BMC Veterinary Research, 15 (1), art. no. 412

DOI: 10.1186/s12917-019-2148-6

<https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85075038149&doi=10.1186%2Fs12917-019-2148-6&partnerID=40&md5=2483fed306d7db9c185b60edfc9c66f2>

196) DOCUMENT TYPE: Article

OPEN ACCESS: ALL OPEN ACCESS; GOLD OPEN ACCESS; GREEN FINAL OPEN ACCESS; GREEN OPEN ACCESS

A., Mohammadinia, Ali, B., Saeidian, Bahram, B.K., Pradhan, Biswajeet K., Z., Ghaemi, Zeinab

AUTHOR FULL NAMES: Mohammadinia, Ali (57211802351); Saeidian, Bahram (57060546300); Pradhan, Biswajeet K. (12753037900); Ghaemi, Zeinab (56938769800) 57211802351; 57060546300; 12753037900; 56938769800

Prediction mapping of human leptospirosis using ANN, GWR, SVM and GLM approaches

(2019) BMC Infectious Diseases, 19 (1), art. no. 971

DOI: 10.1186/s12879-019-4580-4

<https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85075042535&doi=10.1186%2Fs12879-019-4580-4&partnerID=40&md5=cfb055248cb3fa9f4a1d1aac3dba99f9>

197) DOCUMENT TYPE: Article

OPEN ACCESS: ALL OPEN ACCESS; GOLD OPEN ACCESS; GREEN FINAL OPEN ACCESS; GREEN OPEN ACCESS

G., Houemenou, Gualbert, P., Gauthier, Philippe, J.R., Etougbétché, Jonas Raoul, S.A., Badou, Sylvestre Adjakou, H.J., Dossou, Henri Joel, D., Agossou, David, M., Picardeau, Mathieu, G., Dobigny, Gauthier

AUTHOR FULL NAMES: Houemenou, Gualbert (56470737500); Gauthier, Philippe (35821506800); Etougbétché, Jonas Raoul (57210970484); Badou, Sylvestre Adjakou (57211592777); Dossou, Henri Joel (57210969875); Agossou, David (58151697100); Picardeau, Mathieu (6701694004); Dobigny, Gauthier (6701314349) 56470737500; 35821506800; 57210970484; 57211592777; 57210969875; 58151697100; 6701694004; 6701314349

Pathogenic *Leptospira* in Commensal Small Mammals from the Extensively Urbanized Coastal Benin

(2019) *Urban Science*, 3 (3), art. no. 99

DOI: 10.3390/urbansci3030099

[https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85077543053&doi=10.3390%2Furbansci3030099&partnerID=40&md5=daed44539dac683c5a0ebaa96acf6f4e)

[85077543053&doi=10.3390%2Furbansci3030099&partnerID=40&md5=daed44539dac683c5a0ebaa96acf6f4e](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85077543053&doi=10.3390%2Furbansci3030099&partnerID=40&md5=daed44539dac683c5a0ebaa96acf6f4e)

198) DOCUMENT TYPE: Article

OPEN ACCESS: ALL OPEN ACCESS; GOLD OPEN ACCESS; GREEN FINAL OPEN ACCESS; GREEN OPEN ACCESS

M.H., Schønning, Marie Hellung, M.D., Phelps, Matthew David, J.N., Warnasekara, Janith Niwanthaka, S.B., Agampodi, Suneth Buddhika, P., Furu, Peter

AUTHOR FULL NAMES: Schønning, Marie Hellung (57211639581); Phelps, Matthew David (57217185835); Warnasekara, Janith Niwanthaka (57205683854); Agampodi, Suneth Buddhika (23017863100); Furu, Peter (6603611753)

57211639581; 57217185835; 57205683854; 23017863100; 6603611753

A Case–Control Study of Environmental and Occupational Risks of Leptospirosis in Sri Lanka

(2019) *EcoHealth*, 16 (3), pp. 534 - 543

DOI: 10.1007/s10393-019-01448-w

[https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85074712390&doi=10.1007%2Fs10393-019-01448-w&partnerID=40&md5=5c13bfaa27369256fb675a945deb63f8)

[85074712390&doi=10.1007%2Fs10393-019-01448-w&partnerID=40&md5=5c13bfaa27369256fb675a945deb63f8](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85074712390&doi=10.1007%2Fs10393-019-01448-w&partnerID=40&md5=5c13bfaa27369256fb675a945deb63f8)

199) DOCUMENT TYPE: Article

S., Chiu, Shihhui, M., Pan, Mingjeng

AUTHOR FULL NAMES: Chiu, Shihhui (37112007000); Pan, Mingjeng (7202544910) 37112007000; 7202544910

Detection and Treatment of Leptospirosis Kidney Disease

(2019) *Translational Research in Biomedicine*, 7, pp. 37 - 46

DOI: 10.1159/000500381

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[85071913514&doi=10.1159%2F000500381&partnerID=40&md5=ccd7bc6cd27d14065ebc8b50346f1eda](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85071913514&doi=10.1159%2F000500381&partnerID=40&md5=ccd7bc6cd27d14065ebc8b50346f1eda)

200) DOCUMENT TYPE: Article

G., Ding, Guoyong, X., Li, Xiaomei, X., Li, Xuewen, B., Zhang, Baofang, B., Jiang, Baofa, D., Li, Dong, W., Xing, Weijia, Q., Liu, Qiyong, X., Liu, Xuena, H., Hou, Haifeng
AUTHOR FULL NAMES: Ding, Guoyong (55760272200); Li, Xiaomei (57201302579); Li, Xuewen (54890140500); Zhang, Baofang (57209804922); Jiang, Baofa (8607835500); Li, Dong (57221871736); Xing, Weijia (36103493700); Liu, Qiyong (55616174300); Liu, Xuena (57040301800); Hou, Haifeng (57204846912)

55760272200; 57201302579; 54890140500; 57209804922; 8607835500; 57221871736; 36103493700; 55616174300; 57040301800; 57204846912

A time-trend ecological study for identifying flood-sensitive infectious diseases in Guangxi, China from 2005 to 2012

(2019) Environmental Research, 176, art. no. 108577

DOI: 10.1016/j.envres.2019.108577

[https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85068750627&doi=10.1016%2Fj.envres.2019.108577&partnerID=40&md5=eb5ca98d636798c3415ca886115e0ba2)

[85068750627&doi=10.1016%2Fj.envres.2019.108577&partnerID=40&md5=eb5ca98d636798c3415ca886115e0ba2](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85068750627&doi=10.1016%2Fj.envres.2019.108577&partnerID=40&md5=eb5ca98d636798c3415ca886115e0ba2)

201) DOCUMENT TYPE: Article

OPEN ACCESS: ALL OPEN ACCESS; GREEN FINAL OPEN ACCESS; GREEN OPEN ACCESS

P.W., Dhewantara, Pandji Wibawa, W., Hu, Wenbiao, W., Zhang, Wenyi, W., Yin, Wenwu, F., Ding, Fan, A.A., Mamun, Abdullah Al, R.J., Soares Magalhães, Ricardo J.
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57200842699; 57218248248; 57215374020; 7202298949; 57204065568; 55666602500; 8863883300

Climate variability, satellite-derived physical environmental data and human leptospirosis: A retrospective ecological study in China

(2019) Environmental Research, 176, art. no. 108523

DOI: 10.1016/j.envres.2019.06.004

[https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85067202152&doi=10.1016%2Fj.envres.2019.06.004&partnerID=40&md5=7e659e3b4080e20b16a9e94a0e1c4f66)

[85067202152&doi=10.1016%2Fj.envres.2019.06.004&partnerID=40&md5=7e659e3b4080e20b16a9e94a0e1c4f66](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85067202152&doi=10.1016%2Fj.envres.2019.06.004&partnerID=40&md5=7e659e3b4080e20b16a9e94a0e1c4f66)

202) DOCUMENT TYPE: Article

J., Viroj, Jaruwat, C., Lajaunie, Claire, J., Claude, Julien, S., Morand, Serge
AUTHOR FULL NAMES: Viroj, Jaruwat (57225210958); Lajaunie, Claire (56523046200); Claude, Julien (57214204474); Morand, Serge (7006833126)

57225210958; 56523046200; 57214204474; 7006833126

Knowledge and practices of leptospirosis patients, their neighbors, village health volunteers and community leaders regarding leptospirosis prevention and control in Maha Sarakham province, Thailand

(2019) Southeast Asian Journal of Tropical Medicine and Public Health, 50 (4), pp. 760 - 769

<https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85109522531&partnerID=40&md5=b728f59bfc1eae4bfe4dd60836fad701>

203) DOCUMENT TYPE: Article

S.W., Ng, Shing Wei, G.T., Selvarajah, Gayathri Thevi, S., Khairani-Bejo, Siti, R.B., Safii, Razitasham Bt, S.M., Saliluddin, Suhainizam M., A.R.M., Gobil, Abdul Rahman Mohamad, S., Amin-Nordin, S.

AUTHOR FULL NAMES: Ng, Shing Wei (57194048691); Selvarajah, Gayathri Thevi (26436227500); Khairani-Bejo, Siti (15047903000); Safii, Razitasham Bt (57190047234); Saliluddin, Suhainizam M. (57188849484); Gobil, Abdul Rahman Mohamad (56453559700); Amin-Nordin, S. (53464338500)
57194048691; 26436227500; 15047903000; 57190047234; 57188849484; 56453559700; 53464338500

Knowledge, attitudes and practices on leptospirosis prevention among local communities in Jempol district, Negeri Sembilan, Malaysia

(2019) Southeast Asian Journal of Tropical Medicine and Public Health, 50 (3), pp. 554 - 565

<https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85068924653&partnerID=40&md5=8132ca155eeab3b02c1c27e83beeb19f>

204) DOCUMENT TYPE: Article

C.M., Naing, Cho Min, S.A., Reid, Simon Andrew, S.N., Aye, Saint Nway, H., Htet, Htet, S.P., Ambu, Stephen Periathamby

AUTHOR FULL NAMES: Naing, Cho Min (35724580300); Reid, Simon Andrew (7201777637); Aye, Saint Nway (57209072887); Htet, Htet (57190809168); Ambu, Stephen Periathamby (19633408300)
35724580300; 7201777637; 57209072887; 57190809168; 19633408300

Risk factors for human leptospirosis following flooding: A meta-analysis of observational studies

(2019) PLOS ONE, 14 (5), art. no. e0217643

DOI: 10.1371/journal.pone.0217643

<https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85066451320&doi=10.1371%2Fjournal.pone.0217643&partnerID=40&md5=aec08f7f4b9d8c969d55a867e2343416>

205) DOCUMENT TYPE: Article

OPEN ACCESS: ALL OPEN ACCESS; GOLD OPEN ACCESS; GREEN ACCEPTED OPEN ACCESS; GREEN FINAL OPEN ACCESS; GREEN OPEN ACCESS

W.E., Péres, Wolmir Ercides, A., Russo, A., B., Nunes, Baltazar

AUTHOR FULL NAMES: Péres, Wolmir Ercides (57209025486); Russo, A. (55215472500); Nunes, Baltazar (9133723200)
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The association between hydro-meteorological events and leptospirosis hospitalizations in Santa Catarina, Brazil

(2019) *Water (Switzerland)*, 11 (5), art. no. 1052

DOI: 10.3390/w11051052

[https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85066300599&doi=10.3390%2Fw11051052&partnerID=40&md5=9de260c1f53f4dcf766224d5312b0f90)

[85066300599&doi=10.3390%2Fw11051052&partnerID=40&md5=9de260c1f53f4dcf766224d5312b0f90](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85066300599&doi=10.3390%2Fw11051052&partnerID=40&md5=9de260c1f53f4dcf766224d5312b0f90)

206) DOCUMENT TYPE: Article

OPEN ACCESS: ALL OPEN ACCESS; GOLD OPEN ACCESS

M., Pellizzaro, Maysa, C.M., Martins, Camila Marinelli, A.C., Yamakawa, Ana Carolina, D., DaCunha Ferraz, Diogo, V.M., Morikawa, Vivien Midori, F., Ferreira, Fernando,

A.P., dos Santos, Andrea P., A.W., Biondo, Alexander Welker, H., Langoni, Hélio

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(35508353100); dos Santos, Andrea P. (24401080800); Biondo, Alexander Welker

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56582138000; 55314452300; 57208862975; 57208862134; 55201243200; 35508353100;

24401080800; 56008856900; 6603491394

Molecular detection of *Leptospira* spp. In rats as early spatial predictor for human disease in an endemic urban area

(2019) *PLOS ONE*, 14 (5), art. no. e0216830

DOI: 10.1371/journal.pone.0216830

[https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85065998614&doi=10.1371%2Fjournal.pone.0216830&partnerID=40&md5=66745faedc37dc08da04438476769138)

[85065998614&doi=10.1371%2Fjournal.pone.0216830&partnerID=40&md5=66745faedc37dc08da04438476769138](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85065998614&doi=10.1371%2Fjournal.pone.0216830&partnerID=40&md5=66745faedc37dc08da04438476769138)

207) DOCUMENT TYPE: Article

OPEN ACCESS: ALL OPEN ACCESS; GOLD OPEN ACCESS; GREEN ACCEPTED

OPEN ACCESS; GREEN FINAL OPEN ACCESS; GREEN OPEN ACCESS

S.H., Goh, S. H., I., Rosnah, I., S.F., Lau, Seng Fong, P.A., Megat Abdul Rani, Puteri

Azaziah, T.B.M., Mohidin, Taznim Begam Mohd, F.B., Daud, Faiz Bin, A.R., Bahaman,

Abdul Rani, S., Khairani-Bejo, Siti, R., Radzi, Rozanaliza, K.H., Khor, Kuan Hua

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Rani (6602291133); Khairani-Bejo, Siti (15047903000); Radzi, Rozanaliza (55233947500);

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57205219717; 15119585400; 57201281325; 49460924200; 6506232509; 56523048000;

6602291133; 15047903000; 55233947500; 52663838500

Risk factors and prediction of leptospiral seropositivity among dogs and dog handlers in Malaysia

(2019) *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 16 (9), art. no. 1499

DOI: 10.3390/ijerph16091499

<https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85065504808&doi=10.3390%2Fijerph16091499&partnerID=40&md5=d6dabacb2b196e946691b1862f73a38c>

208) DOCUMENT TYPE: Article

OPEN ACCESS: ALL OPEN ACCESS; GOLD OPEN ACCESS; GREEN ACCEPTED OPEN ACCESS; GREEN FINAL OPEN ACCESS; GREEN OPEN ACCESS

C.R.M.R., Hamond, Camila Regua Motta Reis, C.D.S., Silveira, Caroline Da Silva, F., Buroni, Florencia, A., Suanes, Alejandra, C., Nieves, Cecilia, X., Salaberry, Ximena, V., Araoz, Virginia, R.A., Costa, Ricardo A., R., Rivero, Rodolfo, F., Giannitti, Federico
AUTHOR FULL NAMES: Hamond, Camila Regua Motta Reis (37097249900); Silveira, Caroline Da Silva (57202371687); Buroni, Florencia (57204178467); Suanes, Alejandra (57204186756); Nieves, Cecilia (57204179744); Salaberry, Ximena (57204175949); Araoz, Virginia (57205515558); Costa, Ricardo A. (57203839565); Rivero, Rodolfo (36925959500); Giannitti, Federico (40461337200)
37097249900; 57202371687; 57204178467; 57204186756; 57204179744; 57204175949; 57205515558; 57203839565; 36925959500; 40461337200

Leptospira interrogans serogroup Pomona serovar Kennewicki infection in two sheep flocks with acute leptospirosis in Uruguay

(2019) *Transboundary and Emerging Diseases*, 66 (3), pp. 1186 - 1194

DOI: 10.1111/tbed.13133

<https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85061572708&doi=10.1111%2Ftbed.13133&partnerID=40&md5=4631ecb967a93f090c4f349deee6bfde>

209) DOCUMENT TYPE: Article

N.A., Tabo, Norbel A., S.Y.A.M., Villanueva, Sharon Yvette Angelina M., N.G., Gloriani, Nina Gonzales

AUTHOR FULL NAMES: Tabo, Norbel A. (56173363600); Villanueva, Sharon Yvette Angelina M. (7004327679); Gloriani, Nina Gonzales (36080339500)
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Molecular detection of leptospira from environmental samples around abattoirs of Cavite province, Philippines

(2019) *Southeast Asian Journal of Tropical Medicine and Public Health*, 50 (2), pp. 290 - 299

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210) DOCUMENT TYPE: Article

M.S., Abdul Rahman, Mohammad Sabri, S., Khairani-Bejo, Siti, Z., Zakaria, Zunita, L., Hassan, L.

AUTHOR FULL NAMES: Abdul Rahman, Mohammad Sabri (57205217579); Khairani-Bejo, Siti (15047903000); Zakaria, Zunita (36490971800); Hassan, L. (15044258900)

57205217579; 15047903000; 36490971800; 15044258900

Molecular detection of leptospira sp. In cattle and goats in kelantan, malaysia after a massive flood using multiplex polymerase chain reaction

(2019) Tropical Biomedicine, 36 (1), pp. 165 - 171

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[85067987880&partnerID=40&md5=9f25e24c75591604ccac87db7f9018f5](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85067987880&partnerID=40&md5=9f25e24c75591604ccac87db7f9018f5)

211) DOCUMENT TYPE: Article

P.R., Deshmukh, Pradeep Ramrao, R., Narang, Rahul, J., Jain, Jyoti, M.A., Jain, Manish A., K., Pote, Kiran, P., Narang, Pratibha, R.V., Raj, Ratchagadasse Vimal, P.P., Kumar, Praveen P., P., Vijayachari, Paluru

AUTHOR FULL NAMES: Deshmukh, Pradeep Ramrao (7005915755); Narang, Rahul (16684115500); Jain, Jyoti (37031324400); Jain, Manish A. (55853966900); Pote, Kiran (57105343600); Narang, Pratibha (7004873317); Raj, Ratchagadasse Vimal (57191479244); Kumar, Praveen P. (57214807926); Vijayachari, Paluru (6601955151)

7005915755; 16684115500; 37031324400; 55853966900; 57105343600; 7004873317; 57191479244; 57214807926; 6601955151

Leptospirosis in Wardha District, Central India – Analysis of hospital based surveillance data

(2019) Clinical Epidemiology and Global Health, 7 (1), pp. 102 - 106

DOI: 10.1016/j.cegh.2018.02.005

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[85042645595&doi=10.1016%2Fj.cegh.2018.02.005&partnerID=40&md5=18f1f06ef0c15a2db5d5159bee5e285d](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85042645595&doi=10.1016%2Fj.cegh.2018.02.005&partnerID=40&md5=18f1f06ef0c15a2db5d5159bee5e285d)

212) DOCUMENT TYPE: Article

OPEN ACCESS: ALL OPEN ACCESS; HYBRID GOLD OPEN ACCESS

F.D.S.D.A., Moreira, Fernanda Da Silva De Andrade, G.R.B., Ferreira, Giovani Rezende Barbosa, L.C., Dias, Luanna Costa, M.L., Vitorino, Maria Isabel

AUTHOR FULL NAMES: Moreira, Fernanda Da Silva De Andrade (57221792011);

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Vitorino, Maria Isabel (14023788900)

57221792011; 58237937800; 57350507800; 14023788900

Variability temporal space of precipitation in the City of Belém-PA and its relation with the incidence of Leptospirosis Variabilidade da precipitação na Cidade de Belém-PA e sua relação com a incidência de Leptospirose

(2019) Revista Brasileira de Geografia Física, 12 (1), pp. 71 - 80

DOI: 10.26848/rbgf.v12.1.p071-080

[https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85099200311&doi=10.26848%2Frbgf.v12.1.p071-080&partnerID=40&md5=aaa6f4e8b3fac27a3d21b0e138811f25)

[85099200311&doi=10.26848%2Frbgf.v12.1.p071-](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85099200311&doi=10.26848%2Frbgf.v12.1.p071-080&partnerID=40&md5=aaa6f4e8b3fac27a3d21b0e138811f25)

[080&partnerID=40&md5=aaa6f4e8b3fac27a3d21b0e138811f25](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85099200311&doi=10.26848%2Frbgf.v12.1.p071-080&partnerID=40&md5=aaa6f4e8b3fac27a3d21b0e138811f25)

213) DOCUMENT TYPE: Article

OPEN ACCESS: ALL OPEN ACCESS; GOLD OPEN ACCESS; GREEN ACCEPTED OPEN ACCESS; GREEN OPEN ACCESS

A., Builes-Jaramillo, Alejandro, C.S., Arias-Monsalve, Clara S.

AUTHOR FULL NAMES: Builes-Jaramillo, Alejandro (57194789223); Arias-Monsalve, Clara S. (57213619756)

57194789223; 57213619756

Impact of El Niño-Southern oscillation on human leptospirosis in Colombia at different spatial scales

(2019) Journal of Infection in Developing Countries, 13 (12), pp. 1108 - 1116

DOI: 10.3855/jidc.11702

[https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85077930378&doi=10.3855%2Fjidc.11702&partnerID=40&md5=ec1370bcf8e46f358761584ee459a1ea)

[85077930378&doi=10.3855%2Fjidc.11702&partnerID=40&md5=ec1370bcf8e46f358761584ee459a1ea](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85077930378&doi=10.3855%2Fjidc.11702&partnerID=40&md5=ec1370bcf8e46f358761584ee459a1ea)

214) DOCUMENT TYPE: Article

OPEN ACCESS: ALL OPEN ACCESS; GOLD OPEN ACCESS

F., Rahmat, Fariq, A.J., Ishak, Asnor Juraiza, Z.D., Zulkafli, Zed Diyana, H., Yahaya, Hazlina, A.S., Masrani, Afiqah Syamimi

AUTHOR FULL NAMES: Rahmat, Fariq (57211635538); Ishak, Asnor Juraiza (24778781500); Zulkafli, Zed Diyana (55765693100); Yahaya, Hazlina (57522558900); Masrani, Afiqah Syamimi (57211646909)

57211635538; 24778781500; 55765693100; 57522558900; 57211646909

Prediction model of leptospirosis occurrence for Seremban (Malaysia) using meteorological data

(2019) International Journal of Integrated Engineering, 11 (4), pp. 61 - 69

DOI: 10.30880/ijie.2019.11.04.007

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[85074695653&doi=10.30880%2Fijie.2019.11.04.007&partnerID=40&md5=b6456268372b793779ab0b902ad712ad](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85074695653&doi=10.30880%2Fijie.2019.11.04.007&partnerID=40&md5=b6456268372b793779ab0b902ad712ad)

215) DOCUMENT TYPE: Article

OPEN ACCESS: ALL OPEN ACCESS; BRONZE OPEN ACCESS; GREEN ACCEPTED OPEN ACCESS; GREEN FINAL OPEN ACCESS; GREEN OPEN ACCESS

M.A., Alhoot, Mohammed Abdelfatah, R., Nagarajan, Rathika, M.S., Abdulmajid, Mohammad Saad, A.A.A., Alabed, Alabed Ali Ahmed, L.R.A., Al-Majeed, Layla Raad Abd, N.M., Bisri, Najihah Mohd, A.R.M., Al-Maleki, Anis Rageh Mohammad

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54413809700; 57211289018; 57211294810; 57200047571; 57211294313; 57211296507; 57196441953

Effects of global warming on the incidence of infectious diseases in Malaysia

(2019) International Journal of Medical Toxicology and Legal Medicine, 22 (1-2), pp. 111 - 117

DOI: 10.5958/0974-4614.2019.00026.3

<https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85073332960&doi=10.5958%2F0974-4614.2019.00026.3&partnerID=40&md5=c0ec5f05e5b73e7a9963b21f0f2c965e>

216) DOCUMENT TYPE: Article
OPEN ACCESS: ALL OPEN ACCESS; GOLD OPEN ACCESS

J.V., Blagojevic, Jelena V., M., Šekler, Milanko, M., Rajičić, Marija, B., Bajić, Branka, I., Budinski, Ivana, V.M., Jovanović, Vladimir M., T., Adnadjević, Tanja, D., Vidanović, Dejan, K., Matović, Kazimir, M.R., Vujošević, Mladen R.

AUTHOR FULL NAMES: Blagojevic, Jelena V. (55919075800); Šekler, Milanko (13406435900); Rajičić, Marija (56644904200); Bajić, Branka (57205610960); Budinski, Ivana (56048286600); Jovanović, Vladimir M. (56375693700); Adnadjević, Tanja (24461443100); Vidanović, Dejan (35209016000); Matović, Kazimir (25959294800); Vujošević, Mladen R. (7006768072)

55919075800; 13406435900; 56644904200; 57205610960; 56048286600; 56375693700; 24461443100; 35209016000; 25959294800; 7006768072

The prevalence of pathogenic forms of *Leptospira* in natural populations of small wild mammals in Serbia

(2019) *Acta Veterinaria Hungarica*, 67 (3), pp. 338 - 346

DOI: 10.1556/004.2019.035

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217) DOCUMENT TYPE: Article
OPEN ACCESS: ALL OPEN ACCESS; GREEN ACCEPTED OPEN ACCESS; GREEN OPEN ACCESS

E.V., Kuklev, Evgeniy V., A.A., Kovalevskaya, Anastasiya A., B.L., Agapov, Boris L., S.A., Scherbakova, Svetlana A.

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6508025658; 57208390375; 57209076964; 57209657527

Assessment of potential epidemic hazards caused by combined foci with bacterial, viral, and rickettsial infections
Оценка Потенциальной Эпидемической Опасности Сочетанных Природных Очагов Бактериальных, Вирусных И Риккетсиозных Инфекций

(2019) *Health Risk Analysis*, (1), pp. 78 - 83

DOI: 10.21668/HEALTH.RISK/2019.1.08

<https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85071382743&doi=10.21668%2FHEALTH.RISK%2F2019.1.08&partnerID=40&md5=3e28632069b386b4fa6021f40e3ab2d0>

218) DOCUMENT TYPE: Article
OPEN ACCESS: ALL OPEN ACCESS; GOLD OPEN ACCESS

E.V., Kuklev, Evgeniy V., A.A., Kovalevskaya, Anastasiya A., B.L., Agapov, Boris L., S.A., Scherbakova, Svetlana A.
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6508025658; 57208390375; 57209076964; 57209657527
Assessment of potential epidemic hazards caused by combined foci with bacterial, viral, and rickettsial infections
(2019) Health Risk Analysis, 2019 (1), pp. 78 - 83
DOI: 10.21668/health.risk/2019.1.08.eng
<https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85068377041&doi=10.21668%2Fhealth.risk%2F2019.1.08.eng&partnerID=40&md5=fd1138de14e429b5203c5a8f74a1bc8b>

219) DOCUMENT TYPE: Article

OPEN ACCESS: ALL OPEN ACCESS; GOLD OPEN ACCESS

D., Widiyanti, Dian, T., Djannatun, Titiek, I.I.P., Astuti, Ike Irmawati Purbo, E.D., Maharsi, Eri Dian
AUTHOR FULL NAMES: Widiyanti, Dian (55669128400); Djannatun, Titiek (57209331957); Astuti, Ike Irmawati Purbo (57209328172); Maharsi, Eri Dian (57209330151)
55669128400; 57209331957; 57209328172; 57209330151
Leptospira detection in flood-prone environment of Jakarta, Indonesia
(2019) Zoonoses and Public Health, 66 (6), pp. 597 - 602
DOI: 10.1111/zph.12610
<https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85067403227&doi=10.1111%2Fzph.12610&partnerID=40&md5=48fc9f1f37400fd9133cda7817884e4f>

220) DOCUMENT TYPE: Article

S., Rahelinirina, Soanandrasana, P., Bourhy, Pascale, F.M., Andriamiarimanana, Fehivola Mandanirina, B., Garin, Benoît, M.E., Rajerison, Minoarisoa Esther
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8243766200; 8374209300; 55255305400; 7003763595; 13102972100
High prevalence of Leptospira spp. In rodents in an urban setting in Madagascar
(2019) American Journal of Tropical Medicine and Hygiene, 100 (5), pp. 1079 - 1081
DOI: 10.4269/ajtmh.18-0642
<https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85065509679&doi=10.4269%2Fajtmh.18-0642&partnerID=40&md5=068b27222e4c0d4f9ec477ccda753fe2>

221) DOCUMENT TYPE: Article

OPEN ACCESS: ALL OPEN ACCESS; BRONZE OPEN ACCESS; GREEN FINAL OPEN ACCESS; GREEN OPEN ACCESS

J.M., Lara, Jackeline Monsalve, A.P.B.V., Zuben, Andrea Paula Bruno Von, J.V.V., Costa, José Vilton Vilton, M.R., Donalísio, Maria Rita, P.M.S.B., Francisco, Priscila Maria Stolses Bergamo

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Leptospirosis in Campinas, São Paulo, Brazil: 2007-2014 Leptospirose no município de Campinas, São Paulo, Brasil: 2007 a 2014

(2019) Revista Brasileira de Epidemiologia, 22, art. no. E190016

DOI: 10.1590/1980-549720190016

[https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85064205158&doi=10.1590%2F1980-549720190016&partnerID=40&md5=10ca765ab1cc25d3d7453641b8ac99da)

[85064205158&doi=10.1590%2F1980-](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85064205158&doi=10.1590%2F1980-549720190016&partnerID=40&md5=10ca765ab1cc25d3d7453641b8ac99da)

[549720190016&partnerID=40&md5=10ca765ab1cc25d3d7453641b8ac99da](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85064205158&doi=10.1590%2F1980-549720190016&partnerID=40&md5=10ca765ab1cc25d3d7453641b8ac99da)

222) DOCUMENT TYPE: Article

OPEN ACCESS: ALL OPEN ACCESS; GOLD OPEN ACCESS; GREEN ACCEPTED OPEN ACCESS; GREEN FINAL OPEN ACCESS; GREEN OPEN ACCESS

J.L., Duarte, Juliana Lúcia, L.L., Giatti, Leandro Luiz

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Leptospirosis incidence in a state capital in the Western Brazilian Amazon and its relationship with climate and environmental variability, 2008-2013 Incidencia de la leptospirosis en una capital de la Amazonía Occidental brasileña y su relación con la variabilidad climática y ambiental, entre los años 2008 y 2013 Incidência da leptospirose em uma capital da Amazônia Ocidental brasileira e sua relação com a variabilidade climática e ambiental, entre os anos de 2008 e 2013

(2019) Epidemiologia e serviços de saúde : revista do Sistema Único de Saúde do Brasil, 28 (1), art. no. e2017224

DOI: 10.5123/S1679-49742019000100009

[https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85063971715&doi=10.5123%2FS1679-49742019000100009&partnerID=40&md5=77e4cff1830fc665a321825b78f4e1e7)

[85063971715&doi=10.5123%2FS1679-](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85063971715&doi=10.5123%2FS1679-49742019000100009&partnerID=40&md5=77e4cff1830fc665a321825b78f4e1e7)

[49742019000100009&partnerID=40&md5=77e4cff1830fc665a321825b78f4e1e7](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85063971715&doi=10.5123%2FS1679-49742019000100009&partnerID=40&md5=77e4cff1830fc665a321825b78f4e1e7)

223) DOCUMENT TYPE: Article

OPEN ACCESS: ALL OPEN ACCESS; GOLD OPEN ACCESS; GREEN FINAL OPEN ACCESS; GREEN OPEN ACCESS

J.D., Gutiérrez, J. D., R.A., Martínez-Vega, Ruth Aralí, H.A., Botello, Hector A., F.J., Ruiz-Herrera, Freddy Jesús, L.C., Arenas-López, Laura Carolina, K.D., Hernandez-Tellez, Karen Dayana

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26323170100; 10340569200; 57201336318; 57208150119; 57208144187; 57208149446
Environmental and socioeconomic determinants of leptospirosis incidence in Colombia (2019) *Cadernos de Saude Publica*, 35 (3), art. no. e00118417
DOI: 10.1590/0102-311X00118417
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224) DOCUMENT TYPE: Article

OPEN ACCESS: ALL OPEN ACCESS; GOLD OPEN ACCESS; GREEN ACCEPTED OPEN ACCESS; GREEN FINAL OPEN ACCESS; GREEN OPEN ACCESS

D.E.P., Sumalapao, Derick Erl P., B.K.M., Del Rosario, Benjamin Kyle M., L.B.L., Suñga, Lara Beatrice L., C.C., Walther, Catherine C., N.G., Gloriani, Nina Gonzales
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56287762100; 57205584713; 59807256200; 57205581285; 36080339500
Frequency of typhoon occurrence accounts for the Poisson distribution of human leptospirosis cases across the different geographic regions in the Philippines (2019) *Asian Pacific Journal of Tropical Medicine*, 12 (1), pp. 26 - 31
DOI: 10.4103/1995-7645.250343
<https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85060644115&doi=10.4103%2F1995-7645.250343&partnerID=40&md5=5c3e9847560bb2d53d01567b04e7117b>

225) DOCUMENT TYPE: Article

OPEN ACCESS: ALL OPEN ACCESS; GOLD OPEN ACCESS

N.D.B., Ehelepola, N. D.B., K.A.M., Ariyaratne, Kusalika A.M., W.P., Dissanayake, Wasantha P.
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57190576897; 57190570257; 6603420054
The correlation between local weather and leptospirosis incidence in Kandy district, Sri Lanka from 2006 to 2015 (2019) *Global Health Action*, 12 (1), art. no. 1553283
DOI: 10.1080/16549716.2018.1553283
<https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85060341772&doi=10.1080%2F16549716.2018.1553283&partnerID=40&md5=be3a1afe9c27426ee1c271fbaaed0277>

226) DOCUMENT TYPE: Article

OPEN ACCESS: ALL OPEN ACCESS; GOLD OPEN ACCESS; GREEN FINAL OPEN ACCESS; GREEN OPEN ACCESS

I., Sasmal, Indrani, N.P., Gould, Nicholas P., K.L., Schuler, Krysten L., Y., Chang, Yungfu, A.J., Thachil, Anil J., J., Strules, Jennifer, C., Olfenbittel, Colleen, S., Datta, Shubham, C.S., DePerno, Christopher S.

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Leptospirosis in urban and suburban american black bears (*Ursus Americanus*) in western North Carolina, USA

(2019) *Journal of Wildlife Diseases*, 55 (1), pp. 74 - 83

DOI: 10.7589/2017-10-263

[https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85060246606&doi=10.7589%2F2017-10-263&partnerID=40&md5=c40fb39af887ecd1c1dfd24d14f52df5)

[85060246606&doi=10.7589%2F2017-10-](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85060246606&doi=10.7589%2F2017-10-263&partnerID=40&md5=c40fb39af887ecd1c1dfd24d14f52df5)

[263&partnerID=40&md5=c40fb39af887ecd1c1dfd24d14f52df5](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85060246606&doi=10.7589%2F2017-10-263&partnerID=40&md5=c40fb39af887ecd1c1dfd24d14f52df5)

227) DOCUMENT TYPE: Article

N.C., Cárdenas, Nicolás Céspedes, G.P., Infante, Gina Polo, D.A.R., Pacheco, Dina Andrea Rangel, J.P., Diaz, Juan Pablo, D.C.M., Wagner, Diana Carolina Mejia, R.A., Dias, Ricardo Augusto, J.S., Ferreira Neto, José Soares, M., Amaku, Marcos, P., Vargas-Pinto, Piero, L.J., Polo, Luis J.

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Seroprevalence of *Leptospira* spp infection and its risk factors among domestic dogs in Bogotá Colombia

(2018) *Veterinary and Animal Science*, 6, pp. 64 - 68

DOI: 10.1016/j.vas.2018.08.002

[https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85059763017&doi=10.1016%2Fj.vas.2018.08.002&partnerID=40&md5=3eeec4f0f7d8d200ed80845e516898e6)

[85059763017&doi=10.1016%2Fj.vas.2018.08.002&partnerID=40&md5=3eeec4f0f7d8d200ed80845e516898e6](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85059763017&doi=10.1016%2Fj.vas.2018.08.002&partnerID=40&md5=3eeec4f0f7d8d200ed80845e516898e6)

228) DOCUMENT TYPE: Article

OPEN ACCESS: ALL OPEN ACCESS; GOLD OPEN ACCESS; GREEN FINAL OPEN ACCESS; GREEN OPEN ACCESS

P.W., Dhewantara, Pandji Wibawa, A.A., Mamun, Abdullah Al, W., Zhang, Wenyi, W., Yin, Wenwu, F., Ding, Fan, D., Guo, Danhuai, W., Hu, Wenbiao, R.J., Soares Magalhães, Ricardo J.

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57200842699; 55666602500; 57215374020; 7202298949; 57204065568; 32667731300; 57218248248; 8863883300

Geographical and temporal distribution of the residual clusters of human leptospirosis in China, 2005–2016

(2018) Scientific Reports, 8 (1), art. no. 16650

DOI: 10.1038/s41598-018-35074-3

<https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85056252798&doi=10.1038%2Fs41598-018-35074-3&partnerID=40&md5=308c794024595449e4b41f00f1daf02d>

229) DOCUMENT TYPE: Article

OPEN ACCESS: ALL OPEN ACCESS; GOLD OPEN ACCESS; GREEN FINAL OPEN ACCESS; GREEN OPEN ACCESS

O.S., Baquero, Oswaldo Santos, G., Machado, Gustavo

AUTHOR FULL NAMES: Baquero, Oswaldo Santos (57202296367); Machado, Gustavo (37052478400)

57202296367; 37052478400

Spatiotemporal dynamics and risk factors for human Leptospirosis in Brazil

(2018) Scientific Reports, 8 (1), art. no. 15170

DOI: 10.1038/s41598-018-33381-3

<https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85054773084&doi=10.1038%2Fs41598-018-33381-3&partnerID=40&md5=0111e88458505daa04f6c668128a6e02>

230) DOCUMENT TYPE: Article

OPEN ACCESS: ALL OPEN ACCESS; GOLD OPEN ACCESS; GREEN FINAL OPEN ACCESS; GREEN OPEN ACCESS

S., Chadsuthi, Sudarat, K., Chalvet-Monfray, Karine, A., Wiratsudakul, Anuwat, D., Suwancharoen, Duangjai, J., Cappelle, Julien

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33067633200; 6602803804; 37023697200; 22959207100; 24449355500

A remotely sensed flooding indicator associated with cattle and buffalo leptospirosis cases in Thailand 2011-2013

(2018) BMC Infectious Diseases, 18 (1), art. no. 602

DOI: 10.1186/s12879-018-3537-3

<https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85057536231&doi=10.1186%2Fs12879-018-3537-3&partnerID=40&md5=dc230a04d2b8fac0cc55306a810d4db1>

231) DOCUMENT TYPE: Article

OPEN ACCESS: ALL OPEN ACCESS; GOLD OPEN ACCESS; GREEN FINAL OPEN ACCESS; GREEN OPEN ACCESS

A.C., Trimble, Amanda C., C.A., Blevins, Christopher A., L.A., Beard, Laurie A., A.R., Deforno, Ashley R., E.G., Davis, Elizabeth G.

AUTHOR FULL NAMES: Trimble, Amanda C. (57194107197); Blevins, Christopher A. (57204444136); Beard, Laurie A. (7005332521); Deforno, Ashley R. (57204444268); Davis, Elizabeth G. (24779379900)

57194107197; 57204444136; 7005332521; 57204444268; 24779379900

Seroprevalence, frequency of leptospiuria, and associated risk factors in horses in Kansas, Missouri, and Nebraska from 2016-2017

(2018) PLOS ONE, 13 (10), art. no. e0206639

DOI: 10.1371/journal.pone.0206639

[https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85055617930&doi=10.1371%2Fjournal.pone.0206639&partnerID=40&md5=1c990daf9123eb2573b698e5cd6bfc58)

[85055617930&doi=10.1371%2Fjournal.pone.0206639&partnerID=40&md5=1c990daf9123eb2573b698e5cd6bfc58](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85055617930&doi=10.1371%2Fjournal.pone.0206639&partnerID=40&md5=1c990daf9123eb2573b698e5cd6bfc58)

232) DOCUMENT TYPE: Article

OPEN ACCESS: ALL OPEN ACCESS; GOLD OPEN ACCESS; GREEN ACCEPTED OPEN ACCESS; GREEN FINAL OPEN ACCESS; GREEN OPEN ACCESS

M.A., Edre, Mohammad Aidid, H., KadirShahar, Hayati, S., Md Said, Salmiah, S.N., Syed Ismail, S. N.

AUTHOR FULL NAMES: Edre, Mohammad Aidid (57202310161); KadirShahar, Hayati (57204210711); Md Said, Salmiah (36873334100); Syed Ismail, S. N. (57194760047)

57202310161; 57204210711; 36873334100; 57194760047

Determinants of leptospirosis preventive practices among the community in a flood-prone residential area in Kuantan, Malaysia

(2018) Malaysian Journal of Medicine and Health Sciences, 14 (3), pp. 27 - 33

[https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85055003808&partnerID=40&md5=9ff261377aa9f42b7a75d55b9f226971)

[85055003808&partnerID=40&md5=9ff261377aa9f42b7a75d55b9f226971](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85055003808&partnerID=40&md5=9ff261377aa9f42b7a75d55b9f226971)

233) DOCUMENT TYPE: Article

V., Cortez, Valerie, E., Canal, Enrique, J.C., Dupont-Turkowsky, J. Catherine, T., Quevedo, Tatiana, C., Albújar, Christian, T., Chang, Ticheng, G., Salmón-Mulanovich, Gabriela, M.C., Guezala-Villavicencio, Maria C., M.P., Simons, Mark P., E.B., Margolis, Elisa B.

AUTHOR FULL NAMES: Cortez, Valerie (57103131800); Canal, Enrique (6506103289);

Dupont-Turkowsky, J. Catherine (57204142602); Quevedo, Tatiana (56252191800);

Albújar, Christian (41360981100); Chang, Ticheng (35363547900); Salmón-Mulanovich,

Gabriela (22942200300); Guezala-Villavicencio, Maria C. (57204144839); Simons, Mark P. (56119614400); Margolis, Elisa B. (35237994300)
57103131800; 6506103289; 57204142602; 56252191800; 41360981100; 35363547900;
22942200300; 57204144839; 56119614400; 35237994300

Identification of *Leptospira* and *Bartonella* among rodents collected across a habitat disturbance gradient along the Inter- Oceanic Highway in the southern Amazon Basin of Peru

(2018) PLOS ONE, 13 (10), art. no. e0205068

DOI: 10.1371/journal.pone.0205068

[https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85054615771&doi=10.1371%2Fjournal.pone.0205068&partnerID=40&md5=f6986d7227945ac03d85ce37063a4b63)

[85054615771&doi=10.1371%2Fjournal.pone.0205068&partnerID=40&md5=f6986d7227945ac03d85ce37063a4b63](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85054615771&doi=10.1371%2Fjournal.pone.0205068&partnerID=40&md5=f6986d7227945ac03d85ce37063a4b63)

234) DOCUMENT TYPE: Article

OPEN ACCESS: ALL OPEN ACCESS; GOLD OPEN ACCESS; GREEN ACCEPTED OPEN ACCESS; GREEN FINAL OPEN ACCESS; GREEN OPEN ACCESS

S., Manyullei, Syamsuar, A., Daud, Anwar, I.L., Maria, Ida Leida, M.M., Hatta, Mochammad M., D.A., Widyastuti, Diah Ayu

AUTHOR FULL NAMES: Manyullei, Syamsuar (56429686000); Daud, Anwar (57193112691); Maria, Ida Leida (57062982100); Hatta, Mochammad M. (8134403900); Widyastuti, Diah Ayu (57203990472)

56429686000; 57193112691; 57062982100; 8134403900; 57203990472

Identification of serovar leptospirosis in flood-prone areas Wajo district

(2018) Indian Journal of Public Health Research and Development, 9 (9), pp. 325 - 329

DOI: 10.5958/0976-5506.2018.01019.7

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[85053934142&doi=10.5958%2F0976-](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85053934142&doi=10.5958%2F0976-5506.2018.01019.7&partnerID=40&md5=9da418ea53ce60596661ca8af0abdfa3)

[5506.2018.01019.7&partnerID=40&md5=9da418ea53ce60596661ca8af0abdfa3](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85053934142&doi=10.5958%2F0976-5506.2018.01019.7&partnerID=40&md5=9da418ea53ce60596661ca8af0abdfa3)

235) DOCUMENT TYPE: Article

A., Sachu, Arun, A., Madhavan, Anitha, A.K., Vasudevan, Anu K., J., Vasudevapanicker, Jayalakshmi

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57189579810; 57204158140; 57200934764; 57204151893

Prevalence of dengue and leptospirosis co-infection in a tertiary care hospital in south india

(2018) Iranian Journal of Microbiology, 10 (4), pp. 227 - 232

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[85054766025&partnerID=40&md5=543bbd52524ee78316738c30e8b3d9b6](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85054766025&partnerID=40&md5=543bbd52524ee78316738c30e8b3d9b6)

236) DOCUMENT TYPE: Article

A., McPherson, Anna, P.S., Hill, Peter Stewart, M., Kama, Mike, S.A., Reid, Simon Andrew

AUTHOR FULL NAMES: McPherson, Anna (57194323924); Hill, Peter Stewart (7402918108); Kama, Mike (55232631100); Reid, Simon Andrew (7201777637) 57194323924; 7402918108; 55232631100; 7201777637

Exploring governance for a One Health collaboration for leptospirosis prevention and control in Fiji: Stakeholder perceptions, evidence, and processes

(2018) *International Journal of Health Planning and Management*, 33 (3), pp. 677 - 689

DOI: 10.1002/hpm.2521

[https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85044567744&doi=10.1002%2Fhpm.2521&partnerID=40&md5=42106941fe3a0824b2f7391c48418884)

[85044567744&doi=10.1002%2Fhpm.2521&partnerID=40&md5=42106941fe3a0824b2f7391c48418884](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85044567744&doi=10.1002%2Fhpm.2521&partnerID=40&md5=42106941fe3a0824b2f7391c48418884)

237) DOCUMENT TYPE: Article

M.J., Maze, Michael J., S., Cash-Goldwasser, Shama, M.P., Rubach, Matthew P., H.M., Biggs, Holly M., R.L., Galloway, Renee Lynn, K.J., Sharples, Katrina J., K.J., Allan, Kathryn J., J.E., Halliday, Jo E.B., S.C., Cleaveland, Sarah C., M.C., Shand, Mike Clarke
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36816215600; 56563040200; 55751015800; 59873033900; 7102801269; 7004251360; 54881478200; 36000502500; 57191181727; 25422666000

Risk factors for human acute leptospirosis in northern Tanzania

(2018) *PLOS Neglected Tropical Diseases*, 12 (6), art. no. e0006372

DOI: 10.1371/journal.pntd.0006372

[https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85049024392&doi=10.1371%2Fjournal.pntd.0006372&partnerID=40&md5=e429b104744704e3430d8bd008a2cf81)

[85049024392&doi=10.1371%2Fjournal.pntd.0006372&partnerID=40&md5=e429b104744704e3430d8bd008a2cf81](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85049024392&doi=10.1371%2Fjournal.pntd.0006372&partnerID=40&md5=e429b104744704e3430d8bd008a2cf81)

238) DOCUMENT TYPE: Article

Schooley

AUTHOR FULL NAMES: Schooley (57202493917)

57202493917

Our warming planet: Is the HIV-1 infected population in the crosshairs

(2018) *Topics in Antiviral Medicine*, 26 (2), pp. 67 - 70

[https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85048574223&partnerID=40&md5=3b07adb239a3833a8f3bf9aabdd796d8)

[85048574223&partnerID=40&md5=3b07adb239a3833a8f3bf9aabdd796d8](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85048574223&partnerID=40&md5=3b07adb239a3833a8f3bf9aabdd796d8)

239) DOCUMENT TYPE: Article

T., Ricardo, Tamara, L.C., Bergero, Laura Cristina, E.P., Bulgarella, Esteban P., M.A., Previtali, María Andrea

AUTHOR FULL NAMES: Ricardo, Tamara (57202318446); Bergero, Laura Cristina (57202323032); Bulgarella, Esteban P. (57202318618); Previtali, María Andrea (12794799000)
57202318446; 57202323032; 57202318618; 12794799000
Knowledge, attitudes and practices (KAP) regarding leptospirosis among residents of riverside settlements of Santa Fe, Argentina
(2018) PLOS Neglected Tropical Diseases, 12 (5), art. no. e0006470
DOI: 10.1371/journal.pntd.0006470
<https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85047860533&doi=10.1371%2Fjournal.pntd.0006470&partnerID=40&md5=5fefe4d000da15261b48911e56a8b45a>

240) DOCUMENT TYPE: Article

OPEN ACCESS: ALL OPEN ACCESS; GOLD OPEN ACCESS; GREEN ACCEPTED OPEN ACCESS; GREEN FINAL OPEN ACCESS; GREEN OPEN ACCESS

H.J., Mayfield, Helen J., J.H., Lowry, John H., C.H., Watson, Conall H., M., Kama, Mike, E.J., Nilles, Eric J., C.L., Lau, Colleen L.
AUTHOR FULL NAMES: Mayfield, Helen J. (55389475500); Lowry, John H. (58602960300); Watson, Conall H. (57202556038); Kama, Mike (55232631100); Nilles, Eric J. (16643480100); Lau, Colleen L. (57002151900)
55389475500; 58602960300; 57202556038; 55232631100; 16643480100; 57002151900
Use of geographically weighted logistic regression to quantify spatial variation in the environmental and sociodemographic drivers of leptospirosis in Fiji: a modelling study
(2018) The Lancet Planetary Health, 2 (5), pp. e223 - e232
DOI: 10.1016/S2542-5196(18)30066-4
<https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85046357018&doi=10.1016%2FS2542-5196%2818%2930066-4&partnerID=40&md5=3caa85df43c0b84d877588d834ef852b>

241) DOCUMENT TYPE: Article

OPEN ACCESS: ALL OPEN ACCESS; GOLD OPEN ACCESS; GREEN ACCEPTED OPEN ACCESS; GREEN FINAL OPEN ACCESS; GREEN OPEN ACCESS

N., Rodríguez-Valero, Natalia, H.M., Moríñigo, Helena Moza, M.J., Martínez, Miguel J., A., Peiró, Aida, I., Oliveira-Souto, Inés, M., Bodro, Marta, J., Gómez-Junyent, Joan, J., Gascon, Joaquim, J.M., GUTIÉRREZ, JOSE MUÑOZ
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55312111100; 57201121088; 56890159100; 57201118771; 57222562316; 54896352800; 55043261200; 57221993254; 35482708100
Leptospirosis in Spanish travelers returning from Chiang Mai: A case series
(2018) Travel Medicine and Infectious Disease, 23, pp. 77 - 79
DOI: 10.1016/j.tmaid.2018.02.013

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242) DOCUMENT TYPE: Article

OPEN ACCESS: ALL OPEN ACCESS; GREEN ACCEPTED OPEN ACCESS; GREEN OPEN ACCESS

M.L., Sohail, Muhammad Luqman, M.S., Khan, Muhammad Sarwar, M.U., Ijaz, Muhammad Usman, O., Naseer, Omer, Z., Fátima, Zahida, A.S., Ahmad, Abdullah Saghir, W., Ahmad, Waqas

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57205660717; 35078743800; 57221606747; 57189993553; 36833852200; 56678297000; 59184292700

Seroprevalence and risk factor analysis of human leptospirosis in distinct climatic regions of Pakistan

(2018) *Acta Tropica*, 181, pp. 79 - 83

DOI: 10.1016/j.actatropica.2018.01.021

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243) DOCUMENT TYPE: Article

N., Matsushita, Naohiko, C.F.S., Ng, Chris Fook Sheng, Y., Kim, Yoonhee, M., Suzuki, Motoi, N., Saito, Nobuo, K., Ariyoshi, Koya, E.P., Salva, Eumelia P., E.M., Dimaano, Efren M., J.B.R., Villarama, Jose Benito R., W.S., Go, Winston S.

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57201877671; 55651293700; 56402195600; 55554170300; 56029417000; 7005434354; 11539345900; 6507873340; 6507798185; 56707191100

The non-linear and lagged short-term relationship between rainfall and leptospirosis and the intermediate role of floods in the Philippines

(2018) *PLOS Neglected Tropical Diseases*, 12 (4), art. no. e0006331

DOI: 10.1371/journal.pntd.0006331

<https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85046370739&doi=10.1371%2Fjournal.pntd.0006331&partnerID=40&md5=bbc1f056a00d08f4439579c90f5a6a28>

244) DOCUMENT TYPE: Article

OPEN ACCESS: ALL OPEN ACCESS; GOLD OPEN ACCESS; GREEN ACCEPTED OPEN ACCESS; GREEN FINAL OPEN ACCESS; GREEN OPEN ACCESS

N., Nozmi, Noramira, S., Samsudin, Suhailah, S., Sukeri, Surianti, S.N., Mohd-Nazri, Shafei Nazri, W.M., Zahiruddin, Wan Mohd, Z., Idris, Zawaha, W.N., Arifin, Wan Nor, N., Idris, Norazlin, S.N.S., Saudi, Siti Nor Sakinah, N.M., Abdullah, Nurul Munirah
AUTHOR FULL NAMES: Nozmi, Noramira (57201064787); Samsudin, Suhailah (57193255264); Sukeri, Surianti (55794766900); Mohd-Nazri, Shafei Nazri (26025362700); Zahiruddin, Wan Mohd (57200412477); Idris, Zawaha (55657523700); Arifin, Wan Nor (55630160900); Idris, Norazlin (57201528578); Saudi, Siti Nor Sakinah (57193257172); Abdullah, Nurul Munirah (57214435805)
57201064787; 57193255264; 55794766900; 26025362700; 57200412477; 55657523700; 55630160900; 57201528578; 57193257172; 57214435805

Low levels of knowledge, attitudes and preventive practices on leptospirosis among a rural community in Hulu Langat District, Selangor, Malaysia
(2018) International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health, 15 (4), art. no. 693

DOI: 10.3390/ijerph15040693

<https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85045201978&doi=10.3390%2Fijerph15040693&partnerID=40&md5=8d878f88e1492ad791c368fa6f819f3b>

245) DOCUMENT TYPE: Article

OPEN ACCESS: ALL OPEN ACCESS; GOLD OPEN ACCESS; GREEN ACCEPTED OPEN ACCESS; GREEN FINAL OPEN ACCESS; GREEN OPEN ACCESS

E.A.M., Buffon, Elaiz Aparecida Mensch

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Socio-environmental vulnerability to human leptospirosis in urban agglomeration metropolitan of Curitiba, Paraná, Brazil: Methodological proposal from the multicriteria analysis and maps algebra Vulnerabilidade socioambiental à leptospirose humana no aglomerado urbano metropolitano de Curitiba, Paraná, Brasil: Proposta metodológica a partir da análise multicritério e álgebra de mapas

(2018) Saude e Sociedade, 27 (2), pp. 588 - 604

DOI: 10.1590/S0104-12902018170096

[https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85050196466&doi=10.1590%2FS0104-](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85050196466&doi=10.1590%2FS0104-12902018170096&partnerID=40&md5=7d84ed064adc4fc5a469869c891be321)

[12902018170096&partnerID=40&md5=7d84ed064adc4fc5a469869c891be321](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85050196466&doi=10.1590%2FS0104-12902018170096&partnerID=40&md5=7d84ed064adc4fc5a469869c891be321)

[12902018170096&partnerID=40&md5=7d84ed064adc4fc5a469869c891be321](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85050196466&doi=10.1590%2FS0104-12902018170096&partnerID=40&md5=7d84ed064adc4fc5a469869c891be321)

246) DOCUMENT TYPE: Article

OPEN ACCESS: ALL OPEN ACCESS; GOLD OPEN ACCESS; GREEN ACCEPTED OPEN ACCESS; GREEN OPEN ACCESS

K.A., Kaku, Kelsey A., M.H., Davidian, Michael H., E.M., DeSimone, Edward M.

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Leptospirosis: Potential rise from hurricanes and floods

(2018) U.S. Pharmacist, 43 (4), pp. HS2 - HS6

[https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85045753568&partnerID=40&md5=ff4ff88a3693f5e8564aa6dd32516228)

[85045753568&partnerID=40&md5=ff4ff88a3693f5e8564aa6dd32516228](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85045753568&partnerID=40&md5=ff4ff88a3693f5e8564aa6dd32516228)

247) DOCUMENT TYPE: Article

W.M., Zahiruddin, Wan Mohd, W.N., Arifin, Wan Nor, S.N., Mohd-Nazri, Shafei Nazri, S., Sukeri, Surianti, Z., Idris, Zawaha, R.A., Bakar, Rahman Abu, R.A., Hamat, R. A., O.B., Malina, Osman Binti, T.Z., Jamaluddin, T. Z.M.T., P., Arumugam, Pathman

AUTHOR FULL NAMES: Zahiruddin, Wan Mohd (57200412477); Arifin, Wan Nor (55630160900); Mohd-Nazri, Shafei Nazri (26025362700); Sukeri, Surianti (55794766900);

Idris, Zawaha (55657523700); Bakar, Rahman Abu (58381017000); Hamat, R. A. (55838385600); Malina, Osman Binti (25641056700); Jamaluddin, T. Z.M.T. (57218203508); Arumugam, Pathman (57201059773)

(57200412477); 55630160900; 26025362700; 55794766900; 55657523700; 58381017000; 55838385600; 25641056700; 57218203508; 57201059773

Development and validation of a new knowledge, attitude, belief and practice questionnaire on leptospirosis in Malaysia

(2018) BMC Public Health, 18 (1), art. no. 331

DOI: 10.1186/s12889-018-5234-y

[https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85043256449&doi=10.1186%2Fs12889-018-5234-y&partnerID=40&md5=104a7cd1035a72e70e03afdf09f49866)

[85043256449&doi=10.1186%2Fs12889-018-5234-](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85043256449&doi=10.1186%2Fs12889-018-5234-y&partnerID=40&md5=104a7cd1035a72e70e03afdf09f49866)

[y&partnerID=40&md5=104a7cd1035a72e70e03afdf09f49866](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85043256449&doi=10.1186%2Fs12889-018-5234-y&partnerID=40&md5=104a7cd1035a72e70e03afdf09f49866)

[85043256449&doi=10.1186%2Fs12889-018-5234-](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85043256449&doi=10.1186%2Fs12889-018-5234-y&partnerID=40&md5=104a7cd1035a72e70e03afdf09f49866)

[y&partnerID=40&md5=104a7cd1035a72e70e03afdf09f49866](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85043256449&doi=10.1186%2Fs12889-018-5234-y&partnerID=40&md5=104a7cd1035a72e70e03afdf09f49866)

[y&partnerID=40&md5=104a7cd1035a72e70e03afdf09f49866](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85043256449&doi=10.1186%2Fs12889-018-5234-y&partnerID=40&md5=104a7cd1035a72e70e03afdf09f49866)

248) DOCUMENT TYPE: Article

OPEN ACCESS: ALL OPEN ACCESS; GOLD OPEN ACCESS; GREEN FINAL OPEN ACCESS; GREEN OPEN ACCESS

N.A., Tabo, Norbel A., S.Y.A.M., Villanueva, Sharon Yvette Angelina M., N.G., Gloriani, Nina Gonzales

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Prevalence of Leptospira-agglutinating antibodies in abattoir workers and slaughtered animals in selected slaughterhouses in Cavite, Philippines

(2018) Philippine Journal of Science, 147 (1), pp. 27 - 35

[https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85066398455&partnerID=40&md5=93ce7dab22359e4227d123a27351100a)

[85066398455&partnerID=40&md5=93ce7dab22359e4227d123a27351100a](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85066398455&partnerID=40&md5=93ce7dab22359e4227d123a27351100a)

249) DOCUMENT TYPE: Article

C.L., Lau, Colleen L., N.J., Townell, Nicola J., E.B., Skinner, Eloise B., D.J., van den Berg, Debra J., S.B., Craig, Scott Benjamin

AUTHOR FULL NAMES: Lau, Colleen L. (57002151900); Townell, Nicola J. (55257262400); Skinner, Eloise B. (57217238961); van den Berg, Debra J. (57191831912); Craig, Scott Benjamin (7201656455)
57002151900; 55257262400; 57217238961; 57191831912; 7201656455
Leptospirosis: An important zoonosis acquired through work, play and travel
(2018) Australian Journal of General Practice, 47 (3), pp. 105 - 110
DOI: 10.31128/AFP-07-17-4286
<https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85063672162&doi=10.31128%2FAFP-07-17-4286&partnerID=40&md5=4c1043a724ee39a825c880a208d47c12>

250) DOCUMENT TYPE: Article

OPEN ACCESS: ALL OPEN ACCESS; BRONZE OPEN ACCESS; GREEN ACCEPTED OPEN ACCESS; GREEN OPEN ACCESS

J.D., Gutiérrez, J. D., R.A., Martínez-Vega, Ruth Aralí
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26323170100; 10340569200
Spatiotemporal dynamics of human leptospirosis and its relationship with rainfall anomalies in Colombia
(2018) Transactions of the Royal Society of Tropical Medicine and Hygiene, 112 (3), pp. 115 - 123
DOI: 10.1093/trstmh/try032
<https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85047384168&doi=10.1093%2Ftrstmh%2Ftry032&partnerID=40&md5=4604b9af82d5b2e2cdae8c423f6305ad>

251) DOCUMENT TYPE: Article

A., Casanovas-Massana, Arnau, F., Costa, Federico, I.N., Riediger, Irina Nastassja, G.M., da Cunha, Geraldo Marcelo, D.S., de Oliveira, Daiana Santos, D.C., Mota, Diogenes C., E., Sousa, Erica, V.A., Querino, Vladimir Airam, N.R.R., Nery, Nivison Ruy Rocha, M.G., Reis, Mitermayer G.
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35386067500; 55378617300; 36515425700; 8595056000; 56706945700; 57198489436; 57193562905; 57198517099; 57086829100; 35459915300
Spatial and temporal dynamics of pathogenic *Leptospira* in surface waters from the urban slum environment
(2018) Water Research, 130, pp. 176 - 184
DOI: 10.1016/j.watres.2017.11.068

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252) DOCUMENT TYPE: Article

OPEN ACCESS: ALL OPEN ACCESS; GREEN ACCEPTED OPEN ACCESS; GREEN OPEN ACCESS

M., Vitale, Maria, S., Agnello, Stefano, M., Chetta, Michele, B., Amato, Benedetta, G., Vitale, Giustina, C., Di Bella, Calogero, D., Vicari, Domenico, V., Di Marco Lo Presti, Vincenzo

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15058324100; 56526584500; 37021317100; 56526563500; 7101621016; 57197727804; 23486899100; 57211677792

Human leptospirosis cases in Palermo Italy. The role of rodents and climate (2018) *Journal of Infection and Public Health*, 11 (2), pp. 209 - 214

DOI: 10.1016/j.jiph.2017.07.024

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253) DOCUMENT TYPE: Article

OPEN ACCESS: ALL OPEN ACCESS; GOLD OPEN ACCESS

V.C., Colombo, Valeria C., I.J., Gamieta, Ignacio José, S., Grune Löffler, Sylvia, B.F., Brihuega, Bibiana Felicitas, P.M., Beldomenico, Pablo Martín

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56306736000; 56287136500; 55748438400; 23003360500; 56148965800

New host species for *Leptospira borgpetersenii* and *Leptospira interrogans* serovar Copenhageni

(2018) *Veterinary Microbiology*, 215, pp. 90 - 92

DOI: 10.1016/j.vetmic.2018.01.007

<https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85041483867&doi=10.1016%2Fj.vetmic.2018.01.007&partnerID=40&md5=bc314adee8fda5a39ea376297dc591f>

254) DOCUMENT TYPE: Article

OPEN ACCESS: ALL OPEN ACCESS; GREEN FINAL OPEN ACCESS; GREEN OPEN ACCESS

C., Yang, Chihwei

AUTHOR FULL NAMES: Yang, Chihwei (57202512739)

57202512739

Leptospirosis renal disease: Emerging culprit of chronic kidney disease unknown etiology

(2018) *Nephron*, 138 (2), pp. 129 - 136

DOI: 10.1159/000480691

[https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85029747182&doi=10.1159%2F000480691&partnerID=40&md5=4332838ddb95ebcd971071a4202f8e9a)

[85029747182&doi=10.1159%2F000480691&partnerID=40&md5=4332838ddb95ebcd971071a4202f8e9a](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85029747182&doi=10.1159%2F000480691&partnerID=40&md5=4332838ddb95ebcd971071a4202f8e9a)

255) DOCUMENT TYPE: Article

OPEN ACCESS: ALL OPEN ACCESS; BRONZE OPEN ACCESS

M., Picardeau, Mathieu

AUTHOR FULL NAMES: Picardeau, Mathieu (6701694004)

6701694004

Leptospirosis, neglected among the neglected diseases La leptospirose, négligée parmi les maladies négligées

(2018) *Bulletin de l'Academie Veterinaire de France*, 171 (3)

DOI: 10.4267/2042/70088

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[85066903196&doi=10.4267%2F2042%2F70088&partnerID=40&md5=5c0a3bda8a59d01a666f31d5ac72cd0e](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85066903196&doi=10.4267%2F2042%2F70088&partnerID=40&md5=5c0a3bda8a59d01a666f31d5ac72cd0e)

256) DOCUMENT TYPE: Article

OPEN ACCESS: ALL OPEN ACCESS; GOLD OPEN ACCESS

F.O., Okaka, Fredrick Okoth, B.D.O., Odhiambo, Beneah D.O.

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Relationship between flooding and out break of infectious diseases in Kenya: A review of the literature

(2018) *Journal of Environmental and Public Health*, 2018, art. no. 5452938

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[85056308121&doi=10.1155%2F2018%2F5452938&partnerID=40&md5=0e4713de95e0994942d82c756b6e76a7](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85056308121&doi=10.1155%2F2018%2F5452938&partnerID=40&md5=0e4713de95e0994942d82c756b6e76a7)

257) DOCUMENT TYPE: Article

OPEN ACCESS: ALL OPEN ACCESS; GOLD OPEN ACCESS; GREEN FINAL OPEN ACCESS; GREEN OPEN ACCESS

A.N., Supe, Avinash N., M., Khetarpal, Mini, S., Naik, Shantaram, P., Keskar, Padmaja

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Leptospirosis following heavy rains in 2017 in Mumbai: Report of large-scale community chemoprophylaxis

(2018) National Medical Journal of India, 31 (1), pp. 19 - 21

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[85055137624&doi=10.4103%2F0970-](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85055137624&doi=10.4103%2F0970-258X.243407&partnerID=40&md5=119dcfb54e88bf136d86c4cb7378dda1)

[258X.243407&partnerID=40&md5=119dcfb54e88bf136d86c4cb7378dda1](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85055137624&doi=10.4103%2F0970-258X.243407&partnerID=40&md5=119dcfb54e88bf136d86c4cb7378dda1)

258) DOCUMENT TYPE: Article

E., Togami, Eri, M., Kama, Mike, C., Goarant, Cyrille, S.B., Craig, Scott Benjamin, C.L., Lau, Colleen L., J.M., Ritter, Jana M., A., Imrie, Allison, A.I., Ko, Albert I., E.J., Nilles, Eric J.

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57195991541; 55232631100; 6603498952; 7201656455; 57002151900; 55770903300;

7003670637; 7007018347; 16643480100

A large leptospirosis outbreak following successive severe floods in Fiji, 2012

(2018) American Journal of Tropical Medicine and Hygiene, 99 (4), pp. 849 - 851

DOI: 10.4269/ajtmh.18-0335

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[85054430556&doi=10.4269%2Fajtmh.18-](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85054430556&doi=10.4269%2Fajtmh.18-0335&partnerID=40&md5=af916196d8b7ff3b030275c4d2904ba1)

[0335&partnerID=40&md5=af916196d8b7ff3b030275c4d2904ba1](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85054430556&doi=10.4269%2Fajtmh.18-0335&partnerID=40&md5=af916196d8b7ff3b030275c4d2904ba1)

259) DOCUMENT TYPE: Article

OPEN ACCESS: ALL OPEN ACCESS; GREEN FINAL OPEN ACCESS; GREEN OPEN ACCESS

P., Le Turnier, Paul, É., Mosnier, Émilie, R., Schaub, Roxane, P., Bourhy, Pascale, A., Jolivet, Anne, C., Cropet, Claire, N., Villemant, Nicolas, S., Trombert-Paolantoni, Sabine, A., Berlioz-Arthaud, Alain, M., Nacher, Mathieu

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Trombert-Paolantoni, Sabine (56617160200); Berlioz-Arthaud, Alain (6506119019);

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57192950236; 24344432000; 57201097801; 8374209300; 16137962300; 9942663800;

57189518665; 56617160200; 6506119019; 7006076854

Epidemiology of human leptospirosis in French Guiana (2007-2014): A retrospective study

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DOI: 10.4269/ajtmh.17-0734

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[85053065706&doi=10.4269%2Fajtmh.17-](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85053065706&doi=10.4269%2Fajtmh.17-0734&partnerID=40&md5=2c8a1864710fc043ccccf258d97dc3145)

[0734&partnerID=40&md5=2c8a1864710fc043ccccf258d97dc3145](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85053065706&doi=10.4269%2Fajtmh.17-0734&partnerID=40&md5=2c8a1864710fc043ccccf258d97dc3145)

260) DOCUMENT TYPE: Article

OPEN ACCESS: ALL OPEN ACCESS; GREEN FINAL OPEN ACCESS; GREEN OPEN ACCESS

T., Ricardo, Tamara, L.D., Monje, L. D., N.Y., Landolt, Noelia Yolanda, Y.T., Chiani, Yosena Teresita, M., Fernanda Schmeling, M., P.M., Beldomenico, Pablo Martín, N., Bibiana Vanasco, N., M.A., Previtali, María Andrea

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57202318446; 15840104100; 56940611200; 40161256300; 57272789400; 56148965800; 57272547200; 12794799000

First report on *Leptospira interrogans* in the sigmodontine rodent *Scapteromys aquaticus*
Primer informe de *Leptospira interrogans* en el roedor sigmodontino
Scapteromys aquaticus

(2018) Revista Panamericana de Salud Publica/Pan American Journal of Public Health, 42, art. no. e83

DOI: 10.26633/RPSP.2018.83

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[85052016703&doi=10.26633%2FRPSP.2018.83&partnerID=40&md5=07c9f1393ce693e715804b41f58f978c](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85052016703&doi=10.26633%2FRPSP.2018.83&partnerID=40&md5=07c9f1393ce693e715804b41f58f978c)

261) DOCUMENT TYPE: Article

OPEN ACCESS: ALL OPEN ACCESS; GOLD OPEN ACCESS; GREEN FINAL OPEN ACCESS; GREEN OPEN ACCESS

J.G., Filho, João Ghizzo, N.O., Nazário, Nazaré Otília, P.F., Freitas, Paulo Fontoura, G.D.A., Pinto, Gustavo De Araújo, A.D., Schlindwein, Aline Daiane

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57204479501; 6505970714; 7102268797; 57203188986; 35741835400

Temporal analysis of the relationship between leptospirosis, rainfall levels and seasonality, Santa Catarina, Brazil, 2005-2015

(2018) Revista do Instituto de Medicina Tropical de Sao Paulo, 60, art. no. e39

DOI: 10.1590/S1678-9946201860039

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[85050868637&doi=10.1590%2FS1678-9946201860039&partnerID=40&md5=78d76741c4968a41ab23efe1f2d863dc](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85050868637&doi=10.1590%2FS1678-9946201860039&partnerID=40&md5=78d76741c4968a41ab23efe1f2d863dc)

262) DOCUMENT TYPE: Article

OPEN ACCESS: ALL OPEN ACCESS; GOLD OPEN ACCESS; GREEN ACCEPTED OPEN ACCESS; GREEN FINAL OPEN ACCESS; GREEN OPEN ACCESS

K.S., Hayati, K. S., S.I., Sharifah Norkhadijah, Syed Ismail, S., Md Said, Salmiah, M.A., Edre, Mohammad Aidid, T.D., Khin, T. D.

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55068465200; 57202300033; 36873334100; 57202310161; 57202311519

Hot-spot and cluster analysis on legal and illegal dumping sites as the contributors of leptospirosis in a flood hazard area in Pahang, Malaysia

(2018) Asian Journal of Agriculture and Biology, 6 (Specialissue), pp. 78 - 82

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263) DOCUMENT TYPE: Article

M.A., Edre, Mohammad Aidid, K.S., Hayati, K. S., S., Md Said, Salmiah, S.I., Sharifah Nor Khadijah, S. I.

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57202310161; 55068465200; 36873334100; 57202301522

Spatial distribution of knowledge, attitude and practice on leptospirosis prevention and its predictors using stratum risk identification methods among residents in a flood prone area in Kuantan, Pahang, Malaysia

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264) DOCUMENT TYPE: Article

M.F., Mohd Radi, Mohd Firdaus, J.H., Hashim, Jamal Hisham, M.H., Jaafar, Mohd Hasni, R., Hod, Rozita, N., Ahmad, N., A., Mohammed Nawwi, Azmawati, G.M., Baloch, Gul Muhammad, R., Ismail, Rohaida, N.I.F., Ayub, Nur Izzah Farakhin

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57202038820; 6602456173; 56245513300; 37072342700; 55655397900; 55342646100;

6506053085; 57200387554; 57202036813

Leptospirosis outbreak after the 2014 major flooding event in Kelantan, Malaysia: A spatial-temporal analysis

(2018) American Journal of Tropical Medicine and Hygiene, 98 (5), pp. 1281 - 1295

DOI: 10.4269/ajtmh.16-0922

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[85046896491&doi=10.4269%2Fajtmh.16-](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85046896491&doi=10.4269%2Fajtmh.16-0922&partnerID=40&md5=942a4be92fae37b3cf8b18c30ce54cee)

[0922&partnerID=40&md5=942a4be92fae37b3cf8b18c30ce54cee](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85046896491&doi=10.4269%2Fajtmh.16-0922&partnerID=40&md5=942a4be92fae37b3cf8b18c30ce54cee)

265) DOCUMENT TYPE: Article

OPEN ACCESS: ALL OPEN ACCESS; BRONZE OPEN ACCESS; GREEN FINAL OPEN ACCESS; GREEN OPEN ACCESS

M.U., Ijaz, Muhammad Usman, S.H., Farooqi, Shahid Hussain, A.I., Aqib, Amjad Islam, P., Bakht, Painsa, A., Ali, Ahmad, A., Ghaffar, Awais, S., Saleem, Sehrish

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57221606747; 57194081448; 57190972427; 57201997038; 57211194429; 57200941647; 57200942628

Sero-epidemiology of bovine leptospirosis and associated risk factors in a flood affected zone of Pakistan

(2018) Pakistan Veterinary Journal, 38 (2), pp. 179 - 183

DOI: 10.29261/pakvetj/2018.027

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[85046768538&doi=10.29261%2Fpakvetj%2F2018.027&partnerID=40&md5=4ea5f6ee443fd55625285cd6d9ebd4c4](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85046768538&doi=10.29261%2Fpakvetj%2F2018.027&partnerID=40&md5=4ea5f6ee443fd55625285cd6d9ebd4c4)

266) DOCUMENT TYPE: Article

OPEN ACCESS: ALL OPEN ACCESS; GOLD OPEN ACCESS; GREEN ACCEPTED OPEN ACCESS; GREEN OPEN ACCESS

M.U., Ijaz, Muhammad Usman, S.N., Abbas, Syed Nazar, S.H., Farooqi, Shahid Hussain, A.I., Aqib, Amjad Islam, G.A., Anwar, Ghulam Ali, A., Rehman, Abdul, M.M., Ali, Muhammad Muddassir, K.M., Mehmood, Khalid M., A., Khan, Amjad

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57221606747; 57189623439; 57194081448; 57190972427; 57195981384; 57945261900; 56906577100; 39561380000; 57005807200

Sero-epidemiology and hemato-biochemical study of bovine leptospirosis in flood affected zone of Pakistan

(2018) Acta Tropica, 177, pp. 51 - 57

DOI: 10.1016/j.actatropica.2017.09.032

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[85030710613&doi=10.1016%2Fj.actatropica.2017.09.032&partnerID=40&md5=ab162e7f3715382df230d7bf6a77a3d6](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85030710613&doi=10.1016%2Fj.actatropica.2017.09.032&partnerID=40&md5=ab162e7f3715382df230d7bf6a77a3d6)

267) DOCUMENT TYPE: Article

OPEN ACCESS: ALL OPEN ACCESS; BRONZE OPEN ACCESS; GREEN FINAL OPEN ACCESS; GREEN OPEN ACCESS

I.D.O.C., Santos, Ivanildo De Oliveira Correia, M.F.D.A., Landi, Marina Frota De Albuquerque, L.M., Cruz, Laurício Monteiro, M.I.R., Bofill, Maria Isabel Rao, D.E., Dos Santos, Divino Eterno, E.M., Mendes de Lima, Eduardo Mauricio, M.B.D., Castro, Márcio Botelho De

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57200309473; 57200303931; 57188837976; 57188721070; 57200305547; 57211515897; 7102295190

Human leptospirosis in the Federal District, Brazil, 2011-2015: Eco-epidemiological characterization

(2017) Revista da Sociedade Brasileira de Medicina Tropical, 50 (6), pp. 777 - 782

DOI: 10.1590/0037-8682-0234-2017

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268) DOCUMENT TYPE: Article

OPEN ACCESS: ALL OPEN ACCESS; GOLD OPEN ACCESS; GREEN ACCEPTED OPEN ACCESS; GREEN FINAL OPEN ACCESS; GREEN OPEN ACCESS

P., Ribeiro, Policarpo, N.B., Bhatt, Nilesh B., S., Ali, Sádía, V.O., Monteiro, Vanessa Onofre, E., da Silva, Edmilson, I.T., Balassiano, Ilana Teruszkin, C., Aquino, Carolina, N.R., de Deus, Nilsa Razão, O.C., Guiliche, Onelia C., A.F., Muianga, Argentina Felisbela

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57195961937; 35301601300; 57104199500; 57188854479; 58333615200; 35550353500; 57195966711; 24343424100; 57194593851; 57142496800

Seroepidemiology of leptospirosis among febrile patients in a rapidly growing suburban slum and a flood-vulnerable rural district in Mozambique, 2012–2014: Implications for the management of fever

(2017) International Journal of Infectious Diseases, 64, pp. 50 - 57

DOI: 10.1016/j.ijid.2017.08.018

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[85030535915&doi=10.1016%2Fj.ijid.2017.08.018&partnerID=40&md5=7b37a0c141dc58248daa1974d26931c8](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85030535915&doi=10.1016%2Fj.ijid.2017.08.018&partnerID=40&md5=7b37a0c141dc58248daa1974d26931c8)

269) DOCUMENT TYPE: Article

OPEN ACCESS: ALL OPEN ACCESS; GOLD OPEN ACCESS

F., Morán, Flavia, T.J., Ochoa, Theresa J.

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57195594106; 35593777700

Prevention, diagnosis, and treatment of pediatric infections during natural disasters
Prevención, diagnóstico y tratamiento de infecciones pediátricas en desastres naturales
(2017) Revista Peruana de Medicina Experimental y Salud Pública, 34 (4), pp. 723 - 730

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270) DOCUMENT TYPE: Article

OPEN ACCESS: ALL OPEN ACCESS; GOLD OPEN ACCESS; GREEN ACCEPTED
OPEN ACCESS; GREEN OPEN ACCESS

L.B.L., Santos, Leonardo Bacelar Lima, T.J.D., Carvalho, Tiago Jose De, L.O., Anderson, Liana Oighenstein, C.M., Rudorff, Conrado M., V., Marchezini, Victor, L.R., Londe, Luciana R., S.M., Saito, Silvia Midori

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25932362000; 36809208200; 9246510700; 22235251500; 56097667100; 55976711500; 56007418200

An RS-GIS-Based Comprehensive Impact Assessment of Floods-A Case Study in Madeira River, Western Brazilian Amazon

(2017) IEEE Geoscience and Remote Sensing Letters, 14 (9), art. no. 7999247, pp. 1614 - 1617

DOI: 10.1109/LGRS.2017.2726524

[https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85028939063&doi=10.1109%2FLGRS.2017.2726524&partnerID=40&md5=edb83882dced624962443fcf337f9bdb)

[85028939063&doi=10.1109%2FLGRS.2017.2726524&partnerID=40&md5=edb83882dced624962443fcf337f9bdb](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85028939063&doi=10.1109%2FLGRS.2017.2726524&partnerID=40&md5=edb83882dced624962443fcf337f9bdb)

271) DOCUMENT TYPE: Article

K.D., Salagre, Kaustubh Dilip, R.N., Sahay, Ravindra Nath, A.R., Pazare, Amar R., A., Dubey, Abhishek, K.K., Marathe, Kunal K.

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55866221600; 7003683624; 6603281097; 57551760300; 57195521755

A study of clinical profile of patients presenting with complications of acute febrile illnesses during monsoon

(2017) Journal of Association of Physicians of India, 65 (September), pp. 37 - 42

[https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85028585471&partnerID=40&md5=71742a092ec0175a53d982561597a149)

[85028585471&partnerID=40&md5=71742a092ec0175a53d982561597a149](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85028585471&partnerID=40&md5=71742a092ec0175a53d982561597a149)

272) DOCUMENT TYPE: Article

S.D.A., Silva, Suzana De Araújo, J.A.D.S., Gama, José Aparecido Da Silva, N.H., Callado, Nélia Henriques, V.C., Souza, Vladimir C.B.De
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57195393891; 58438687400; 6508310371; 57195624690
Sanitation and public health in the hydrographic basin of Reginaldo Creek, maceió, Alagoas Saneamento básico e saúde pública na bacia hidrográfica do Riacho Reginaldo em Maceió, Alagoas
(2017) Engenharia Sanitaria e Ambiental, 22 (4), pp. 699 - 709
DOI: 10.1590/S1413-41522017146971
<https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85027688936&doi=10.1590%2FS1413-41522017146971&partnerID=40&md5=00fa7f602f4b0b3fb6ddcc949888011a>

273) DOCUMENT TYPE: Article

OPEN ACCESS: ALL OPEN ACCESS; GOLD OPEN ACCESS; GREEN FINAL OPEN ACCESS; GREEN OPEN ACCESS

S., Jorge, Sérgio, R.A., Schuch, Rodrigo Andrade, N.R., de Oliveira, Natasha Rodrigues, C.E.P., da Cunha, Carlos Eduardo Pouey, C.K., Gomes, Charles Klazer, T.L., Oliveira, Thaís Larre, C., Rizzi, Caroline, A.F., Qadan, Aisha Farid, V.D., Pacce, Violetta Dias, A.L., Coelho Recuero, Ana Lúcia
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55303796600; 56193063100; 56288936800; 55814517400; 56289000900; 36718002900; 16639869800; 57195150893; 57193274685; 57195153798
Human and animal leptospirosis in Southern Brazil: A five-year retrospective study
(2017) Travel Medicine and Infectious Disease, 18, pp. 46 - 52
DOI: 10.1016/j.tmaid.2017.07.010
<https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85025835959&doi=10.1016%2Fj.tmaid.2017.07.010&partnerID=40&md5=f2840298fc5d82a05514d5e48fca0f50>

274) DOCUMENT TYPE: Article

OPEN ACCESS: ALL OPEN ACCESS; GREEN FINAL OPEN ACCESS; GREEN OPEN ACCESS

J., Ledien, Julia, S., Sorn, Sopheak, S., Hem, Sopheak, R., Huy, Rekol, P., Buchy, Philippe, A.P., Tarantola, A. P., J., Cappelle, Julien

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Assessing the performance of remotelysensed flooding indicators and their potential contribution to early warning for leptospirosis in Cambodia
(2017) PLOS ONE, 12 (7), art. no. e0181044

DOI: 10.1371/journal.pone.0181044

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[85024381641&doi=10.1371%2Fjournal.pone.0181044&partnerID=40&md5=1b5f278f70128c7032fef727ff2a97e6](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85024381641&doi=10.1371%2Fjournal.pone.0181044&partnerID=40&md5=1b5f278f70128c7032fef727ff2a97e6)

275) DOCUMENT TYPE: Article

OPEN ACCESS: ALL OPEN ACCESS; GOLD OPEN ACCESS; GREEN ACCEPTED OPEN ACCESS; GREEN FINAL OPEN ACCESS; GREEN OPEN ACCESS

R., Lovera, Rosario, M.S., Fernández, María Soledad, J., Jacob, Jens, N.E., Lucero, Nidia E., G.E., Morici, Gabriel E., B.F., Brihuega, Bibiana Felicitas, M.I., Farace, María Isabel, J.L., Caracostantogolo, Jorge Luis, C., Regino, Cavia

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Intrinsic and extrinsic factors related to pathogen infection in wild small mammals in intensive milk cattle and swine production systems

(2017) PLOS Neglected Tropical Diseases, 11 (6), art. no. e0005722

DOI: 10.1371/journal.pntd.0005722

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[85021651942&doi=10.1371%2Fjournal.pntd.0005722&partnerID=40&md5=9a0b182f4b4b36eb4ab42cf31f2eb215](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85021651942&doi=10.1371%2Fjournal.pntd.0005722&partnerID=40&md5=9a0b182f4b4b36eb4ab42cf31f2eb215)

276) DOCUMENT TYPE: Article

OPEN ACCESS: ALL OPEN ACCESS; GOLD OPEN ACCESS; GREEN ACCEPTED OPEN ACCESS; GREEN FINAL OPEN ACCESS; GREEN OPEN ACCESS

Y.P., Joshi, Yadav Prasad, E., Kim, Eunhye, H., Cheong, Hae-kwan

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57192296551; 57207014213; 57216615333

The influence of climatic factors on the development of hemorrhagic fever with renal syndrome and leptospirosis during the peak season in Korea: An ecologic study

(2017) BMC Infectious Diseases, 17 (1), art. no. 406

DOI: 10.1186/s12879-017-2506-6

<https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85020233326&doi=10.1186%2Fs12879-017-2506-6&partnerID=40&md5=ed94c8a29c9ed7cde86c5b093aacf7f7>

277) DOCUMENT TYPE: Article

OPEN ACCESS: ALL OPEN ACCESS; GOLD OPEN ACCESS; GREEN FINAL OPEN ACCESS; GREEN OPEN ACCESS

M., Cristina, Maria, J.X., Velasco-Hernández, Jorge X., K., Min, Kyung-duk, D.G., Leonel, Deise Galan, D., Baca-Carrasco, David, M.E., Gompper, Matthew Edzart, R.A., Hartskeerl, Rudy A., C.A., Muñoz-Zanzi, Claudia A.

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57711639600; 6603918524; 57194494795; 57194497919; 56809311700; 6701362520; 7003778876; 6602544065

The use of chemoprophylaxis after floods to reduce the occurrence and impact of leptospirosis outbreaks

(2017) International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health, 14 (6), art. no. 594

DOI: 10.3390/ijerph14060594

<https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85020460537&doi=10.3390%2Fijerph14060594&partnerID=40&md5=a03bd0fdcc39b29a658ec05f0e0cd58c>

278) DOCUMENT TYPE: Article

OPEN ACCESS: ALL OPEN ACCESS; GOLD OPEN ACCESS; GREEN ACCEPTED OPEN ACCESS; GREEN FINAL OPEN ACCESS; GREEN OPEN ACCESS

B.K., Bett, Bernard K., M.Y., Said, Mohammed Yahya, R.C., Sang, Rosemary C., S.A., Bukachi, Salome Atieno, S., Wanyoike, Salome, S.C., Kifugo, Shem Chege, F.T., Otieno, Fredrick Tom, E.M., Ontiri, Enoch M., I.J., Njeru, Ian J., J.F., Lindahl, Johanna Frida

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36132872400; 15745984700; 6701697241; 6507722951; 56052240900; 36465135600; 36448415600; 56627015400; 55886456900; 56754299200

Effects of flood irrigation on the risk of selected zoonotic pathogens in an arid and semi-arid area in the eastern Kenya

(2017) PLOS ONE, 12 (5), art. no. e0172626

DOI: 10.1371/journal.pone.0172626

<https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85020035885&doi=10.1371%2Fjournal.pone.0172626&partnerID=40&md5=974ecff2497d93470a5923dbaf03505e>

279) DOCUMENT TYPE: Article

OPEN ACCESS: ALL OPEN ACCESS; GOLD OPEN ACCESS; GREEN ACCEPTED OPEN ACCESS; GREEN FINAL OPEN ACCESS; GREEN OPEN ACCESS

M., Kirs, Marek, P.S., Moravcik, Philip S., P., Gyawali, Pradip, K.A., Hamilton, Kerry A., V., Kisand, Veljo, I., Gurr, Ian, C.K., Shuler, Christopher K., W., Ahmed, Warish
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24332025100; 6603836503; 56035719200; 56076127500; 7004348076; 57193763664; 57193763836; 8709269900

Rainwater harvesting in American Samoa: current practices and indicative health risks (2017) Environmental Science and Pollution Research, 24 (13), pp. 12384 - 12392

DOI: 10.1007/s11356-017-8858-z

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[85016429803&doi=10.1007%2Fs11356-017-8858-](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85016429803&doi=10.1007%2Fs11356-017-8858-z&partnerID=40&md5=234f98e84ead3aa9918584d3dd76e9ae)

[z&partnerID=40&md5=234f98e84ead3aa9918584d3dd76e9ae](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85016429803&doi=10.1007%2Fs11356-017-8858-z&partnerID=40&md5=234f98e84ead3aa9918584d3dd76e9ae)

280) DOCUMENT TYPE: Article

A.M., White, Allison M., C.M., Zambrana-Torrel, Carlos M., T., Allen, Toph, M.K., Rostal, Melinda K., A.K., Wright, Andrea K., E.C., Ball, Eileen C., P., Daszak, Peter, W.B., Karesh, William B.

AUTHOR FULL NAMES: White, Allison M. (57193230798); Zambrana-Torrel, Carlos M. (14020715600); Allen, Toph (56902165500); Rostal, Melinda K. (24482404300); Wright, Andrea K. (57193933947); Ball, Eileen C. (57192102858); Daszak, Peter (7003646071); Karesh, William B. (55990995700)

57193230798; 14020715600; 56902165500; 24482404300; 57193933947; 57192102858; 7003646071; 55990995700

Hotspots of canine leptospirosis in the United States of America

(2017) Veterinary Journal, 222, pp. 29 - 35

DOI: 10.1016/j.tvjl.2017.02.009

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[85017535008&doi=10.1016%2Fj.tvjl.2017.02.009&partnerID=40&md5=a40854897ce973742b66414bb5b0f263](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85017535008&doi=10.1016%2Fj.tvjl.2017.02.009&partnerID=40&md5=a40854897ce973742b66414bb5b0f263)

281) DOCUMENT TYPE: Article

OPEN ACCESS: ALL OPEN ACCESS; HYBRID GOLD OPEN ACCESS

J., Habuš, Josipa, Z., Peršić, Zdenka, S., Špičić, Silvio, S., Vince, Silvijo, Z., Štritof, Zrinka, Z., Milas, Zoran, Ž., Cvetnić, Željko, M., Perharić, Matko, N., Turk, Nenad

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32867636100; 18233796000; 8355287700; 14032448800; 6504399208; 6603563721; 55908011000; 55735600800; 6701454963

32867636100; 18233796000; 8355287700; 14032448800; 6504399208; 6603563721;
55908011000; 55735600800; 6701454963
New trends in human and animal leptospirosis in Croatia, 2009–2014
(2017) *Acta Tropica*, 168, pp. 1 - 8
DOI: 10.1016/j.actatropica.2017.01.002
<https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85008622525&doi=10.1016%2Fj.actatropica.2017.01.002&partnerID=40&md5=40a77221284f989d5bbdc2f5c69e7c39>

282) DOCUMENT TYPE: Article

L.F.L., Correia, Lucas Francisco L., A.P.P., Loureiro, Ana Paula Pereira, W., Lilenbaum, Walter
AUTHOR FULL NAMES: Correia, Lucas Francisco L. (57193250806); Loureiro, Ana Paula Pereira (55693710600); Lilenbaum, Walter (56235293200)
57193250806; 55693710600; 56235293200
Effects of rainfall on incidental and host-maintained leptospiral infections in cattle in a tropical region
(2017) *Veterinary Journal*, 220, pp. 63 - 64
DOI: 10.1016/j.tvjl.2016.12.016
<https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85011965726&doi=10.1016%2Fj.tvjl.2016.12.016&partnerID=40&md5=935be22493f81c3ccf698382fe6a9e30>

283) DOCUMENT TYPE: Article

A.N., Zolotokrylin, Alexander Nikolaevich, E.A., Cherenkova, E. A.
AUTHOR FULL NAMES: Zolotokrylin, Alexander Nikolaevich (6701605831); Cherenkova, E. A. (22956908700)
6701605831; 22956908700
Seasonal changes in precipitation extremes in russia for the last several decades and their impact on vital activities of the human population
(2017) *Geography, Environment, Sustainability*, 10 (4), pp. 69 - 82
DOI: 10.24057/2071-9388-2017-10-4-69-82
<https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85040035049&doi=10.24057%2F2071-9388-2017-10-4-69-82&partnerID=40&md5=84ba5c20c6f87d9b8dfb43abaa002b72>

284) DOCUMENT TYPE: Article

OPEN ACCESS: ALL OPEN ACCESS; GOLD OPEN ACCESS; GREEN ACCEPTED OPEN ACCESS; GREEN OPEN ACCESS

M.S., Ruiz-Díaz, María Stephany, G., Mora-García, Gustavo, G.I., Salgado-Madrid, Germán Israel, A., Alario, Ángelo, D.E., Gómez-Camargo, Doris Esther
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55611593700; 59157876600; 55611526900; 56105342100; 53982777400

Analysis of health indicators in two rural communities on the Colombian Caribbean coast: Poor water supply and education level are associated with water-related diseases (2017) *American Journal of Tropical Medicine and Hygiene*, 97 (5), pp. 1378 - 1392
DOI: 10.4269/ajtmh.16-0305

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[85034071568&doi=10.4269%2Fajtmh.16-](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85034071568&doi=10.4269%2Fajtmh.16-0305&partnerID=40&md5=f25e92dbdccc9c6bf481088d218c8753)

[0305&partnerID=40&md5=f25e92dbdccc9c6bf481088d218c8753](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85034071568&doi=10.4269%2Fajtmh.16-0305&partnerID=40&md5=f25e92dbdccc9c6bf481088d218c8753)

285) DOCUMENT TYPE: Article

OPEN ACCESS: ALL OPEN ACCESS; BRONZE OPEN ACCESS; GREEN FINAL OPEN ACCESS; GREEN OPEN ACCESS

P., Hernández-Rodríguez, Patricia, A.P., Gómez, A. Patricia, L.C., Villamil-Jimenez, Luis Carlos

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36625778700; 57225666605; 6603204027

Implications of urban and rural agricultural practices on the transmission of leptospirosis Implicaciones de las prácticas agropecuarias urbanas Y rurales sobre la transmisión de la leptospirosis

(2017) *Agrociencia*, 51 (7), pp. 725 - 741

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[85032463468&partnerID=40&md5=65d29c0d692ebd9e5a77ca268b67ca41](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85032463468&partnerID=40&md5=65d29c0d692ebd9e5a77ca268b67ca41)

286) DOCUMENT TYPE: Article

A., Sumi, Ayako, E.F.O., Telan, Elizabeth Freda Omengan, H., Chagan-Yasutan, Haorile, M.B., Piolo, M. B., T., Hattori, Toshio, N., Kobayashi, Nobumichi

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Hattori, Toshio (56649515200); Kobayashi, Nobumichi (7404310750)

7005095121; 26768418300; 34879448100; 57191096481; 56649515200; 7404310750

Effect of temperature, relative humidity and rainfall on dengue fever and leptospirosis infections in Manila, the Philippines

(2017) *Epidemiology and Infection*, 145 (1), pp. 78 - 86

DOI: 10.1017/S095026881600203X

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[84986563141&doi=10.1017%2FS095026881600203X&partnerID=40&md5=838b5ec8a36bf6d1cbc4bd675cd5830](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-84986563141&doi=10.1017%2FS095026881600203X&partnerID=40&md5=838b5ec8a36bf6d1cbc4bd675cd5830)

287) DOCUMENT TYPE: Article

OPEN ACCESS: ALL OPEN ACCESS; BRONZE OPEN ACCESS; GREEN FINAL OPEN ACCESS; GREEN OPEN ACCESS

P., Widayani, Prima, T., Gunawan, Totok, P., Danoedoro, Projo, S.J., Mardihusodo, Sugeng Juwono

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Application of geographically weighted regression for vulnerable area mapping of leptospirosis in Bantul District

(2016) Indonesian Journal of Geography, 48 (2), pp. 168 - 177

DOI: 10.22146/ijg.17601

[https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85011025190&doi=10.22146%2Fijg.17601&partnerID=40&md5=6c6dee04e8c69b41d64f98a3a3a8d8d6)

[85011025190&doi=10.22146%2Fijg.17601&partnerID=40&md5=6c6dee04e8c69b41d64f98a3a3a8d8d6](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85011025190&doi=10.22146%2Fijg.17601&partnerID=40&md5=6c6dee04e8c69b41d64f98a3a3a8d8d6)

288) DOCUMENT TYPE: Article

OPEN ACCESS: ALL OPEN ACCESS; GOLD OPEN ACCESS

N.V., Gonçalves, Nélon Veiga, E.N.D., Araújo, Ediane Nunes De, A.D.S., Sousa Júnior, Alcinês Da Silva, W.M.M., Pereira, Waltair Maria Martins, C., do Socorro Carvalho Miranda, Cláudia, P.S.D.S., Campos, Pedro Silvestre Da S., M.W.D.S., Matos, Mauro Wendel De Souza, V.R.D.C.M., Palácios, Vera Regina Da Cunha Menezes

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Leptospirosis space-time distribution and risk factors in Belém, Pará, Brazil

Distribuição espaço-temporal da leptospirose e fatores de risco em Belém, Pará, Brasil

(2016) Ciencia e Saude Coletiva, 21 (12), pp. 3947 - 3955

DOI: 10.1590/1413-812320152112.07022016

[https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85005973826&doi=10.1590%2F1413-812320152112.07022016&partnerID=40&md5=230d08e3d98dec541a9e1e88f793794a)

[85005973826&doi=10.1590%2F1413-](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85005973826&doi=10.1590%2F1413-812320152112.07022016&partnerID=40&md5=230d08e3d98dec541a9e1e88f793794a)

[812320152112.07022016&partnerID=40&md5=230d08e3d98dec541a9e1e88f793794a](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85005973826&doi=10.1590%2F1413-812320152112.07022016&partnerID=40&md5=230d08e3d98dec541a9e1e88f793794a)

289) DOCUMENT TYPE: Article

OPEN ACCESS: ALL OPEN ACCESS; GOLD OPEN ACCESS; GREEN ACCEPTED

OPEN ACCESS; GREEN FINAL OPEN ACCESS; GREEN OPEN ACCESS

L.R., Londe, Luciana R., R.S., da Conceição, Rodrigo Silva, T., Bernardes, Tiago, M.C.D.A., Dias, Mariane Carvalho De Assis

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Flood-related leptospirosis outbreaks in Brazil: perspectives for a joint monitoring by health services and disaster monitoring centers

(2016) *Natural Hazards*, 84 (2), pp. 1419 - 1435

DOI: 10.1007/s11069-016-2493-8

[https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-84982984300&doi=10.1007%2Fs11069-016-2493-8&partnerID=40&md5=8424e7091bfe13b97603828b6c44e2cb)

[84982984300&doi=10.1007%2Fs11069-016-2493-](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-84982984300&doi=10.1007%2Fs11069-016-2493-8&partnerID=40&md5=8424e7091bfe13b97603828b6c44e2cb)

[8&partnerID=40&md5=8424e7091bfe13b97603828b6c44e2cb](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-84982984300&doi=10.1007%2Fs11069-016-2493-8&partnerID=40&md5=8424e7091bfe13b97603828b6c44e2cb)

290) DOCUMENT TYPE: Article

A.S., Vieira, Anahí Souto, L., Narduche, Lorena, G.M.D.S., Martins, Gabriel Mendes De Souza, I.A.H.F., Schabib Péres, Igor Alexandre Hany Fuzeta, N.P., Zimmermann, Namor Pinheiro, R.S., Juliano, Raquel Soares, A.O., Pellegrin, Aiesca Oliveira, W., Lilenbaum, Walter

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36191386000; 56423703500; 25959265200; 57190736179; 56382116200; 21740463700; 6603622747; 56235293200

Detection of wild animals as carriers of *Leptospira* by PCR in the Pantanal biome, Brazil

(2016) *Acta Tropica*, 163, pp. 87 - 89

DOI: 10.1016/j.actatropica.2016.08.001

[https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-84982843386&doi=10.1016%2Fj.actatropica.2016.08.001&partnerID=40&md5=f5de45b808186907b36c061fee43d199)

[84982843386&doi=10.1016%2Fj.actatropica.2016.08.001&partnerID=40&md5=f5de45b808186907b36c061fee43d199](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-84982843386&doi=10.1016%2Fj.actatropica.2016.08.001&partnerID=40&md5=f5de45b808186907b36c061fee43d199)

291) DOCUMENT TYPE: Article

V.A., Barragán, Verónica Alexandra, J., Chiriboga, Jorge, E.B., Miller, Erin B., S.M., Olivas, Sonora M., D.N., Birdsell, Dawn N., C.M., Hepp, Crystal M., H.M., Hornstra, Heidie M., J.M., Schupp, James M., M., Morales, Melba, M.A., Gonzalez-Gonzalez, Manuel A.

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24767738100; 56404471200; 57191614607; 56080125600; 26530764900; 57215223927; 16238600200; 7007032883; 56966108400; 57200506307

High *Leptospira* Diversity in Animals and Humans Complicates the Search for Common Reservoirs of Human Disease in Rural Ecuador

(2016) *PLOS Neglected Tropical Diseases*, 10 (9), art. no. e0004990

DOI: 10.1371/journal.pntd.0004990

<https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-84992092127&doi=10.1371%2Fjournal.pntd.0004990&partnerID=40&md5=887b7c30b6a70f9ede7e0e3997a8716d>

292) DOCUMENT TYPE: Article

OPEN ACCESS: ALL OPEN ACCESS; GOLD OPEN ACCESS; GREEN ACCEPTED OPEN ACCESS; GREEN FINAL OPEN ACCESS; GREEN OPEN ACCESS

C., Van Dijck, Christophe, M.J.A., van Esbroeck, Marjan J.A., R., Rutsaert, Robert
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6507970927; 12753496000; 57213365416

A 54-year-old Philippine sailor with fever and jaundice
(2016) *Acta Clinica Belgica: International Journal of Clinical and Laboratory Medicine*, 71 (5), pp. 319 - 322

DOI: 10.1080/17843286.2015.1105606

<https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-84988530867&doi=10.1080%2F17843286.2015.1105606&partnerID=40&md5=50a8f8825011fbdad462b8483344a4cb>

293) DOCUMENT TYPE: Article

S.B., Agampodi, Suneth Buddhika, N.J., Dahanayaka, Niroshana Jathun, K., Nöckler, Karsten, A., Mayer-Scholl, Anne, J.M., Vinetz, Joseph M.
AUTHOR FULL NAMES: Agampodi, Suneth Buddhika (23017863100); Dahanayaka, Niroshana Jathun (54883790800); Nöckler, Karsten (55941959000); Mayer-Scholl, Anne (8105296400); Vinetz, Joseph M. (7003519222)

23017863100; 54883790800; 55941959000; 8105296400; 7003519222

Redefining gold standard testing for diagnosing leptospirosis: Further evidence from a well-characterized, flood-related outbreak in Sri Lanka

(2016) *American Journal of Tropical Medicine and Hygiene*, 95 (3), pp. 531 - 536

DOI: 10.4269/ajtmh.16-0033

<https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-84984796589&doi=10.4269%2Fajtmh.16-0033&partnerID=40&md5=e9d6bf45c4ccffefbfba9177d2d9c2b>

294) DOCUMENT TYPE: Article

OPEN ACCESS: ALL OPEN ACCESS; GREEN FINAL OPEN ACCESS; GREEN OPEN ACCESS

M.L., Sohail, Muhammad Luqman, M.S., Khan, Muhammad Sarwar, M., Avais, Muhammad, M.Y., Zahoor, Muhammad Yasir, M.U., Ijaz, Muhammad Usman, A., Ullah, Aman, Z., Fátima, Zahida, O., Naseer, Omer, I.U.D., Khattak, Irfan Ud Din, S., Ali, Sadaqat

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(55953568800); Fátima, Zahida (36833852200); Naseer, Omer (57189993553); Khattak, Irfan Ud Din (36893522200); Ali, Sadaqat (57199264554)
57205660717; 35078743800; 26631598200; 36683492000; 57221606747; 55953568800;
36833852200; 57189993553; 36893522200; 57199264554
Seroprevalence of *Leptospira* spp. in Horses of Distinct Climatic Regions of Punjab, Pakistan
(2016) *Journal of Equine Veterinary Science*, 44, pp. 82 - 89
DOI: 10.1016/j.jevs.2016.01.007
<https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-84976291643&doi=10.1016%2Fj.jevs.2016.01.007&partnerID=40&md5=696f719965794dfc23c0f1ce5e25c8ff>

295) DOCUMENT TYPE: Article

J., Zhao, Jian, J., Liao, Jishan, X., Huang, Xu, J., Zhao, Jing, Y., Wang, Yeping, J., Ren, Jinghuan, X., Wang, Xiaoye, F., Ding, Fan
AUTHOR FULL NAMES: Zhao, Jian (59847036600); Liao, Jishan (55323141000); Huang, Xu (57198044595); Zhao, Jing (59851057000); Wang, Yeping (57190308988); Ren, Jinghuan (57190294180); Wang, Xiaoye (57192626254); Ding, Fan (57204065568)
59847036600; 55323141000; 57198044595; 59851057000; 57190308988; 57190294180;
57192626254; 57204065568
Mapping risk of leptospirosis in China using environmental and socioeconomic data
(2016) *BMC Infectious Diseases*, 16 (1), art. no. 343
DOI: 10.1186/s12879-016-1653-5
<https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-84978971642&doi=10.1186%2Fs12879-016-1653-5&partnerID=40&md5=f65806f05a68ef305cace23b2414806b>

296) DOCUMENT TYPE: Article

OPEN ACCESS: ALL OPEN ACCESS; GOLD OPEN ACCESS; GREEN ACCEPTED OPEN ACCESS; GREEN FINAL OPEN ACCESS; GREEN OPEN ACCESS

E.U., Andersen-Ranberg, Emilie Ulrikka, C.B., Pipper, Christian Bressen, P.M., Jensen, Per Moestrup
AUTHOR FULL NAMES: Andersen-Ranberg, Emilie Ulrikka (57190392203); Pipper, Christian Bressen (22735054000); Jensen, Per Moestrup (35322280600)
57190392203; 22735054000; 35322280600
Global patterns of *Leptospira* prevalence in vertebrate reservoir hosts
(2016) *Journal of Wildlife Diseases*, 52 (3), pp. 468 - 477
DOI: 10.7589/2014-10-245
<https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-84979678854&doi=10.7589%2F2014-10-245&partnerID=40&md5=f06c07367901692f32ebc5bdc7a88b53>

297) DOCUMENT TYPE: Article

P.C., Parmar, Piyushkumar C., M.H., Momin, Mohmmedirfan H., N.R., Godara, Naresh R., S.L., Kantharia, Shantilal L.

AUTHOR FULL NAMES: Parmar, Piyushkumar C. (57190069020); Momin, Mohmmedirfan H. (36108933400); Godara, Naresh R. (23012182300); Kantharia, Shantilal L. (6507376077)

57190069020; 36108933400; 23012182300; 6507376077

Profile of leptospirosis patients Admitted in tertiary care centre of South Gujarat (2016) Indian Journal of Public Health Research and Development, 7 (3), pp. 288 - 292

DOI: 10.5958/0976-5506.2016.00173.X

[https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-84977079251&doi=10.5958%2F0976-5506.2016.00173.X&partnerID=40&md5=8a0d2062f5d8f39c3f80c51db290ad27)

[84977079251&doi=10.5958%2F0976-](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-84977079251&doi=10.5958%2F0976-5506.2016.00173.X&partnerID=40&md5=8a0d2062f5d8f39c3f80c51db290ad27)

[5506.2016.00173.X&partnerID=40&md5=8a0d2062f5d8f39c3f80c51db290ad27](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-84977079251&doi=10.5958%2F0976-5506.2016.00173.X&partnerID=40&md5=8a0d2062f5d8f39c3f80c51db290ad27)

298) DOCUMENT TYPE: Article

V., Balamurugan, V., S.R.A., Thirumalesh, Sushma Rahim Assadi, R., Sridevi, Rajangam, G., Govindaraj, Gurrappanaidu, M., Nagalingam, Mohandoss, D., Hemadri, Divakar, M.R., Gajendragad, Mukund Raghavendra, M.H., Rahman, Md H.

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6603723706; 55921414600; 36121558900; 56825565300; 54401495200; 6701806131;

6603795418; 57225857366

Microscopic Agglutination Test Analysis Identifies Prevalence of Intermediate Species Serovars in Ruminants in Endemic States of India

(2016) Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences India Section B - Biological Sciences, 86 (2), pp. 469 - 475

DOI: 10.1007/s40011-014-0469-6

[https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-84969645941&doi=10.1007%2Fs40011-014-0469-6&partnerID=40&md5=e0cc05d457c246da4bd79aeff825a9ae)

[84969645941&doi=10.1007%2Fs40011-014-0469-](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-84969645941&doi=10.1007%2Fs40011-014-0469-6&partnerID=40&md5=e0cc05d457c246da4bd79aeff825a9ae)

[6&partnerID=40&md5=e0cc05d457c246da4bd79aeff825a9ae](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-84969645941&doi=10.1007%2Fs40011-014-0469-6&partnerID=40&md5=e0cc05d457c246da4bd79aeff825a9ae)

299) DOCUMENT TYPE: Article

L., Azócar-Aedo, Lucía, G.E., Monti, Gustavo Enrique

AUTHOR FULL NAMES: Azócar-Aedo, Lucía (56375822400); Monti, Gustavo Enrique (8977170000)

56375822400; 8977170000

Meta-Analyses of Factors Associated with Leptospirosis in Domestic Dogs

(2016) Zoonoses and Public Health, 63 (4), pp. 328 - 336

DOI: 10.1111/zph.12236

[https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-84949256425&doi=10.1111%2Fzph.12236&partnerID=40&md5=833f8e199d9ce2958cc70b60e069695f)

[84949256425&doi=10.1111%2Fzph.12236&partnerID=40&md5=833f8e199d9ce2958cc70b60e069695f](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-84949256425&doi=10.1111%2Fzph.12236&partnerID=40&md5=833f8e199d9ce2958cc70b60e069695f)

300) DOCUMENT TYPE: Article

D., Benacer, Douadi, K.L., Thong, Kwai Lin, C., Ng, Choungmin, K.B., Verasahib, Khebir Bin, R.L., Galloway, Renee Lynn, R.A., Hartskeerl, Rudy A., M., Souris, Marc, S.N., Mohd Zain, Siti Nursheena

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36187720400; 35390355100; 36468803200; 55761507700; 7102801269; 7003778876; 15729878600; 55547500500

Epidemiology of human leptospirosis in Malaysia, 2004-2012

(2016) *Acta Tropica*, 157, pp. 162 - 168

DOI: 10.1016/j.actatropica.2016.01.031

[https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-84958243887&doi=10.1016%2Fj.actatropica.2016.01.031&partnerID=40&md5=911d806f1ae685b5fa15b5d19dbd0769)

[84958243887&doi=10.1016%2Fj.actatropica.2016.01.031&partnerID=40&md5=911d806f1ae685b5fa15b5d19dbd0769](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-84958243887&doi=10.1016%2Fj.actatropica.2016.01.031&partnerID=40&md5=911d806f1ae685b5fa15b5d19dbd0769)

301) DOCUMENT TYPE: Article

P., Della Rossa, Pauline, K., Tantrakarnapa, Kraichat, D., Sutdan, Derek, K., Kasetsinsombat, Kitisak, J.F., Cosson, Jean François, Y., Supputamongkol, Yupin, K., Chaisiri, Kittipong, A., Tran, Annelise, S., Supputamongkol, S., A., Binot, Aurélie

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56982940100; 35220859500; 56982937900; 57226161928; 7005908632; 6507147462; 36571515900; 7103072369; 56983081600; 26639119300

Environmental factors and public health policy associated with human and rodent infection by leptospirosis: A land cover-based study in Nan province, Thailand

(2016) *Epidemiology and Infection*, 144 (7), pp. 1550 - 1562

DOI: 10.1017/S0950268815002903

[https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-84948660390&doi=10.1017%2FS0950268815002903&partnerID=40&md5=e20c7324e07661d431ee79a9ddc16752)

[84948660390&doi=10.1017%2FS0950268815002903&partnerID=40&md5=e20c7324e07661d431ee79a9ddc16752](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-84948660390&doi=10.1017%2FS0950268815002903&partnerID=40&md5=e20c7324e07661d431ee79a9ddc16752)

302) DOCUMENT TYPE: Article

OPEN ACCESS: ALL OPEN ACCESS; BRONZE OPEN ACCESS; GREEN FINAL OPEN ACCESS; GREEN OPEN ACCESS

S.E., Grayzel, Sharon E., E.E., DeBess, Emilio E.

AUTHOR FULL NAMES: Grayzel, Sharon E. (56565434600); DeBess, Emilio E. (6602682669)

56565434600; 6602682669

Characterization of leptospirosis among dogs in Oregon, 2007–2011

(2016) Journal of the American Veterinary Medical Association, 248 (8), pp. 908 - 915
DOI: 10.2460/javma.248.8.908
<https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-84962407114&doi=10.2460%2Fjavma.248.8.908&partnerID=40&md5=76d10232a827070acdbedd3a28f887ea>

303) DOCUMENT TYPE: Article

L., Gao, Lu, Y., Zhang, Ying, G., Ding, Guoyong, Q., Liu, Qiyong, B., Jiang, Baofa
AUTHOR FULL NAMES: Gao, Lu (55760033300); Zhang, Ying (55739776200); Ding, Guoyong (55760272200); Liu, Qiyong (55616174300); Jiang, Baofa (8607835500) 55760033300; 55739776200; 55760272200; 55616174300; 8607835500
Identifying flood-related infectious diseases in Anhui Province, China: A spatial and temporal analysis
(2016) American Journal of Tropical Medicine and Hygiene, 94 (4), pp. 741 - 749
DOI: 10.4269/ajtmh.15-0338
<https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-84963644273&doi=10.4269%2Fajtmh.15-0338&partnerID=40&md5=96c37f43b587e22f72f8b88331b285c4>

304) DOCUMENT TYPE: Article

OPEN ACCESS: ALL OPEN ACCESS; GREEN FINAL OPEN ACCESS; GREEN OPEN ACCESS

K., Vinod Kumar, K., C., Lall, Chandan, R., Vimal Raj, Ratchagadasse, K., Vedhagiri, Kumaresan, P., Vijayachari, Paluru
AUTHOR FULL NAMES: Vinod Kumar, K. (56993304700); Lall, Chandan (56699848300); Vimal Raj, Ratchagadasse (56700228800); Vedhagiri, Kumaresan (25923151200); Vijayachari, Paluru (6601955151) 56993304700; 56699848300; 56700228800; 25923151200; 6601955151
Molecular detection of pathogenic leptospiral protein encoding gene (lipL32) in environmental aquatic biofilms
(2016) Letters in Applied Microbiology, 62 (4), pp. 311 - 315
DOI: 10.1111/lam.12533
<https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-84962511223&doi=10.1111%2Flam.12533&partnerID=40&md5=05f6172e4541760ee74c7c872c2afc64>

305) DOCUMENT TYPE: Article

OPEN ACCESS: ALL OPEN ACCESS; BRONZE OPEN ACCESS

L., Suryani, Lilis, H., Pramoedyo, Henny, Sudarto, S., Andarini, Sri
AUTHOR FULL NAMES: Suryani, Lilis (57219694941); Pramoedyo, Henny (57189002977); Sudarto (57199627627); Andarini, Sri (57188996572) 57219694941; 57189002977; 57199627627; 57188996572
The spread pattern and various risk factors of human leptospirosis in Yogyakarta, Indonesia

(2016) Journal of Pure and Applied Microbiology, 10 (1), pp. 11 - 16
<https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-84964576035&partnerID=40&md5=530b6402120a38a92c0d248876578128>

306) DOCUMENT TYPE: Article

C.L., Lau, Colleen L., C.H., Watson, Conall H., J.H., Lowry, John H., M.C., David, Michael C., S.B., Craig, Scott Benjamin, S.J., Prior, Sarah Jane, M., Kama, Mike, E.J., Nilles, Eric J.

AUTHOR FULL NAMES: Lau, Colleen L. (57002151900); Watson, Conall H. (57202556038); Lowry, John H. (58602960300); David, Michael C. (55313533800); Craig, Scott Benjamin (7201656455); Prior, Sarah Jane (57200657503); Kama, Mike (55232631100); Nilles, Eric J. (16643480100)
57002151900; 57202556038; 58602960300; 55313533800; 7201656455; 57200657503; 55232631100; 16643480100

Human Leptospirosis Infection in Fiji: An Eco-epidemiological Approach to Identifying Risk Factors and Environmental Drivers for Transmission

(2016) PLOS Neglected Tropical Diseases, 10 (1), art. no. e0004405

DOI: 10.1371/journal.pntd.0004405

[https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-84961366849&doi=10.1371%2Fjournal.pntd.0004405&partnerID=40&md5=0f6f3212c1b9ca31e3341ae3fd7034fa)

[84961366849&doi=10.1371%2Fjournal.pntd.0004405&partnerID=40&md5=0f6f3212c1b9ca31e3341ae3fd7034fa](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-84961366849&doi=10.1371%2Fjournal.pntd.0004405&partnerID=40&md5=0f6f3212c1b9ca31e3341ae3fd7034fa)

307) DOCUMENT TYPE: Article

OPEN ACCESS: ALL OPEN ACCESS; GOLD OPEN ACCESS; GREEN ACCEPTED OPEN ACCESS; GREEN FINAL OPEN ACCESS; GREEN OPEN ACCESS

N.G., Gloriani, Nina Gonzales, S.Y.A.M., Villanueva, Sharon Yvette Angelina M., Y., Yanagihara, Yasutake, S., Yoshida, Shinichi

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36080339500; 7004327679; 35515355800; 35449620400

Post-flooding surveillance of leptospirosis after the onslaught of typhoons Nesat, Nalgae and Washi in the Philippines

(2016) Southeast Asian Journal of Tropical Medicine and Public Health, 47 (4), pp. 774 - 786

[https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85024503636&partnerID=40&md5=8018bb8dc639bb4b7d8abd5b8e17f699)

[85024503636&partnerID=40&md5=8018bb8dc639bb4b7d8abd5b8e17f699](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85024503636&partnerID=40&md5=8018bb8dc639bb4b7d8abd5b8e17f699)

308) DOCUMENT TYPE: Article

I.S., Christova, Iva S., E.I., Tasseva, Evgenia I.

AUTHOR FULL NAMES: Christova, Iva S. (54790583700); Tasseva, Evgenia I. (6505914969)

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Human leptospirosis in Bulgaria, 2010-2014

(2016) Problems of Infectious and Parasitic Diseases, 44 (2), pp. 23 - 29
<https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85018203222&partnerID=40&md5=b04c22a12dbc502a215edba17229fee1>

309) DOCUMENT TYPE: Article

E.A., Roxas, Evalyn Alarkon, M.M., Alejandría, Marissa M., M.T., Mendoza, Myrna T., A.D.E., Roman, Arthur Dessi E., K.T., Leyritana, Katerina T., J.K.B., Ginete-Garcia, Joann Kathleen B.

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55970672400; 14630139000; 7101729281; 55970231200; 55247411700; 57193947755

Leptospirosis outbreak after a heavy rainfall typhoon in the Philippines: Clinical features, outcome and prognostic factors for mortality

(2016) Acta Medica Philippina, 50 (3), pp. 121 - 128

<https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85017622314&partnerID=40&md5=c0c65f123acc93265b036b4d7223c43d>

85017622314&partnerID=40&md5=c0c65f123acc93265b036b4d7223c43d

310) DOCUMENT TYPE: Article

J.P., Guevarra, Jonathan P., M.P., Borja, Maridel P., N.G., Gloriani, Nina Gonzales, R.M., Napulan, Roderick M., S., Yoshida, Shinichi

AUTHOR FULL NAMES: Guevarra, Jonathan P. (56076826900); Borja, Maridel P. (54787348300); Gloriani, Nina Gonzales (36080339500); Napulan, Roderick M. (57193953689); Yoshida, Shinichi (35449620400)

56076826900; 54787348300; 36080339500; 57193953689; 35449620400

Knowledge, attitudes and practices of the community residents concerning the prevention and control of Leptospirosis in the National Capital Region (NCR), Philippines

(2016) Acta Medica Philippina, 50 (3), pp. 129 - 135

<https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85017592693&partnerID=40&md5=d5daffa6308f69c3507e1b075771b887>

85017592693&partnerID=40&md5=d5daffa6308f69c3507e1b075771b887

311) DOCUMENT TYPE: Article

C.R., Oliveira, Carlos R., G.S.R., Costa, Gisela S.R., I.A.D., Paploski, Igor Adolfo Dexheimer, M., Kikuti, Mariana, A.M., Kasper, Amelia M., M.M.O., Silva, Monaíse Madalena Oliveira, A.S., Tavares, Aline S., J.S., Cruz, Jaqueline Silva, T.L., Queiroz, Tássia L., H.C.A.V., Lima, Helena Cristina Alves Vieira

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57189964945; 57192870904; 37071101000; 54414303300; 56767789700; 55467658100;
56767660400; 56767538800; 56588783700; 35759162900

Influenza-like illness in an urban community of Salvador, Brazil: Incidence, seasonality
and risk factors

(2016) BMC Infectious Diseases, 16 (1), art. no. 125

DOI: 10.1186/s12879-016-1456-8

[https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85008489952&doi=10.1186%2Fs12879-016-1456-8&partnerID=40&md5=b09caade83f4e6a1ef0354ddbe333b3b)

85008489952&doi=10.1186%2Fs12879-016-1456-

8&partnerID=40&md5=b09caade83f4e6a1ef0354ddbe333b3b

312) DOCUMENT TYPE: Article

OPEN ACCESS: ALL OPEN ACCESS; GOLD OPEN ACCESS; GREEN FINAL OPEN
ACCESS; GREEN OPEN ACCESS

M., Sato, Mari, Y., Nakamura, Yasuka, F., Atogami, Fumi, R., Horiguchi, Ribeka, R.,
Tamaki, Raita, T., Yoshizawa, Toyoko, H., Oshitani, Hitoshi

AUTHOR FULL NAMES: Sato, Mari (12782174400); Nakamura, Yasuka (55487623600);

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12782174400; 55487623600; 6507037859; 57147549400; 36784738300; 7202636093;

57202772650

Immediate needs and concerns among pregnant women during and after typhoon
haiyan (Yolanda)

(2016) PLoS Currents, 8 (DISASTERS)

DOI: 10.1371/currents.dis.29e4c0c810db47d7fd8d0d1fb782892c

[https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-84959432936&doi=10.1371%2Fcurrents.dis.29e4c0c810db47d7fd8d0d1fb782892c&partnerID=40&md5=8e9bc9b91e760d726db6fe791b1bc045)

84959432936&doi=10.1371%2Fcurrents.dis.29e4c0c810db47d7fd8d0d1fb782892c&partne

rID=40&md5=8e9bc9b91e760d726db6fe791b1bc045

313) DOCUMENT TYPE: Article

OPEN ACCESS: ALL OPEN ACCESS; GOLD OPEN ACCESS; GREEN ACCEPTED
OPEN ACCESS; GREEN FINAL OPEN ACCESS; GREEN OPEN ACCESS

E., Jensen-Jarolim, Erika

AUTHOR FULL NAMES: Jensen-Jarolim, Erika (7003817550)

7003817550

Aluminium in Allergies and Allergen immunotherapy

(2015) World Allergy Organization Journal, 8 (1), art. no. 60

DOI: 10.1186/s40413-015-0060-5

[https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-84928750939&doi=10.1186%2Fs40413-015-0060-5&partnerID=40&md5=344ba68cd27ffde417a15a4c6c35316e)

84928750939&doi=10.1186%2Fs40413-015-0060-

5&partnerID=40&md5=344ba68cd27ffde417a15a4c6c35316e

314) DOCUMENT TYPE: Article

OPEN ACCESS: ALL OPEN ACCESS; GOLD OPEN ACCESS; GREEN FINAL OPEN
ACCESS; GREEN OPEN ACCESS

M., Lélou, Maud, C.A., Muñoz-Zanzi, Claudia A., B., Higgins, Brooke, R.L., Galloway, Renee Lynn

AUTHOR FULL NAMES: Lélou, Maud (36127653400); Muñoz-Zanzi, Claudia A. (6602544065); Higgins, Brooke (56609877200); Galloway, Renee Lynn (7102801269) 36127653400; 6602544065; 56609877200; 7102801269

Seroepidemiology of leptospirosis in dogs from rural and slum communities of Los Rios Region, Chile

(2015) BMC Veterinary Research, 11 (1), art. no. 31

DOI: 10.1186/s12917-015-0341-9

[https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-84928654711&doi=10.1186%2Fs12917-015-0341-9&partnerID=40&md5=2046f20c0b1a37d1ca406528a63291f5)

84928654711&doi=10.1186%2Fs12917-015-0341-

9&partnerID=40&md5=2046f20c0b1a37d1ca406528a63291f5

315) 3DOCUMENT TYPE: Article

OPEN ACCESS: ALL OPEN ACCESS; GOLD OPEN ACCESS; GREEN FINAL OPEN ACCESS; GREEN OPEN ACCESS

H.Y., Yang, Huang Yu, C., Hung, Chengchieh, S., Liu, Suhsun, Y., Guo, Yigen, Y., Chen, Yungchang, Y., Ko, Yiching, C., Huang, Chiungtseng, L., Chou, Lifang, Y., Tian, Yachung, M.Y., Chang, M. Y.

AUTHOR FULL NAMES: Yang, Huang Yu (54390408000); Hung, Chengchieh (8266357600); Liu, Suhsun (55694046700); Guo, Yigen (57138829600); Chen, Yungchang (55721061700); Ko, Yiching (15733061000); Huang, Chiungtseng (57212180051); Chou, Lifang (36924249100); Tian, Yachung (7402840520); Chang, M. Y. (7404504561) 54390408000; 8266357600; 55694046700; 57138829600; 55721061700; 15733061000; 57212180051; 36924249100; 7402840520; 7404504561

Overlooked Risk for Chronic Kidney Disease after Leptospiral Infection: A Population-Based Survey and Epidemiological Cohort Evidence

(2015) PLOS Neglected Tropical Diseases, 9 (10), art. no. e0004105

DOI: 10.1371/journal.pntd.0004105

[https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-84959075399&doi=10.1371%2Fjournal.pntd.0004105&partnerID=40&md5=3d900b02f2f15f8f069107778813fd21)

84959075399&doi=10.1371%2Fjournal.pntd.0004105&partnerID=40&md5=3d900b02f2f15f8f069107778813fd21

316) DOCUMENT TYPE: Article

OPEN ACCESS: ALL OPEN ACCESS; GOLD OPEN ACCESS; GREEN ACCEPTED OPEN ACCESS; GREEN FINAL OPEN ACCESS; GREEN OPEN ACCESS

G., Dobigny, Gauthier, M., Garba, Madougou, C., Tatard, Caroline, A., Loiseau, Anne, M., Galan, Max, I., Kadaouré, Ibrahima, J.P., Rossi, Jean Pierre, M., Picardeau, Mathieu, E.G.G., Bertherat, Eric Gerard Georges

AUTHOR FULL NAMES: Dobigny, Gauthier (6701314349); Garba, Madougou (56175512200); Tatard, Caroline (23487054100); Loiseau, Anne (7006519840); Galan, Max (57213790100); Kadaouré, Ibrahima (6504409945); Rossi, Jean Pierre (36741558600); Picardeau, Mathieu (6701694004); Bertherat, Eric Gerard Georges (6701390898) 6701314349; 56175512200; 23487054100; 7006519840; 57213790100; 6504409945; 36741558600; 6701694004; 6701390898

Urban Market Gardening and Rodent-Borne Pathogenic *Leptospira* in Arid Zones: A Case Study in Niamey, Niger
(2015) PLOS Neglected Tropical Diseases, 9 (10), art. no. e0004097
DOI: 10.1371/journal.pntd.0004097
<https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-84959153626&doi=10.1371%2Fjournal.pntd.0004097&partnerID=40&md5=22793ae8036c63dccd8e076efb1b7821>

317) DOCUMENT TYPE: Article

OPEN ACCESS: ALL OPEN ACCESS; GOLD OPEN ACCESS; GREEN ACCEPTED OPEN ACCESS; GREEN FINAL OPEN ACCESS; GREEN OPEN ACCESS

M.A., Mwachui, Mwanajaa Abdalla, L., Crump, Lisa, R.A., Hartskeerl, Rudy A., J., Zinsstag, Jakob, J., Hattendorf, Jan
AUTHOR FULL NAMES: Mwachui, Mwanajaa Abdalla (56888677400); Crump, Lisa (55317538800); Hartskeerl, Rudy A. (7003778876); Zinsstag, Jakob (7004623067); Hattendorf, Jan (13808305100)
56888677400; 55317538800; 7003778876; 7004623067; 13808305100
Environmental and Behavioural Determinants of Leptospirosis Transmission: A Systematic Review
(2015) PLOS Neglected Tropical Diseases, 9 (9), art. no. e0003843
DOI: 10.1371/journal.pntd.0003843
<https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-84943196151&doi=10.1371%2Fjournal.pntd.0003843&partnerID=40&md5=fde650f81e0bcd5e3b9899c396892d00>

318) DOCUMENT TYPE: Article

OPEN ACCESS: ALL OPEN ACCESS; GOLD OPEN ACCESS; GREEN ACCEPTED OPEN ACCESS; GREEN FINAL OPEN ACCESS; GREEN OPEN ACCESS

B., Miklausic-Pavic, Bozana, N., Pandak, Nenad, I., Čabraja, Ivica, M., Šiško, Marijan
AUTHOR FULL NAMES: Miklausic-Pavic, Bozana (54407069900); Pandak, Nenad (6506008185); Čabraja, Ivica (24068352500); Šiško, Marijan (24069326000)
54407069900; 6506008185; 24068352500; 24069326000
The effects of climate elements on the incidence of leptospirosis in Brod – Posavina County
Učejak klimatskih elemenata na pojavnost leptospiroze u Brodsko-posavskoj županiji
(2015) Infektoloski Glasnik, 35 (2-3), pp. 67 - 73
<https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-84960090509&partnerID=40&md5=d8bc5a005be9a01caabaa601a038005e>

319) DOCUMENT TYPE: Article

J.H., Diaz, James Henry
AUTHOR FULL NAMES: Diaz, James Henry (57214434480)
57214434480

Rodent-borne infectious disease outbreaks after flooding disasters: Epidemiology, management, and prevention
(2015) Journal of Emergency Management, 13 (5), pp. 459 - 467
DOI: 10.5055/jem.2015.0255
<https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-84947067085&doi=10.5055%2Fjem.2015.0255&partnerID=40&md5=ee8d165d419c11c8c9d116c15b10f3af>

320) DOCUMENT TYPE: Article

N., Issa, Nahéma, O., Guisset, Olivier, G., Mourissoux, Gaëlle, C., Gabinski, Claude, F., Camou, Fabrice
AUTHOR FULL NAMES: Issa, Nahéma (55443884800); Guisset, Olivier (12140635000); Mourissoux, Gaëlle (35196581800); Gabinski, Claude (6602167644); Camou, Fabrice (6506520205)
55443884800; 12140635000; 35196581800; 6602167644; 6506520205
Leptospirosis and thrombocytopenia Leptospirose et thrombopénie
(2015) Revue de Medecine Interne, 36 (8), pp. 558 - 560
DOI: 10.1016/j.revmed.2014.10.358
<https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-84937736591&doi=10.1016%2Fj.revmed.2014.10.358&partnerID=40&md5=9a1b9ea735019743785cd540637fb4eb>

321) DOCUMENT TYPE: Article

S., Sánchez-Montes, Sokani, D.V., Espinosa-Martínez, Deborah Veranea, C.A., Ríos-Muñoz, César A., M., Berzunza-Cruz, Miriam, I.D., Becker, Ingeborg D.
AUTHOR FULL NAMES: Sánchez-Montes, Sokani (55917375000); Espinosa-Martínez, Deborah Veranea (56611965900); Ríos-Muñoz, César A. (23052226200); Berzunza-Cruz, Miriam (55993709000); Becker, Ingeborg D. (7006656913)
55917375000; 56611965900; 23052226200; 55993709000; 7006656913
Leptospirosis in Mexico: Epidemiology and potential distribution of human cases
(2015) PLOS ONE, 10 (7), art. no. e0133720
DOI: 10.1371/journal.pone.0133720
<https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-84941975727&doi=10.1371%2Fjournal.pone.0133720&partnerID=40&md5=b900597da64d0fa232368a6bd07ca3e5>

322) DOCUMENT TYPE: Article

J.J., Waggoner, Jesse J., I.T., Balassiano, Ilana Teruszkin, A., Mohamed-Hadley, Alisha, J.M., Vital-Brazil, Juliana Magalhães, M.K., Sahoo, Malaya K., B.A., Pinsky, Benjamin A.
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55260327600; 35550353500; 57191606218; 6505797517; 55481515000; 6603375926

Reverse-transcriptase PCR detection of *Leptospira*: Absence of agreement with single-specimen microscopic agglutination testing
(2015) PLOS ONE, 10 (7), art. no. e0132988
DOI: 10.1371/journal.pone.0132988
<https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-84941308405&doi=10.1371%2Fjournal.pone.0132988&partnerID=40&md5=9c646bd92c77f0c25b368c593d98ec10>

323) DOCUMENT TYPE: Article

OPEN ACCESS: ALL OPEN ACCESS; GOLD OPEN ACCESS; GREEN ACCEPTED OPEN ACCESS; GREEN FINAL OPEN ACCESS; GREEN OPEN ACCESS

S., Suwanpakdee, Sarin, J., Kaewkungwal, J., L.J., White, Lisa J., N., Asensio, Norberto, P., Ratanakorn, Parntep, P., Singhasivanon, Pratap, N.P., Day, Nicholas P.J., W., Pan-
Ngum, Wirichada

AUTHOR FULL NAMES: Suwanpakdee, Sarin (26025357000); Kaewkungwal, J. (6701733827); White, Lisa J. (55809735100); Asensio, Norberto (16232567300); Ratanakorn, Parntep (6603353149); Singhasivanon, Pratap (7003665904); Day, Nicholas P.J. (36071528500); Pan-
Ngum, Wirichada (36739433600)
26025357000; 6701733827; 55809735100; 16232567300; 6603353149; 7003665904; 36071528500; 36739433600

Spatio-temporal patterns of leptospirosis in Thailand: Is flooding a risk factor?

(2015) Epidemiology and Infection, 143 (10), pp. 2106 - 2115

DOI: 10.1017/S0950268815000205

<https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-84930755498&doi=10.1017%2FS0950268815000205&partnerID=40&md5=17e3a2104faa3a07bd5e3441489aba1d>

324) DOCUMENT TYPE: Article

OPEN ACCESS: ALL OPEN ACCESS; GREEN FINAL OPEN ACCESS; GREEN OPEN ACCESS; HYBRID GOLD OPEN ACCESS

J., Jang, Jinhwa, J., Lee, Ji-hae, M.K., Je, Mikyeong Kyung, M., Cho, Myeongji, Y., Bae, Youngmee, H., Son, Hyeonseok, I., Ahn, Insung

AUTHOR FULL NAMES: Jang, Jinhwa (56768614700); Lee, Ji-hae (56002577600); Je, Mikyeong Kyung (57205469726); Cho, Myeongji (57203856398); Bae, Youngmee (7201466005); Son, Hyeonseok (7102742272); Ahn, Insung (15020330800)
56768614700; 56002577600; 57205469726; 57203856398; 7201466005; 7102742272; 15020330800

Correlations between the incidence of national notifiable infectious diseases and public open data, including meteorological factors and medical facility resources

(2015) Journal of Preventive Medicine and Public Health, 48 (4), pp. 203 - 215

DOI: 10.3961/jpmph.14.057

<https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-84938865015&doi=10.3961%2Fjpmph.14.057&partnerID=40&md5=5b0ac53acc5a67ea900ece366706c5e1>

325) DOCUMENT TYPE: Article

OPEN ACCESS: ALL OPEN ACCESS; GOLD OPEN ACCESS; GREEN ACCEPTED OPEN ACCESS; GREEN FINAL OPEN ACCESS; GREEN OPEN ACCESS

C.L., Lau, Colleen L., C., Skelly, Chris, M.F., Dohnt, Michael Francis, L.D., Smythe, Lee Douglas

AUTHOR FULL NAMES: Lau, Colleen L. (57002151900); Skelly, Chris (57217186839); Dohnt, Michael Francis (6602081980); Smythe, Lee Douglas (7003482425)

57002151900; 57217186839; 6602081980; 7003482425

The emergence of *Leptospira borgpetersenii* serovar Arborea in Queensland, Australia, 2001 to 2013

(2015) BMC Infectious Diseases, 15 (1), art. no. 230

DOI: 10.1186/s12879-015-0982-0

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84931270785&doi=10.1186%2Fs12879-015-0982-

0&partnerID=40&md5=37f33324b56b9a4dbfa30bd0fc313ecd

326) DOCUMENT TYPE: Article

OPEN ACCESS: ALL OPEN ACCESS; GOLD OPEN ACCESS; GREEN FINAL OPEN ACCESS; GREEN OPEN ACCESS

T.C.L., Benevides, Thais Celi Lopes, F.A., Orsi, Fernanda A., M.P., Colella, Marina Pereira, P.O., Percout, Priscila Oliveira, M.S., Moura, Muriel Silva, M.A., Dias, Maria Almeida, B.D., Lins, Betina Diniz, E.V., De Paula, Erich V., J., Vassallo, Jose, J.M., Annichino-Bizzachi, Joyce Maria

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56576354200; 55403844500; 54892907100; 56576287000; 56576022100; 57581834500; 56576199900; 7005969319; 7005637352; 55664319500

Acquired thrombotic thrombocytopenic purpura due to antibody-mediated

ADAMTS13 deficiency precipitated by a localized Castleman's disease: A case report

(2015) Platelets, 26 (3), pp. 263 - 266

DOI: 10.3109/09537104.2014.904504

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84925946841&doi=10.3109%2F09537104.2014.904504&partnerID=40&md5=5afc837ff5e2a49917fb2e2db4f987ef

327) DOCUMENT TYPE: Article

M.F., Jancloes, Michel F., V., Anderson, Vidya, P.L., Gosselin, Pierre L., C., Mee, Carol, N.J., Chong, Nicholas J.

AUTHOR FULL NAMES: Jancloes, Michel F. (55893417300); Anderson, Vidya

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55893417300; 57192116135; 7006375242; 51665700500; 55922315100
WWOSC 2014: Research needs for better health resilience to weather hazards
(2015) *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 12 (3), pp.
2895 - 2900
DOI: 10.3390/ijerph120302895
<https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-84927544748&doi=10.3390%2Fijerph120302895&partnerID=40&md5=ce72a36133665047023ae36b2eb79fb4>

328) DOCUMENT TYPE: Article

OPEN ACCESS: ALL OPEN ACCESS; GOLD OPEN ACCESS; GREEN ACCEPTED
OPEN ACCESS; GREEN FINAL OPEN ACCESS; GREEN OPEN ACCESS

P., Vilain, Pascal, F., Pagés, Frédéric, X., Combes, Xavier, P.J., Marianne-Dit-Cassou,
Pierre Jean, K., Mougin-Damour, Katia, Y., Jacques-Antoine, Yves, L., Filleul, Laurent
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54950783600; 7005250308; 6602759168; 56532087000; 56041971700; 56532094300;
6701741423

Health impact assessment of cyclone bejisa in reunion Island (France) using syndromic
surveillance

(2015) *Prehospital and Disaster Medicine*, 30 (2), pp. 137 - 144

DOI: 10.1017/S1049023X15000163

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329) DOCUMENT TYPE: Article

J.H., Diaz, James Henry

AUTHOR FULL NAMES: Diaz, James Henry (57214434480)

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Rodent-borne infectious disease outbreaks after flooding disasters: Epidemiology,
management, and prevention

(2015) *American journal of disaster medicine*, 10 (3), pp. 259 - 267

DOI: 10.5055/ajdm.2015.0207

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330) DOCUMENT TYPE: Article

C., Lin, Chunyu, T.C., Chen, Tun Chieh, C.Y., Dai, Chia Yen, M., Yu, Minglung, P.L.,
Lu, Po Liangs, J., Yen, Jenghsien, Y.H., Chen, Yen Hsu

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47961108100; 24329508400; 57141624500; 7404272543; 57141463400; 7202000077;
7601434795

Serological investigation to identify risk factors for post-flood infectious diseases: A longitudinal survey among people displaced by Typhoon Morakot in Taiwan
(2015) *BMJ Open*, 5 (5), art. no. e007008

DOI: 10.1136/bmjopen-2014-007008

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[84930221969&doi=10.1136%2Fbmjopen-2014-](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-84930221969&doi=10.1136%2Fbmjopen-2014-007008&partnerID=40&md5=0e72392d917c8851103bd21e2bc126f5)

[007008&partnerID=40&md5=0e72392d917c8851103bd21e2bc126f5](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-84930221969&doi=10.1136%2Fbmjopen-2014-007008&partnerID=40&md5=0e72392d917c8851103bd21e2bc126f5)

331) DOCUMENT TYPE: Article

OPEN ACCESS: ALL OPEN ACCESS; GOLD OPEN ACCESS; GREEN FINAL OPEN ACCESS; GREEN OPEN ACCESS

L.J., McIver, Lachlan J., M., Hashizume, Masahiro, H., Kim, Ho, Y., Honda, Yasushi, M.E., Pretrick, Moses E., S.N., Iddings, Steven Ned, B.I., Pavlin, Boris Igor

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36616340700; 7102046632; 55313739600; 56336538800; 26647826600; 15057748800;
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Assessment of climate-sensitive infectious diseases in the Federated States of Micronesia

(2015) *Tropical Medicine and Health*, 43 (1), pp. 29 - 40

DOI: 10.2149/tmh.2014-17

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[84925337203&doi=10.2149%2Ftmh.2014-](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-84925337203&doi=10.2149%2Ftmh.2014-17&partnerID=40&md5=fefe28f2db320998b878ada73ecdd009)

[17&partnerID=40&md5=fefe28f2db320998b878ada73ecdd009](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-84925337203&doi=10.2149%2Ftmh.2014-17&partnerID=40&md5=fefe28f2db320998b878ada73ecdd009)

332) DOCUMENT TYPE: Article

OPEN ACCESS: ALL OPEN ACCESS; BRONZE OPEN ACCESS; GREEN FINAL OPEN ACCESS; GREEN OPEN ACCESS

H.M., Faddy, Helen M. , C.R., Seed, Clive R., C.L., Lau, Colleen L., V.N., Racloz, Vanessa Nadine, R.L., Flower, Robert L., L.D., Smythe, Lee Douglas, M.A.A., Burns, Mary Anne A., M.F., Dohnt, Michael Francis, S.B., Craig, Scott Benjamin, R.J., Harley, Robert J.

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57216801585; 6602359324; 57002151900; 15060432500; 55449903600; 7003482425;

35271241600; 6602081980; 7201656455; 36130202800

Antibodies to *Leptospira* among blood donors in higher-risk areas of Australia:
Possible implications for transfusion safety

(2015) *Blood Transfusion*, 13 (1), pp. 32 - 36

DOI: 10.2450/2014.0012-14

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[84922311155&doi=10.2450%2F2014.0012-](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-84922311155&doi=10.2450%2F2014.0012-14&partnerID=40&md5=4e33e259995ffa0f3324e8e7fc0f4a65)

[14&partnerID=40&md5=4e33e259995ffa0f3324e8e7fc0f4a65](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-84922311155&doi=10.2450%2F2014.0012-14&partnerID=40&md5=4e33e259995ffa0f3324e8e7fc0f4a65)

333) DOCUMENT TYPE: Article

D.A., Haake, David A., P.N., Levett, Paul N.

AUTHOR FULL NAMES: Haake, David A. (7006383677); Levett, Paul N. (7005351133)

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Leptospirosis in humans

(2015) *Current Topics in Microbiology and Immunology*, 387, pp. 65 - 97

DOI: 10.1007/978-3-662-45059-8_5

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[84921782926&doi=10.1007%2F978-3-662-45059-](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-84921782926&doi=10.1007%2F978-3-662-45059-8_5&partnerID=40&md5=af47c47a4e9e2ea4b563801497884d4d)

[8_5&partnerID=40&md5=af47c47a4e9e2ea4b563801497884d4d](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-84921782926&doi=10.1007%2F978-3-662-45059-8_5&partnerID=40&md5=af47c47a4e9e2ea4b563801497884d4d)

334) DOCUMENT TYPE: Article

J.B., Baitello, João Batista, F.E.S.P., Vilela, Francisco Eduardo Silva Pinto, F.A.R.D.P.,
Arzolla, Frederico Alexandre Roccia Dal Pozzo, A.A.V., Assad, Amanda Aparecida
Vianna, S.M.B., Florsheim, Sandra Monteiro Borges, E.L., Longui, Eduardo Luiz, I.L.,
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34976164900; 56533609100; 33567594900; 56533597000; 36337637800; 24329969700;

6602794191

Ecological wood anatomy of *ocotea curucutuensis*

(2014) *IAWA Journal*, 35 (4), pp. 356 - 362

DOI: 10.1163/22941932-00000071

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[84923925320&doi=10.1163%2F22941932-](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-84923925320&doi=10.1163%2F22941932-00000071&partnerID=40&md5=5176de885cc85d7c9f35a902715aa5c4)

[00000071&partnerID=40&md5=5176de885cc85d7c9f35a902715aa5c4](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-84923925320&doi=10.1163%2F22941932-00000071&partnerID=40&md5=5176de885cc85d7c9f35a902715aa5c4)

335) DOCUMENT TYPE: Article

S., Chusri, Sarunyou, E.B., McNeil, Edward B., T., Hortiwakul, Thanaporn, B.,
Charoenmak, Boonsri, S., Sritrairatchai, Somporn, W., Santimaleeworagun, Wichai, S.,
Pattharachayakul, Sutthiporn, P., Suksanan, Paritasana, B.K., Thaisomboonsuk, Butsayu
K., R.G., Jarman, Richard G.

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48661710400; 35870443600; 55078231000; 55183921100; 55325933200; 42462360300; 6506956229; 56331718100; 8731849500; 16052947100

Single dosage of doxycycline for prophylaxis against leptospiral infection and leptospirosis during urban flooding in southern Thailand: A non-randomized controlled trial

(2014) *Journal of Infection and Chemotherapy*, 20 (11), pp. 709 - 715

DOI: 10.1016/j.jiac.2014.07.016

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[84908221478&doi=10.1016%2Fj.jiac.2014.07.016&partnerID=40&md5=89afc0acc01b478991c525a76bfde845](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-84908221478&doi=10.1016%2Fj.jiac.2014.07.016&partnerID=40&md5=89afc0acc01b478991c525a76bfde845)

336) DOCUMENT TYPE: Article

R., Gracie, Renata, C., Barcellos, Christovam, M.A.F.M., Magalhães, Mônica Avelar Figueiredo Mafra, R., Souza-Santos, Reinaldo, P.R., Guimarães Barrocas, Paulo Rubens

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Santos, Reinaldo (12445696100); Guimarães Barrocas, Paulo Rubens (8223382900)

13205380200; 7003540827; 57208596929; 12445696100; 8223382900

Geographical scale effects on the analysis of leptospirosis determinants

(2014) *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 11 (10), pp. 10366 - 10383

DOI: 10.3390/ijerph111010366

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[84908337124&doi=10.3390%2Fijerph111010366&partnerID=40&md5=8435386aca87b1ff5339dd6c48624dd6](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-84908337124&doi=10.3390%2Fijerph111010366&partnerID=40&md5=8435386aca87b1ff5339dd6c48624dd6)

337) DOCUMENT TYPE: Article

OPEN ACCESS: ALL OPEN ACCESS; GOLD OPEN ACCESS; GREEN ACCEPTED OPEN ACCESS; GREEN FINAL OPEN ACCESS; GREEN OPEN ACCESS

K., Su, Kuanjen, Y.C., Yeh, Yen Cheng, R., Ben, Renjy

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Fulminant leptospirosis: A case report and review of the literature

(2014) *Journal of Internal Medicine of Taiwan*, 25 (5), pp. 357 - 361

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[84921768019&partnerID=40&md5=42a3b5a3af42d2a333020c3828d69e94](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-84921768019&partnerID=40&md5=42a3b5a3af42d2a333020c3828d69e94)

338) DOCUMENT TYPE: Article

C., Ridoutt, C., A., Lee, A., B.J., Moloney, Barbara J., P., Massey, Pd, N.R., Charman, N. R., D., Jordan, D.

AUTHOR FULL NAMES: Ridoutt, C. (57195450814); Lee, A. (59112266900); Moloney, Barbara J. (23985497000); Massey, Pd (57195455453); Charman, N. R. (55907720600); Jordan, D. (58426718500)

57195450814; 59112266900; 23985497000; 57195455453; 55907720600; 58426718500

Detection of brucellosis and leptospirosis in feral pigs in New South Wales

(2014) Australian Veterinary Journal, 92 (9), pp. 343 - 347

DOI: 10.1111/avj.12203

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[85027923176&doi=10.1111%2Favj.12203&partnerID=40&md5=66744d7b344e3268f43dcea50891d5f4](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85027923176&doi=10.1111%2Favj.12203&partnerID=40&md5=66744d7b344e3268f43dcea50891d5f4)

339) DOCUMENT TYPE: Article

A., Major, Andrea, A., Schweighauser, Ariane, T., Francey, Thierry

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Increasing incidence of canine leptospirosis in Switzerland

(2014) International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health, 11 (7), pp.

7242 - 7260

DOI: 10.3390/ijerph110707242

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[84904437928&doi=10.3390%2Fijerph110707242&partnerID=40&md5=53603bf2a47a630874367a499ba3694c](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-84904437928&doi=10.3390%2Fijerph110707242&partnerID=40&md5=53603bf2a47a630874367a499ba3694c)

340) DOCUMENT TYPE: Article

OPEN ACCESS: ALL OPEN ACCESS; GOLD OPEN ACCESS; GREEN ACCEPTED

OPEN ACCESS; GREEN FINAL OPEN ACCESS; GREEN OPEN ACCESS

C.A.R., Pereira, Carlos Alexandre Rodrigues, M.M.D.L., Barata, Martha Macedo De Lima, A.G.M., Trigo, Aline Guimarães Monteiro

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Social cost of leptospirosis cases attributed to the 2011 disaster striking Nova Friburgo, Brazil

(2014) International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health, 11 (4), pp.

4140 - 4157

DOI: 10.3390/ijerph110404140

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[84898851369&doi=10.3390%2Fijerph110404140&partnerID=40&md5=a32830819fc9abfb69330257827f7c1c](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-84898851369&doi=10.3390%2Fijerph110404140&partnerID=40&md5=a32830819fc9abfb69330257827f7c1c)

341) DOCUMENT TYPE: Article

OPEN ACCESS: ALL OPEN ACCESS; GOLD OPEN ACCESS; GREEN ACCEPTED OPEN ACCESS; GREEN FINAL OPEN ACCESS; GREEN OPEN ACCESS

J., Rügamer, J., R., Kaaden, Rainer, W., Mohren, W.

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Leptospirosis after refurbishment of old buildings

(2014) Deutsche Medizinische Wochenschrift, 139 (9), pp. 427 - 429

DOI: 10.1055/s-0033-1360095

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342) DOCUMENT TYPE: Article

K., Chan, Kunwei, Y., Hsu, Yunhsiu, W., Hu, Weiling, M., Pan, Mingjeng, J.M., Lai, Jyhmirn Mirn, K., Huang, Kwoching, S., Chou, Shihjen

AUTHOR FULL NAMES: Chan, Kunwei (35174113600); Hsu, Yunhsiu (56038987700); Hu, Weiling (56039083800); Pan, Mingjeng (7202544910); Lai, Jyhmirn Mirn (54407099100); Huang, Kwoching (14062139600); Chou, Shihjen (57137465000)

35174113600; 56038987700; 56039083800; 7202544910; 54407099100; 14062139600;

57137465000

Serological and PCR detection of feline *Leptospira* in Southern Taiwan

(2014) Vector-Borne and Zoonotic Diseases, 14 (2), pp. 118 - 123

DOI: 10.1089/vbz.2013.1324

[https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-84894166130&doi=10.1089%2Fvbz.2013.1324&partnerID=40&md5=c3dc5196aa917ff0a5ed9dc533f021e5)

[84894166130&doi=10.1089%2Fvbz.2013.1324&partnerID=40&md5=c3dc5196aa917ff0a5ed9dc533f021e5](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-84894166130&doi=10.1089%2Fvbz.2013.1324&partnerID=40&md5=c3dc5196aa917ff0a5ed9dc533f021e5)

343) DOCUMENT TYPE: Article

F., Pagés, Frédéric, D., Polycarpe, Dominique, J.S., DeHecq, Jean Sébastien, M., Picardeau, Mathieu, N., Caillère, Nadège, M.C., Jaffar-Bandjee, Marie Christine, A., Michault, Alain, L., Filleul, Laurent

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7005250308; 6507083096; 15018988800; 6701694004; 14819159200; 6602390556;

7004254813; 6701741423

7005250308; 6507083096; 15018988800; 6701694004; 14819159200; 6602390556;

7004254813; 6701741423

Human leptospirosis on Reunion Island: Past and current burden

(2014) International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health, 11 (1), pp. 968 - 982

968 - 982

DOI: 10.3390/ijerph110100968

<https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-84892384422&doi=10.3390%2Fijerph110100968&partnerID=40&md5=228e2b6e6d18827a88ec231d0cf8d74c>

344) 3DOCUMENT TYPE: Article

OPEN ACCESS: ALL OPEN ACCESS; GOLD OPEN ACCESS; GREEN FINAL OPEN ACCESS; GREEN OPEN ACCESS

L.J., McIver, Lachlan J., V.S., Chan, Vibol S., K.J., Bowen, Kathryn J., S.N., Iddings, Steven Ned, K., Hero, Kol, P.P., Raingsey, Piseth P.

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36616340700; 56460849500; 36806415600; 15057748800; 57188768641; 36519727700

Review of Climate Change and Water-Related Diseases in Cambodia and Findings from Stakeholder Knowledge Assessments

(2014) Asia-Pacific Journal of Public Health, 28, pp. 49 - 58

DOI: 10.1177/1010539514558059

<https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-84962860775&doi=10.1177%2F1010539514558059&partnerID=40&md5=450e2910b0b3f9c465ab5b3edda85497>

345) DOCUMENT TYPE: Article

D., Dos Santos, Daniel, M.D.R., Toledo Filho, Manoel Da Rocha

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Study of meteorological variable influences on hospital admissions in maceio-al during the 1998-2006 period Estudo sobre a influência de variáveis meteorológicas em internações hospitalares em maceió-al, durante o período 1998 a 2006

(2014) Revista Brasileira de Meteorologia, 29 (3), pp. 457 - 467

DOI: 10.1590/0102-778620110324

<https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-84940329243&doi=10.1590%2F0102-778620110324&partnerID=40&md5=db77a0aaa9930149e5c9d1724af9b855>

346) DOCUMENT TYPE: Article

OPEN ACCESS: ALL OPEN ACCESS; GOLD OPEN ACCESS; GREEN ACCEPTED OPEN ACCESS; GREEN FINAL OPEN ACCESS; GREEN OPEN ACCESS

T., Shafighi, Toba, T., Zahraei-Salehi, Taghi, G.R., Abdollahpour, Gholamreza R., L., Asadpour, Leila, H.A., Akbarein, Hesameddin Aldin, A., Salehzadeh, Ali

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58883946600; 8929122400; 7801422582; 36699334100; 36095760800; 24464669900

Molecular detection of *Leptospira* spp. in the urine of cattle in northern Iran
(2014) *Iranian Journal of Veterinary Research*, 15 (4), pp. 402 - 405

[https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-84922946533&partnerID=40&md5=9b25c34749a220c1845c2165010dfc12)

[84922946533&partnerID=40&md5=9b25c34749a220c1845c2165010dfc12](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-84922946533&partnerID=40&md5=9b25c34749a220c1845c2165010dfc12)

347) DOCUMENT TYPE: Article

A., Wójcik-Fatla, Angelina, V., Zając, Violetta, B., Wasieński, Bernard, J., Sroka, Jacek, E.,
Cisak, Ewa, A., Sawczyn-Domańska, Anna, J., Dutkiewicz, Jacek

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8612441100; 25923213200; 18937734400; 7004016099; 6601970442; 55295824200;
7103201691

Occurrence of *Leptospira* DNA in water and soil samples collected in eastern Poland
(2014) *Annals of Agricultural and Environmental Medicine*, 21 (4), pp. 730 - 732

DOI: 10.5604/12321966.1129924

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[84915737760&doi=10.5604%2F12321966.1129924&partnerID=40&md5=3dc9c4371a495390291331bc424d1d89](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-84915737760&doi=10.5604%2F12321966.1129924&partnerID=40&md5=3dc9c4371a495390291331bc424d1d89)

348) DOCUMENT TYPE: Article

OPEN ACCESS: ALL OPEN ACCESS; GOLD OPEN ACCESS; GREEN ACCEPTED
OPEN ACCESS; GREEN OPEN ACCESS

M., Saito, Mitsumasa, S., Miyahara, Satoshi, S.Y.A.M., Villanueva, Sharon Yvette
Angelina M., N., Aramaki, Natsumi, M., Ikejiri, Mami, Y., Kobayashi, Yoshie, J.P.,
Guevarra, Jonathan P., T., Masuzawa, Toshiyuki, N.G., Gloriani, Nina Gonzales, Y.,
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7404972747; 7101941112; 7004327679; 56396797400; 56396476000; 56395802600;
56076826900; 7202640565; 36080339500; 56396988500

PCR and culture identification of pathogenic *Leptospira* spp. from coastal soil in leyte,
Philippines, after a storm surge during super Typhoon Haiyan (Yolanda)

(2014) *Applied and Environmental Microbiology*, 80 (22), pp. 6926 - 6932

DOI: 10.1128/AEM.02568-14

[https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-84908284945&doi=10.1128%2FAEM.02568-14&partnerID=40&md5=bbed6b6b7ca15e8cad38ceea262183e4)

[84908284945&doi=10.1128%2FAEM.02568-](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-84908284945&doi=10.1128%2FAEM.02568-14&partnerID=40&md5=bbed6b6b7ca15e8cad38ceea262183e4)

[14&partnerID=40&md5=bbed6b6b7ca15e8cad38ceea262183e4](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-84908284945&doi=10.1128%2FAEM.02568-14&partnerID=40&md5=bbed6b6b7ca15e8cad38ceea262183e4)

349) DOCUMENT TYPE: Article

OPEN ACCESS: ALL OPEN ACCESS; BRONZE OPEN ACCESS; GREEN FINAL OPEN ACCESS; GREEN OPEN ACCESS

M.A.P., Finger, Mariane Angélica Pommerening, I.R., De Barros Filho, Ivan Roque, C.M., Leutenegger, Christian M., M.M., Estrada, Marko M., L.S., Ullmann, Leila S., H., Langoni, Hélio, M., Kikuti, Mariana, P.T., Dornbush, Peterson Triches, I., Deconto, Ivan, A.W., Biondo, Alexander Welker

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Serological and molecular survey of *Leptospira* spp. among cart horses from an endemic area of human leptospirosis in Curitiba, Southern Brazil Inquérito sorológico e molecular de *Leptospira* spp. em cavalos carroceiros de área endêmica para leptospirose humana em Curitiba, Sul do Brasil

(2014) Revista do Instituto de Medicina Tropical de Sao Paulo, 56 (6), pp. 473 - 476

DOI: 10.1590/S0036-46652014000600003

[https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-84908208715&doi=10.1590%2FS0036-46652014000600003&partnerID=40&md5=f44e24e79c362fa34031a7953ff6cf61)

[84908208715&doi=10.1590%2FS0036-](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-84908208715&doi=10.1590%2FS0036-46652014000600003&partnerID=40&md5=f44e24e79c362fa34031a7953ff6cf61)

[46652014000600003&partnerID=40&md5=f44e24e79c362fa34031a7953ff6cf61](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-84908208715&doi=10.1590%2FS0036-46652014000600003&partnerID=40&md5=f44e24e79c362fa34031a7953ff6cf61)

350) DOCUMENT TYPE: Article

OPEN ACCESS: ALL OPEN ACCESS; GOLD OPEN ACCESS; GREEN ACCEPTED OPEN ACCESS; GREEN FINAL OPEN ACCESS; GREEN OPEN ACCESS

R.M., Guimarães, Raphael Mendonça, O.G., Gonçalves Cruz, Oswaldo Gonçalves, V.G., Parreira, Viviane Gomes, M.L., Mazoto, Máira Lopes, J.D., Vieira, Juliana Dias, C.I.R., Froes-Asmus, Carmen Ildes Rodrigues

AUTHOR FULL NAMES: Guimarães, Raphael Mendonça (23134500400); Gonçalves Cruz, Oswaldo Gonçalves (23989979100); Parreira, Viviane Gomes (55930426900); Mazoto, Máira Lopes (56348959600); Vieira, Juliana Dias (56348909600); Froes-Asmus, Carmen Ildes Rodrigues (57222765121) 23134500400; 23989979100; 55930426900; 56348959600; 56348909600; 57222765121

Temporal analysis of the relationship between leptospirosis and the occurrence of flooding due to rainfall in the city of Rio de Janeiro, Brazil, 2007-2012 Análise temporal da relação entre leptospirose e ocorrência de inundações por chuvas no município do Rio de Janeiro, Brasil, 2007-2012

(2014) Ciencia e Saude Coletiva, 19 (9), pp. 3683 - 3692

DOI: 10.1590/1413-81232014199.06432014

[https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-84906901908&doi=10.1590%2F1413-81232014199.06432014&partnerID=40&md5=1f6c46de046da1eeafe3a5e4ed07cf00)

[84906901908&doi=10.1590%2F1413-](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-84906901908&doi=10.1590%2F1413-81232014199.06432014&partnerID=40&md5=1f6c46de046da1eeafe3a5e4ed07cf00)

[81232014199.06432014&partnerID=40&md5=1f6c46de046da1eeafe3a5e4ed07cf00](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-84906901908&doi=10.1590%2F1413-81232014199.06432014&partnerID=40&md5=1f6c46de046da1eeafe3a5e4ed07cf00)

351) DOCUMENT TYPE: Article

OPEN ACCESS: ALL OPEN ACCESS; GOLD OPEN ACCESS; GREEN ACCEPTED OPEN ACCESS; GREEN OPEN ACCESS

N.J., Dahanayaka, Niroshana Jathun, S.B., Agampodi, Suneth Buddhika, A.K., Bandaranayaka, Anoma K., S., Priyankara, Sumudu, J.M., Vinetz, Joshep M.
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54883790800; 23017863100; 56032200400; 56031247500; 59022012100
Hantavirus infection mimicking leptospirosis: How long are we going to rely on clinical suspicion?
(2014) *Journal of Infection in Developing Countries*, 8 (8), pp. 1072 - 1075
DOI: 10.3855/jidc.4115
<https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-84906055853&doi=10.3855%2Fjidc.4115&partnerID=40&md5=50d847030dc8526d5018d58bda61b972>

352) DOCUMENT TYPE: Article

OPEN ACCESS: ALL OPEN ACCESS; GOLD OPEN ACCESS; GREEN ACCEPTED OPEN ACCESS; GREEN OPEN ACCESS

P.B., Allwood, Paul B., C.A., Muñoz-Zanzi, Claudia A., M., Chang, Martin, P.D., Brown, Paul Dean
AUTHOR FULL NAMES: Allwood, Paul B. (6602827175); Muñoz-Zanzi, Claudia A. (6602544065); Chang, Martin (56139396500); Brown, Paul Dean (57212264458)
6602827175; 6602544065; 56139396500; 57212264458
Knowledge, perceptions, and environmental risk factors among Jamaican households with a history of leptospirosis
(2014) *Journal of Infection and Public Health*, 7 (4), pp. 314 - 322
DOI: 10.1016/j.jiph.2014.03.004
<https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-84904049026&doi=10.1016%2Fj.jiph.2014.03.004&partnerID=40&md5=98516c0990dfdb62f37857302d180e32>

353) DOCUMENT TYPE: Article

OPEN ACCESS: ALL OPEN ACCESS; BRONZE OPEN ACCESS

A., Aragón-Martínez, Arianna, L.D., Olivera-Gómez, León David, D., Jiménez-Domínguez, Darwin
AUTHOR FULL NAMES: Aragón-Martínez, Arianna (56259005000); Olivera-Gómez, León David (6505976988); Jiménez-Domínguez, Darwin (56258776300)
56259005000; 6505976988; 56258776300
Seasonal prevalence of antibodies to *Leptospira Interrogans* in antillean manatees from a landlocked lake in Tabasco, Mexico
(2014) *Journal of Wildlife Diseases*, 50 (3), pp. 505 - 511
DOI: 10.7589/2013-05-102

<https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-84903980728&doi=10.7589%2F2013-05-102&partnerID=40&md5=bf93054339969beb08552240ef518bda>

354) DOCUMENT TYPE: Article

OPEN ACCESS: ALL OPEN ACCESS; BRONZE OPEN ACCESS

S.J., Prior, Sarah Jane, S.B., Craig, Scott Benjamin, G.C., Graham, Glenn Charles, B.R., Blair, Barry R., M.A.A., Burns, Mary Anne A., S.L., Weier, Steven L., T.A.N., Collet, Trudi Anne Nne, D.B., McKay, David B.

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57200657503; 7201656455; 26531009000; 13105979800; 35271241600; 55371712400; 36898251800; 56612838700

The emergence of *Leptospira borgpetersenii* serovar Arborea as the dominant infecting serovar following the summer of natural disasters in Queensland, Australia 2011 (2014) *Tropical Biomedicine*, 31 (2), pp. 281 - 285

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[84901653966&partnerID=40&md5=67947ca348234d58240d14c3035751b0](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-84901653966&partnerID=40&md5=67947ca348234d58240d14c3035751b0)

355) DOCUMENT TYPE: Article

I., Golden, Isaac, G.G., Bracho, Gustavo G.

AUTHOR FULL NAMES: Golden, Isaac (54787489700); Bracho, Gustavo G. (12791912700)

54787489700; 12791912700

A Reevaluation of the Effectiveness of Homoeoprophylaxis Against Leptospirosis in Cuba in 2007 and 2008

(2014) *Journal of Evidence-Based Complementary and Alternative Medicine*, 19 (3), pp. 155 - 160

DOI: 10.1177/2156587214525402

[https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-84901609715&doi=10.1177%2F2156587214525402&partnerID=40&md5=193bee6cd4eb3926b4ee72d561669b82)

[84901609715&doi=10.1177%2F2156587214525402&partnerID=40&md5=193bee6cd4eb3926b4ee72d561669b82](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-84901609715&doi=10.1177%2F2156587214525402&partnerID=40&md5=193bee6cd4eb3926b4ee72d561669b82)

356) DOCUMENT TYPE: Article

OPEN ACCESS: ALL OPEN ACCESS; BRONZE OPEN ACCESS

R.B.O., Filho, Ruy Brayner Oliveira, K.C., Malta, Karla Campos, V.L.D.A., Santana, Vânia Lúcia De Assis, M.H.V., Harrop, Mabel Hanna Vance, D.T., Stipp, Danilo Tancler, D.F., Brandespim, Daniel Friguglietti, R.A., Mota, Rinaldo Aparecido, J.W., Pinheiro Junior, José Wilton

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Friguglietti (44960897200); Mota, Rinaldo Aparecido (7005490492); Pinheiro Junior, José Wilton (25951815400)
56184255000; 55524033500; 24765190600; 55358069400; 11338952800; 44960897200;
7005490492; 25951815400

Spatial characterization of *Leptospira* spp. infection in equids from the Brejo Paraibano micro-region in Brazil

(2014) *Geospatial Health*, 8 (2), pp. 463 - 469

DOI: 10.4081/gh.2014.35

[https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-84901591647&doi=10.4081%2Fgh.2014.35&partnerID=40&md5=f91a8cf0dc222aa8c9e079fedf067a3d)

[84901591647&doi=10.4081%2Fgh.2014.35&partnerID=40&md5=f91a8cf0dc222aa8c9e079fedf067a3d](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-84901591647&doi=10.4081%2Fgh.2014.35&partnerID=40&md5=f91a8cf0dc222aa8c9e079fedf067a3d)

357) DOCUMENT TYPE: Article

OPEN ACCESS: ALL OPEN ACCESS; GOLD OPEN ACCESS; GREEN ACCEPTED OPEN ACCESS; GREEN OPEN ACCESS

M., Usuzawa, Motoki, E.F.O., Telan, Elizabeth Freda Omengan, R.L., Kawano, Razel L., C.S., Dizon, Carmela S., B., Alisjahbana, Bacti, Y., Ashino, Yugo, S., Egawa, Shinichi, M., Fukumoto, Manabu, T., Izumi, Takako, Y., Ono, Yuichi

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24069599200; 26768418300; 56176866700; 49361078800; 6506944516; 7003907296;

35430817900; 7202935320; 56177150900; 55741741800

Awareness of disaster reduction frameworks and risk perception of natural disaster: A questionnaire survey among Philippine and Indonesian health care personnel and public health students

(2014) *Tohoku Journal of Experimental Medicine*, 233 (1), pp. 43 - 48

DOI: 10.1620/tjem.233.43

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[84901289264&doi=10.1620%2Ftjem.233.43&partnerID=40&md5=56e4ae3cf7769cf75f5a798f2c526dd7](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-84901289264&doi=10.1620%2Ftjem.233.43&partnerID=40&md5=56e4ae3cf7769cf75f5a798f2c526dd7)

358) DOCUMENT TYPE: Article

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D.M., Weinberger, Daniel Martin, N., Baroux, Noémie, J.P., Grangeon, Jean Paul, A.I., Ko, Albert I., C., Goarant, Cyrille

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El Niño Southern Oscillation and Leptospirosis Outbreaks in New Caledonia

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359) DOCUMENT TYPE: Article

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X., Zhang, Xu, L., Peng, Liangbin, W., Liu, Wendong, L., Fan, Lirui, Q., Zhang, Qi, G., Chen, Guangjie, P., He, Pan, R., Wu, Ruixiao, A., Liu, Anping, Y., Yang, Yexun
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57249097500; 37029001000; 43161100500; 43160992700; 57204563685; 43160970900; 56088534100; 55469437700; 55459860700; 56088850700

Response of primary vectors and related diseases to impoundment by the Three Gorges Dam

(2014) Tropical Medicine and International Health, 19 (4), pp. 440 - 449

DOI: 10.1111/tmi.12272

<https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-84897070411&doi=10.1111%2Ftmi.12272&partnerID=40&md5=b7ccea827b762ca33f58fb20452514d>

360) DOCUMENT TYPE: Article

C.A., Muñoz-Zanzi, Claudia A., M.R., Mason, Meghan R., C.A., Encina, Carolina A., M., Gonzalez, Marcelo, S.S., Berg, Sergey S.
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6602544065; 56067412500; 35073773100; 57198487457; 56067244900

Household characteristics associated with rodent presence and Leptospira infection in rural and urban communities from Southern Chile

(2014) American Journal of Tropical Medicine and Hygiene, 90 (3), pp. 497 - 506

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361) DOCUMENT TYPE: Article

OPEN ACCESS: ALL OPEN ACCESS; BRONZE OPEN ACCESS; GREEN FINAL OPEN ACCESS; GREEN OPEN ACCESS

S.B., Agampodi, Suneth Buddhika, N.J., Dahanayaka, Niroshana Jathun, A.K., Bandaranayaka, Anoma K., M.H.M.T.S., Perera, Manoj H.M.T.S., S., Priyankara,

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23017863100; 54883790800; 56032200400; 57198137180; 56031247500; 55645196600; 7004106625; 7003519222

Regional Differences of Leptospirosis in Sri Lanka: Observations from a Flood-Associated Outbreak in 2011

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[84893718542&doi=10.1371%2Fjournal.pntd.0002626&partnerID=40&md5=25a03d43edbcbdcd905d890cd6ece4af](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-84893718542&doi=10.1371%2Fjournal.pntd.0002626&partnerID=40&md5=25a03d43edbcbdcd905d890cd6ece4af)

362) DOCUMENT TYPE: Article

OPEN ACCESS: ALL OPEN ACCESS; GOLD OPEN ACCESS; GREEN ACCEPTED OPEN ACCESS; GREEN FINAL OPEN ACCESS; GREEN OPEN ACCESS

A., Calvo-Cano, Antonia, E., Aldasoro, Edelweiss, M.F., Ramírez, M. F., M.J., Martínez, Miguel J., A., Requena-Méndez, A., J., Gascon, Joaquim

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56009052500; 50460997800; 7201568243; 56890159100; 57203667273; 57221993254

Two cases of laboratory-confirmed leptospirosis in travellers returning to Spain from Thailand, September 2013

(2014) Eurosurveillance, 19 (2)

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[https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-84892777639&doi=10.2807%2F1560-7917.ES2014.19.2.20675&partnerID=40&md5=dad5e8566ec51815c74396fa21e990c8)

[84892777639&doi=10.2807%2F1560-](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-84892777639&doi=10.2807%2F1560-7917.ES2014.19.2.20675&partnerID=40&md5=dad5e8566ec51815c74396fa21e990c8)

[7917.ES2014.19.2.20675&partnerID=40&md5=dad5e8566ec51815c74396fa21e990c8](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-84892777639&doi=10.2807%2F1560-7917.ES2014.19.2.20675&partnerID=40&md5=dad5e8566ec51815c74396fa21e990c8)

363) DOCUMENT TYPE: Article

OPEN ACCESS: ALL OPEN ACCESS; GOLD OPEN ACCESS; GREEN ACCEPTED OPEN ACCESS; GREEN OPEN ACCESS

F., Costa, Federico, F.H., Porter, Fleur Helena, G., Rodrigues, Gorete, H., Farias, Helena, M.T., de Faria, Marcus Tucunduva, E.A., Wunder, Elsie Augusto, L.M., Osikowicz, Lynn M., M.Y., Kosoy, Michael Ye, M.G., Reis, Mitermayer G., A.I., Ko, Albert I.

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55378617300; 55884179700; 55884438700; 55885108600; 55987085400; 14008124800; 55353997500; 6701343165; 35459915300; 7007018347

Infections by *Leptospira interrogans*, seoul virus, and bartonella spp. among norway rats (*rattus norvegicus*) from the Urban slum environment in Brazil

(2014) Vector-Borne and Zoonotic Diseases, 14 (1), pp. 33 - 40

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[84891677932&doi=10.1089%2Fvbz.2013.1378&partnerID=40&md5=6856fa110f98c48c0d574bbc3015ecb7](https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-84891677932&doi=10.1089%2Fvbz.2013.1378&partnerID=40&md5=6856fa110f98c48c0d574bbc3015ecb7)

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